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"An Investigation in to the relationship between brand awareness and purchasing intention,
recommending of the suitable sales strategy for a mid-size event-based company.

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Declaration

I, Gaurav Aggarwal, hereby declare that this thesis is entirely my own work and was carried per the regulation of the University of the West of Scotland. I hereby declare that any additional source has been fully cited. This thesis has not been previously submitted to any university for the award of any degree or other similar titles of recognition.

Gaurav Aggarwal,

JUNE 2021.

ABSTRACT

The ultimate aim of many firms' is to gain maximum profit. It is only possible when they can understand the needs and requirements of customers and deliver those services accordingly. Brand values of customers towards companies increases when the set of requirements listed by service users are satisfied. The rate of competition has risen tremendously in all sectors. Firms make use of strategies so that they attract more and more customers. The focus is on identifying the factors that affect customers' purchase intention concerning event management.

To conduct the research, both primary and secondary methods were used by exploring the use of pragmatism. More specifically, 5 different event management firms are selected from the UK. From each of these companies, 1 manager and 20 customers were selected from each company. So, in total, there were 5 managers and 100 customers with whom interviews and questionnaires were conducted. These respondents were selected that were helpful enough to provide adequate information for the research topic.

From the findings, the analysis showed that an individual's perception is positive for the services and products when a firm has high brand recognition. Further, a primary focus needs to be made on the high quality of goods and services by organisations to raise brand loyalty among customers.

So, the study's outcome is that there is a relationship between brand awareness and customer purchase intention. Moreover, the factors related to branding impact on purchase power of customers. Here, factors such as packaging, brand, familiarity, etc., influence purchase intention.

Keywords- Customer intention,Pragmatism, purchase, brand management, competition, brand loyalty.

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Chapter 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

Management of an event is a crucial task that requires the active attention of parties associated with the same to render a perfect quality of services. Project management is a kind of approach under which varied activities are scheduled regarding the cost and time involved. That proves effective by integrating all business activities and support management to carry out their operation activities effectively. It is vital to shedding light on brand awareness to increase the purchase intention of customers. This is because, if a customer is familiar with a particular brand, this aids to increase the attention of consumers and create word of mouth recommendation (Mazodier and Merunka, 2012). This proves to be effective for business to increase the overall rate of return and raises the satisfaction level of customers.

Some key factors aid in promoting the customer's purchase decision to a great extent: factors such as brand, social media and word of mouth, and conversations. Other factors such as intelligence, creativeness, and trustworthiness influence buyers to purchase a particular product or service. This, in turn, becomes easy to grab their attention and ensure their inclusion in the process of repeat purchase decision (Chang and Chen, 2014). It indicates a clear link between a particular brand and the repeat purchase decision of customers. Also, parties show their interest in the brands by seeing advertisements and other related strategies. The purchasing decisions of buyers are affected, and due to that overall sales performance of the company gets influenced. This is critical because these factors' impact should be considered to improve the organisation's performance.

Along with this, brand awareness impacts the consumer's purchasing decisions about the business. Many external and internal elements influence the buying decisions and because the purchase of products and services in the market gets affected. Advice and recommendations given by friends and family members affect the thought process of the buyer.

Companies integrate customer-facing activities so that it becomes easy to provide them with quick information related to products and services. Not only this but with the help of customer-focused activities, the firm gains trust. Furthermore, online targeting strategies are applied by marketers to make it possible for customers to be effectively connected with the business and getting information regarding the varied kind of products and services: for example, information Websites and public relations (PR) as well as loyalty programmes (Aaker and

Joachimsthaler, 2012). The business-like Ticket Desk takes initiatives to attract clients and make them aware of new offerings of the business. In this way, corporations gain the attraction of buyers and make it possible for them to get good quality services and an appropriate business environment. Also, companies develop the expertise of personnel, enabling them to focus on the products and services of the corporation (Hafeez and et al., 2016). This proves to be influential in determining the long-term success and development of the company.

Branding of an event has its importance, such as promotion, creating brand strategy and setting it up for success. In this manner, event management companies effectively promote their services just with the help of branding (Kalafatis, 2016). It enables a firm to spread the information related to event management organisation and makes customers aware of the importance of the particular brand. Furthermore, brand awareness is considered the dominant choice tactic among buyers. However, some customers prefer a brand just because of its involvement and emotional appeal (Balakrishnan, Nekhili and Lewis, 2011). So, the Customer does not consider the same item in terms of price and quality due to their focus on brand only. Therefore, it becomes essential for an organisation to promote the given brand and accordingly cater to their customer's requirement appropriate for introducing several kinds of promotional tools and technologies (Zhao, Sun and Kakuda 2017).

The present investigation is based on Ticket Desk companies associated with several kinds of West End that show currency exchange and concert tickets and tour packages. This firm has contracts with several companies, such as 'Big Bus' and 'Golden Tours', and secondary agents, to increase revenue and meet the expectations of all related stakeholders in an effective manner (Andaleeb, 2016). The organisation is situated in Central London, and customer footfalls are more than 400 customers every day. This reflects the higher sales turnover for the business and attracts more and more customers because of the excellent quality of services. The company contacts different suppliers or parties such as TUI and thetrainline.com, and Saga (Herzog, Lepa and Egermann, 2016). Cultural exhibitions and sightseeing tend to form an integral part of our product range. This makes it easy to offer competitive prices (Osakwe, Chovancova and Ogbonna, 2016). Also, restaurant packages and group rates are charged to provide a rich experience for the users.

Moreover, the Ticket Desk provides services for several tourist attractions, such as the London Zoo and London Eye and London Aquarium (Booth and Matic, 2011), the Tower of London, and

the London Dungeon. Thus, the firm is working in partnership with many other parties through which it becomes easy to organise the most appropriate event following different parties. It proves to be effective for deriving a higher level of satisfaction among various parties and retains them for a longer time (Pickering, 2017). In addition to this, a sightseeing tour of the centre includes Charing Cross Island and Leicester Square Station and the Criterion Theatre. These attractions remain open per the convenience of visitors, and provides them with an appropriate kind of service package and also helps them to organise their events in a most effective manner (Shaltoni, 2017).

Feedback taken from consumers aids in making positive improvements in the business's overall performance, and weak performing areas can be easily identified. Comment card systems can also be used so that difficulties and issues faced by the consumers can be evaluated, and based on that, strategies and action plans can be formed (Liu, et al., 2016). The event management sector is facing enormous challenges and competition. Therefore, strategic approaches must be made to gain a competitive advantage for business (Padfield and et al., 2016). Moreover, strategies and action plans used by rival firms can also be identified so that better, more effective measures can be taken for meeting the challenges from the rival firms. The satisfaction level of consumers is essential so that more consumers can be added to the business and potential buyers can be identified. That will help ensure growth and success for the enterprise (Nguyen and et al., 2016).

The event management sector sheds light on promoting their services and giving a higher level of satisfaction among customers. It is considered a practical aspect whereby the business's competitive edge is created (Green, 2016). For this purpose, the focus is laid on quality, price and other related aspects. Ticket Desk, the event management firm, follows its structured approach with the customers' specific requirements taken into account, and provide services accordingly. It can be critically evaluated that if the business does not follow the most appropriate approach, then the company will pay the cost in terms of higher loss (Brimah and Tweneboah-Koduah, 2011). Extra benefits associated with service delivery are considered by the users or corporation from which customer satisfaction can be significantly increased (Osakwe, Chovancova and Ogbonna. 2016). It contributes towards generating a positive attitude among customers and making them aware of a particular brand. Brand awareness among customers indicates that consumers possess the necessary knowledge regarding the brand (Pickering, 2017).

The big reason corporations operating in the event management industry prepare the emotional communication package to create a positive affective response (Bruhn, Schoenmueller and Schäfer, 2012). It leads to an increase in their loyalty towards the brand. Customers prefer the brand which attracts them and meets their requirement to a great extent. Also, good interaction with their relatives is essential to have positive word of mouth in the marketplace (Shaltoni, 2017).

Advice given by friends and family members plays a vital role in influencing the thought process of buyers. If friends give positive recommendations, family members and relatives will encourage the buyer to purchase the products offered by the organisation (Liu, et al., 2016). If friends and family members give negative reviews, this will create a negative brand image of the firm. The company should regularly make efforts to interact and communicate with the buyers. Social media platforms can be used for making positive interaction with consumers (Padfield and et al., 2016). This enhances the business experiences of buyers, who are then most likely to repurchase the products and services offered by the company. Event management companies can use innovative approaches so that positive reviews can be gained from the buyers. This will aid in ensuring the long-term growth and survival of the business (Nguyen and et al., 2016).

1.2 Significance of the study

Brand awareness is crucial for the upward direction of the business, which assists the corporation in creating a solid market position. It aids in integrating all business activities and supporting the business in deriving a good outcome (Rexhepi and et al., 2017). It assists a corporation in adopting the most suitable sales strategies to increase customers' attention towards a particular brand that best meets their expectations. In the modern era, competition is increasing, making it imperative for businesses to gain the attention of buyers (Brodie and et al., 2016). For this purpose, it is crucial to shed light on the expectations of customers. The role of the latest communication technology is significant through which companies come into contact with buyers and make them aware of the range of products and services (Ewing, 2017). It is a fact that brand conscious customers would not likely switch to another brand frequently unless they become dissatisfied with the current one (Buil, De Chernatony and Martínez, 2013). However, some unique features available with a new brand attract them to switch towards that brand. To beat the competition and retain customers, companies are opting for suitable strategies through which a positive attitude is generated among customers to stay connected with a particular brand

for a more extended period (Tollin and Christensen, 2017). **Brand awareness is essential in buying** decision-making as consumers must recall the **brand** in the context of a given specific product category, **awareness** increasing the probability that the **brand** will be a member of the consideration set.

The study under consideration would be adequate to understand the link between brand awareness and its direct impact on customers' purchase intention. This assists management in delivering a good quality of services to potential buyers and addresses the issues facing in searching for the best quality of products and services (Cleary and van Caenegem, 2017). Here, mid-sized companies offering services at higher cost would be provided with suggestions related to higher customer satisfaction and implementing cost-effective strategies to derive more significant revenue for the business. Furthermore, the event management business of the UK suffers from greater competition due to the availability of varied tourist destinations and the operation of the number of tour operators (Zerfass and Winkler, 2016.). It becomes essential to approach the customers and access cost-effective sources to retain them (Buil, Martínez and de Chernatony, 2013). These **studies** measure the ability of customers to recognize a **brand** from a list of brands shown. **Brand recognition** levels are crucial in scenarios where customers are presented with a selection of products from various brands, such as at the supermarket.

This current thesis would be practical to highlight how the Ticket Desk can apply the study's outcome to repeat clients' repeat purchase decisions and ensure its expansion in the global marketplace. Furthermore, the study would be practical for parties contributing to the literature (Valaei et al., 2016). This firm can use the literature to construct good outcomes and apply their knowledge to complete the investigation in the most effective manner. Apart from this, students studying in a similar field will find the thesis most effective for their reference (Eide, Hargreaves and Cunningham, 2016). In addition to this, the most important advantage can be considered in terms of mid-sized event management companies which are operating their business at a relatively small level and struggling to create their competitive edge in the marketplace (Panda and Reddy, 2016). Therefore, this current study on assessing the impact of brand awareness on customers' purchase intention is significant to bring about improvements in this sector (Angelopulo, 2017).

Besides this, it is significant for the organisations associated with event management to undertake some branding strategies. This is basically to make a positive impact on the perception

buying decisions of consumers in a way that leads to the enhancement of sales (Sturgeon and et al., 2016). There are some refined strategies of branding where a certain amount of interpretation is necessary for carrying out this research work based upon a similar agenda. This is an essential aspect of the development of business. It will improve brand awareness and gives identity and worth (Szymoszkowskyj and et al., 2016). If the product is well received, this will also give solid growth of the product. The following strategies have to be followed. Firstly is brand name recognition, which is generally used by a well-developed and established company to use its brand name to promote its new product or extend its existing product (Ahmed and Ibrahim, 2017). The top-rated company can be easily recognisable by their logo, colour or slogans.

Another strategy is individual branding, which can happen when larger companies manufacture products that have their brand name and are independent of their parent company (Gao, Smits and Wang, 2016). This strategy will help establish the new brand as a unique identity that will be very easily recognisable. All brands use this kind of strategy to bring their old products and services to life. Companies such as Nike and Apple are automatically associated with a certain style as their most valuable brand identity component (Chiambaretto and Gurău, 2017).

Then there is yet another impelling strategy of branding known as no-brand branding, where the products which have no brand are generally straightforward and generic in terms of design (Nikraftar and et al., 2016). Sometimes, most successful companies use this type of strategy to attract more consumers to increase their profitability. Besides this, the brand extension only exists when the flagship brand enters a new market (Gerber and Sriramesh, 2016). For example, a shoe company will try to enter into clothing or any other industry. The brand name in such a case plays a significant role in carrying their own identity into the new industry.

Private labels are recognised as an effective branding strategy and are becoming very popular with supermarkets (Paulsen, 2016). Some of the well-known retail chains like Asda, Kroger, and Wal-Mart have their very cost-effective products to compete with larger retailers like Tesco (Kudeshia, Sikdar and Mittal, 2016). Lastly, there exists the branding strategy known as crowdsourcing. This will involve all the consumers in the naming process, which will effectively drive up the personal interest in the new products (Kladou, 2017).

Personal motivation for doing research

My motivation is that study will help me to gain experience and skills in doing research. Moreover, the area of marketing and brand awareness interest me the most. That will be helpful to me in doing the study and completing the thesis. This will boost my confidence to conduct consultancy in the area in the future and maybe even supervise theses on this or similar topics in the future.

1.3 Problem statement

Customers in the modern era have become quite brand conscious, so it becomes challenging for marketers to attract such influential customers. However, this affects the performance of the event management companies by reducing their rate of return and decreasing the customer base (Hashemi and Mokhtaran, 2016). The present study has been conducted to analyse the impact of brand awareness on customers' purchase intention. It enables companies to assess those factors through which customers can be attracted towards the particular brand (Burmam and et al., 2017). It enables the management of the business to apply the most effective strategies for the promotion of their brand and make the customers aware of it. At this juncture, the marketing mode, reward strategies and uniqueness in the current products and services are considered (Dolbec and Chebat, 2013).

1. Brand awareness is based on marketing, and its direct impact can be seen on purchase intention (Thompson, 2017). The present investigation is carried out to assess that how brand awareness contributes towards increasing the purchase intention of the UK event management industry. Specific focus is laid on Ticket Desk as the mid-sized organisation through which it becomes easy to evaluate the importance of brand awareness (Avraham and Ketter, 2016). Thus, the issue is related to brand awareness and its direct impact on consumers' purchase intention.

2. Therefore, the study under consideration has been taken into account to produce a good outcome and draw inferences. To meet the specific research objectives effectively (Shieh and Lai, 2017). Apart from this, how the issue related to a lack of brand loyalty among customers is affecting the performance of the business and increasing the operation cost (Balakrishnan, Nekhili and Lewis, 2011). This can be resolved only by increasing brand loyalty among users. This helps to utilise the limited resources effectively and ensures its contribution to creating the

business's competitive edge. Hence, completing the entire study would be helpful for the event management industry to address the issues related to customer retention (Rocha and Fink, 2017).

3. Furthermore, Branding is recognised to be a considerate measure that needs to be done using some verified means, and which in turn necessitates the organisations to undertake such effective measures that will gain the interest of a large number of users (Quan, 2016). Branding is used for marketing the proposed goods and services that are offered to the clients and which results in enhancing the sales of the enterprise to a great extent (Schroeder, Borgerson and Wu, 2016). It is thus crucial for the marketing personnel of an organisation to consider some appropriate strategies of branding that will attract a large number of consumers. The present study is in the context of branding and its impact on the purchase intention of consumers (Elliot and et al., 2016). This, in turn, has reflected some other vital consideration of the marketers that will be investigated in this study.

4. This will assist the organisations in undertaking effective practices of marketing that will increase the sale of their products. Herein, some specification of branding strategies will positively impact the buying intention of the customers to undertake the proposed services of event management companies (Di Benedetto and Kim, 2016). It is the responsibility of marketers to consider employing effective strategies to market the services that meet the identified needs and demands of the consumers. This study will also discuss accessible strategies of branding that will be beneficial for the event management companies specifically. Also, these ventures are required to adopt a more dynamic nature to fulfil the changing preferences of the users for the demonstration of some effective marketing practices, which this study will focus upon (Barnes, 2016).

1.4 Research aim and objectives

The research aim and objectives of the study are presented in the following manner, which the researcher has decided to be effective in completing the thesis in line with the selected methodology (O'Brien, 2017). A full rationale for the methodological approach adopted will be provided in Chapter 3.

Aim

The aim of the current research is "To carry out a critical investigation on how brand awareness impacts on the purchase intentions of customers in the UK event management industry and, to determine how mid-sized event-based companies located in the UK can develop effective customised sales strategy which influences the purchase intentions of their target customers". **Brand awareness** is a marketing term that describes the degree of consumer **recognition** of a product by its name. Creating **brand awareness** is a key step in promoting a new product or reviving an older **brand**. Ideally, **awareness** of the **brand** may include the qualities that distinguish the product from its competition.

This aim may be expressed more concisely as:

"To identify key factors related to branding on purchase intention of event industry customers."

Objectives

The research objectives of the current study are as follows

- To determine the relationship between brand awareness and customer purchase intentions
- To examine the impact of branding factors on customers' purchase intentions in the UK event management industry.
- To recommend suitable sales strategies for mid-sized event-based companies located in the UK to influence their target customers properly.

Research hypothesis-

H0- There is no significant relationship between brand awareness and customer purchase intention.

H1- There is a significant relationship between brand awareness and customer purchase intention.

1.5 Research questions

The research questions for the current research are constructed under the framed research aim and objectives (Kasemsap, 2016).

- What is the relationship between brand awareness and customer purchase intention in the event management industry in the UK?

- What is the impact of branding factors influencing the purchase intention in the event management industry in the UK?
- What sales strategies are most appropriate for mid-sized companies to follow in the event industry?

1.6 Research framework

The framework section reflects the methodology used in the present research to present the findings effectively (Zavattaro and Adams, 2016). It provides a detailed analysis of the selected methods and techniques which are applied in the study. The aspects mentioned below show a detailed explanation of the current study's research methods (Ahmed and Ibrahim, 2017). The research framework of the current investigation is explained below-

- ***Type of investigation***-The investigation used in the current research is of a mixed-method approach, and in this, the researcher will use appropriate quantitative statistical methods for the quantitative part of the study (Degaris, Kwak and McDaniel, 2017). However, the study uses both qualitative and quantitative methods as this mixed approach is considered to result in more meaningful and useful findings (Franklin, 2012; Lang and et al., 2016). In this manner, from evidence from the literature and the researchers own professional opinion a mixed-method approach is considered the most appropriate one for deriving a valid and meaningful conclusion to the work (Eismann and et al., 2017).
- ***Research approach***- The deductive and inductive approaches (overall an abductive approach) will be used in the current research through which the study will include theories or general knowledge related to the research (Wang, 2016). This is considered after careful reflection by the researcher to be the most effective given the nature of the research problems and the data needed to address them (Whiteley and Whiteley, 2006). In this manner, the researcher can derive valid outcomes in line with the direction of the aim and objectives of the work (Barreda, 2016).
- ***Research design***- The research design used in the current study is largely descriptive although there are some analytic procedures used in Chapter 4. Hence it is largely descriptive but not entirely descriptive. This is helpful to present the outcome from the direction of the research in attaining the aim and objectives (Papadimitriou, Kaplanidou and Papacharalampous, 2016). Furthermore, the selected research design aids to understand the characteristics of the population which is being studied. The offered use

of descriptive research design helps assess the impact that brand awareness has on the purchase intention of customers (Goodwin and et al., 2017). Therefore, the selection of a descriptive research design one will contribute towards deriving the most suitable outcome.

- **Research philosophy**- The research philosophy selected for the current investigation will be a mixture of positivism and interpretivism (abductive – quantitative/ deductive and qualitative/ inductive). Further, findings can be derived effectively towards the aims and objectives (Choi, Ko and Kim, 2016). The selection of this particular research philosophy is appropriate for conducting the in-depth analysis of the collected data and deriving the most appropriate outcome (Jackson, 2010).
- **Data collection methods**- The data collected for the current investigation will be both primary and secondary. For this purpose, a questionnaire method has been used to collect primary data (Amatulli and et al., 2017). Moreover, the selected mode of data collection was found to be very effective for the researcher and the respondents, too (Easterby-Smith, Thorpe and Jackson, 2008). Therefore a mixed method of both the questionnaire method and interviews was chosen, and other methods related to secondary data are referenced (Chen et al., 2017).
- **Data analysis**- The data analysis under the current investigation will be based on qualitative and quantitative methods (Butt et al., 2017). It effectively aids in drawing a valid outcome. The main reason behind selecting the quantitative type of investigation is to carry out an in-depth analysis of the aim and objectives (Danish, Latif and Ahmad, 2016). Quantitative method research is a technique to ask questions to the target audience in an organized manner using surveys, polls or questionnaires. Received responses can be analyzed to make well-thought decisions for improving products and services, which will, in turn, help increase respondent satisfaction levels. This market research technique revolves around surveys, questionnaires and polls and the data collected is evaluated numerically, statistically, mathematically to form better strategies and marketing plans. For the qualitative data the researcher has used thematic analysis so that the gathered information can be presented in the form of tables, charts, graphs, etc. Here, the researcher provides a detailed discussion regarding the collected qualitative information

from both the primary and secondary data. This means that the findings can be presented straightforwardly to develop readers' understanding (Danish, Latif and Ahmad, 2016).

1.7 Structure of the thesis

The researcher needs to follow the particular structure of the thesis to present the findings effectively and draw a valid outcome out of the same (Samiee et al., 2016). In this regard, the structure mentioned below has been followed in the current thesis-

- **Chapter 1: Introduction**-It is the core and most important chapter of the thesis in which the researcher provides a brief overview of the selected topic. It consists of the overview, rationale of the study, aim and objectives. (Ben-Shaul and Reichel, 2017). These three factors are considered the most important aspect through which the researcher comes to know about the reason behind selecting the particular topic for investigation (Vanwesenbeeck, Ponnet and Walrave, 2017). However, the introduction chapter also provides the framework related to the research and structure, which is being followed for the thesis. This, in turn, means that readers can effectively realise the importance of the particular topic and its significance in drawing a valid outcome (Jeon et al., 2017).
- **Chapter 2: Literature review**-After the completion of the introduction chapter, the second chapter, the literature review, starts in which secondary data are presented and consists of different sources from which collection secondary data was collected (Seetharaman et al., 2017). The literature review chapter is completed with the help of sources like ISI-ranked journals, reputable publishers like Oxford University and Blackwell, etc. (Diallo and Siqueira, 2017). Selection from such sources makes it possible to collect to produce valid outcomes. (Phua, Jin and Kim, 2017). Books and online articles are also considered to collect secondary data and develop a deep understanding of the topic (Molinillo et al., 2017). Moreover, the literature review chapter would be more effective due to the inclusion of examples that the researcher can effectively reach from these important sources of information (Khan and Mohsin, 2017).
- **Chapter 3: Research methodology**-Research methodology is the third chapter of the thesis, providing a detailed overview of the study. In this, varied methods such as the type of investigation, research design, philosophy and approaches are explained. This enables the researcher to select the most suitable method for producing a valid outcome and incorporate its findings to resolve the research issue (He et al., 2016). The chapter on

research methodology offers an opportunity for readers to understand the importance of each type of methodology and its contribution towards developing a valid outcome (Ketelaar et al., 2017).

- **Chapter 4: Findings** - This is the fourth and foremost chapter of the thesis under which all collected information is analysed with the application of a suitable technique (Katiyar and Sain, 2016). The collected information in the current investigation is analysed in light of the research aim and objectives. This helps to meet the objectives of the investigation in a most effective manner (Khuong, Hoa and Nguyen, 2016). This proves to be effective for readers to get an in-depth understanding (Kim and et al., 2016).
- **Chapter 5: Discussion and conclusion**- This is the last chapter of the thesis under which all collected information and analysis is presented effectively (Kristal and et al., 2016). It begins with a discussion in which the collected information is discussed in the light of aim and objectives (Behe, Huddleston and Sage, 2016). Here the researcher shows the consistency between the primary and secondary data. It leads to a valid conclusion and meets the research purpose effectually (Song, et al., 2017). After the discussion in the last chapter, the researcher concludes. This provides valid suggestions and enables the researcher to shed light on the main findings and their direct relevance with the research topic (Ahn and Back, 2017).

1.8 Summary

In this chapter, the researcher has described the introduction of the thesis, explained the background of the study, problem statement, rationale, aim and objectives of the thesis. The researcher further formulated research questions, described the framework of the research study and explained the structure explicitly and succinctly. At the initial stage, the research has focused on providing theoretical aspects concerning brand awareness. Many companies deliver their customers similar type of products and services. To attain a competitive advantage, firms focus on raising their brand image so that people get attracted to the products and services delivered by the firm. The chapter also includes all the research methodologies used by the investigator to conduct the research study effectively.

Chapter 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The literature review is the most important chapter and consists of all the important information related to the selected topic. It covers all the important concepts and the related framework of the study to develop a deep understanding of the outcome of the investigation in a most effective manner (Yang and Wu, 2016). The literature review is completed with the help of varied sources of information such as journals, books and online articles. These sources of information facilitate the scholar to the outcome of the investigation and produce effective results (Uribe, 2016). The literature review is completed based on the research aim and objectives, whereby the scholar accesses appropriate information to deliver a fruitful outcome (Martin and Strong, 2016).

The current investigation is based on the relationship between brand awareness and purchasing intention, recommending a suitable sales strategy for mid-sized event-based companies. The researcher splits the aim into objectives (Kanji and Ganesan, 2017). The aim of the study has been accomplished with the help of assessing the impact of brand awareness on purchase intention in the event management industry of the UK, firstly and the different key factors which influence the intention to purchase (Ahmad et al., 2016). The literature review covers all the important concepts associated with the aim of the investigation and accomplishes this by proposing a valid justification (Godey et al., 2016).

2.2 Concept of Branding

According to Paulsen, 2019, the brand is considered the foremost aspect of adding value for the business (Klimchuk and Krasovec, 2013). It is an intangible asset for the business whereby a corporation can effectively increase its overall rate of return along with a higher level of satisfaction among users (Islam and Rahman, 2017, Martin and Strong, 2016, Godey et al., 2016). Customers perceive a brand that is easy to find from the information along about the product. However, customers' preferences to take a purchase decision consist of factors, such as price, features, quality and image etc. (Jung et al., 2016). This helps cater to all related parties' needs and supports them to make a positive decision for the business. A firm specifies its brand with the help of a symbol, logo, name or term (Chahal and Rani, 2017). All these related factors tend to create a distinct image of the business in the marketplace, and accordingly, the sales turnover of the business can be increased. The major role of a brand image is related to the

recognition of the manufacturer and ensures the differentiation from products and services of other parties (De Kerviler, Demoulin and Zidda, 2016, Hwang and Hyun, 2017, Nam, Dong and Lee, 2017). The brand image of the business is created with the introduction of a unique logo or symbol. However, according to the views of Pohjola, 2020, the statement can be critically evaluated, that other factors affect the buying behaviour of the customer, which are personal disposable income and personal preference to the brand and loyalty towards it (Okonkwo 2016).

The concept of brand sheds light on representing the image of companies from the event management sector, which strives to meet the expectations of all related parties (GU, Wei and Xu, 2016). At the same time, the focus is laid on the product and its quality, from which the business can effectively increase the satisfaction level of users by offering them the right kind of service (Merrilees, 2017, Suhartanto and Triyuni 2016, Nam, Dong and Lee, 2017). The purchase frequency is increased rather than the occasional purchase, reflecting brand loyalty (Hwang and Hyun, 2017). Customers become loyal towards a particular product or service only when they are provided with suitable products and services. There is a significant difference between brand loyalty and replicating purchase intention (Prakash and Pathak, 2017). The replicate purchase shows that a customer has a relationship with the brand expressed by his replicate purchase. This kind of scenario helps to cater to stakeholders' need as increased profitability helps them get a certain percentage of return in an effectual manner (Han and Stoel, 2017). On a critical note, consumers loyal to the brand usually do not evaluate the same but make the purchase decision confidently. This experience towards a particular brand matters a lot (Nam, Dong and Lee, 2017).

On the contrary, Okonkwo (2016) asserted that customers' loyalty could be understood in two terms, emotional and behavioural (Okonkwo, 2016). Customers attached to a brand behaviourally will tend to be loyal but not emotional (Lu and Gursoy, 2017). On the other hand, some consumers are attached to a particular brand with respect to emotion only. Their emotion is based on their experience or interest in a brand (Ayob, Low and Abdul Jalil, 2017, Prakash and Pathak, 2017). According to the views of Hyun and Kim (2011), the customer may get attached too emotionally to the product and do not want to change the brand even if there are better products available in the market (Hyun and Kim, 2011). Apart from this, some brands make customers loyal forcefully because of their monopoly where customers' interest is not focused (Tingchi Liu, Anthony Wong and Tseng, 2014). Owing to this, an appropriate strategy can be

applied to switch from one to another brand only with the help of available options (Paulsen, 2019). However, businesses try their best to retain buyers by increasing their level of satisfaction and offering them desired products and services.

According to Kotler and Armstrong (2011), Branding directly impacts the performance of the business because, with the help of a brand, a corporation can easily create its goodwill in the marketplace (Kotler and Armstrong, 2011). This is made possible by informing the customers about the availability of different products and services (Hsu and Hsu, 2017, Han and Stoel, 2017). It reveals that the importance of a brand can be seen in terms of the appropriate performance of the business, as consumers will be attracted, and their intention to purchase the particular brand will also be influenced to a great extent (Williams and et al., 2017). Branding is popularised by the selection of marketing strategies only. The businesses use a suitable mode of communication to gain buyers' attraction and make them more aware of the varied products and services (Park and Kwon, 2017). This, in turn, enables consumers to get the most suitable product. It shows that advertising plays an important role in attracting buyers. If particular event management promotes its services with the help of YouTube and other related popular chains, customers get to know about their success and access those services.

On the other hand, Pohjola, 2020 critically evaluated that management of the business incurs huge cost in adopting suitable marketing strategies (Ashraf, Thongpapanl and Northey, 2016, Hamari, Alha and Paavilainen, 2017). For example, access to the internet requires extensive efforts from the firm and selecting the right content and other related things. Similarly, marketing strategies such as Facebook and Twitter have become common through which stakeholders and customers are both attracted towards the business (Hamari, Alha and Paavilainen, 2017). Thus, the concept of branding, has a huge impact in maintaining the good reputation of the business and ensuring its long survival with an increased rate of return (Faqih, 2016). Criticising the statement, as per the views of Hao, Dong and Ma, 2016, to target older people, it becomes important to advertise on radio and television as well, as they are not active on social media websites. (Barreda, Bilgihan and Okumus, 2015)

(Tungate, 2019) presented that brand loyalty is derived via communicating with customers. Here, customers emphasised the unique products and specific features of products and services (Bues, Steiner and Krafft, 2017, Ferreira, da Veiga and da Veiga, 2017). This information is helpful for a business to increase its attention and provide the most suitable kind

of services for the wellbeing of consumers. Consumers do not like to access the products and services from brands that do not value money and their expectations (Ferreira, da Veiga and da Veiga, 2017). For this purpose, advertising plays an important role in the company, showing that it values all its workforce and customers. Companies need to shed light on suitable modes of communication in the context of popularity and resources requirement (Wang, Wang and Guo, 2017). For example, a mode of communication requiring higher cost and resources will not be selected by the business due to an increment in the overall indirect cost of production. At this juncture, a company must carry out its operational activities based on cost and resources requirement (Hao, Dong and Ma, 2016, Wang, Wang and Guo, 2017).

As critiqued by Han and Stoel (2017), branding has become an integral part of marketing. This is because it has provided a base for companies to attract customers. Through effective branding, people automatically get attracted to products. Customers can get an insight into what the company is and what offers it provides. However, it makes it easy for them to differentiate and compare it with other companies.

Moreover, effective branding leads to an increase in brand value in the market. Thus, it becomes easy for the organisation as well as consumers to identify the brand. Recently it has become essential for a business to establish themselves as a brand through marketing and then progress further. However, as said by Okonkwo (2016), there is a change in the current trends of Branding. It is a completely modified way of marketing products to target an audience. This has highly influenced the perception of people. Now, companies have integrated the concept of branding with the purchasing behaviour of customers. The way companies do branding reflects on people's behaviour: This has enabled in developing strategies accordingly and implementing them.

These assists corporations in integrating the business operation to determine the long-run success with the increased rate of return. Accordingly, Quoquab, Pahlevan and Thurasamy (2017) view communication may cost higher to the company, but it contributes to the profits (Erkan, Gokerik, and Acikgoz, 2019). Asserted that brand strategy is deemed to be the long-term plan whereby specific goals are attained by the business to carry out the operational activities. He stressed that brand is not just the website, logo or product, and the name, but it is more than all of these. This fact must be kept in mind by the management of the business (Imanina and Fadhilah,

2016, Zhang, Liu and Yang, 2017) as the brand is intangible. Hence, managements need to put more effort to maintain it and keep the loyalty of customers.

There are seven components of a comprehensive branding strategy. The first one is about purpose, reflecting that the brand must promise its associated customers (Oh, Shin and Park, 2016). Under that promise, a company should not target its own profitability but the profit or well-being of customers. For example, IKEA posted under its vision that "It is not just to sell furniture but rather aims to create a better everyday life" ((Samran, Wahyuni, and Putri, 2019 page 14). It has a significant impact on the purchasing power of customers. This enables the business to increase the number of customers (Chan, Zheng and Lee, 2014, Luis Méndez, Rubio and Oubiña, 2011). These are different options. Thus, a better relationship occurs between customers and the organisation to make it possible to provide good products and services. Added to this, as per the views of Luis Méndez, Rubio and Oubiña (2011), brand logo and brand slogan both play an important role. Hence, the organisation's logo must also be effective (Luis Méndez, Rubio and Oubiña, 2011). Another important factor that must be considered regarding brand development is consistency. It means that a firm does not get the audience confused about the brand. For example, if you continuously update the pictures on the social network, it would negatively impact the business. This is because the organisation is simply showing off its products rather than meeting the expectations of buyers.

Samran, Wahyuni, and Putri, 2019, reported that customers or audience must not feel the pressure of a brand advertisement. Rather customer must get a cohesive message (Sasmit and Mohd Suki, 2015). This proves to be effective to increase the rating of the business. Along with that, lifestyle needs to be considered for the brand under which the corporation ensures that customers are attracted). It should also be noted that customers are not always rational. Rather, act emotionally too. Owing to this, both aspects must be considered through which a fruitful outcome can be derived (Quoquab, Pahlevan and Thurasamy, 2017). This further explained that personal association with customers is important so that the company can easily address any kind of issues that are being faced. This would be more effective in retaining them for a longer time-span and making them loyal to the brand. In contrast to this, as per the views of Hutter et al. (2013), another important activity of the business is by sending personalised mail and doing personal selling, which would have better, and more effective results as compared to the other strategies (Hutter et al., 2013, Aldhmour and Sarayrah, 2016). It is common knowledge that if a

customer is continuously referring to the brand, he develops loyalty. (Aldhmour and Sarayrah, 2016). This derives the additional or extra benefit whereby both parties can be satisfied. Thus, Branding makes a huge difference for an organisation. In this manner, event management companies effectively implement the activities related to the communication and advertisement of products and services (Biedenbach, Bengtsson, and Marell, 2015). Apart from this, flexibility must be ensured in the services to incorporate the views and suggestions of customers and accordingly update both the products and services (Seyedghorban, Matanda and LaPlaca, 2016, Funamori and Mori, 2016). For example, if the age group of 18-40 does not prefer to use the television, they must be targeted using social media and other related modes of communication. However, it requires extensive research by the firm or management to understand the targeted audience to provide them with services (Funamori and Mori, 2016).

(Cheung, Pires, and Rosenberger, 2019) critiqued that the involvement of the workforce is also important for building a brand (Luis Méndez, Rubio and Oubiña, 2011). For this purpose, formal meetings can be organised with personnel to extract customers' views and suggestions. This can be improved through consultation and open sessions (Farsky, Schnittka and Lorth, 2017). It is a fact that customers are directly interacted with by employees to gain ideas regarding their preferences. For this purpose, event management companies need to ensure that workforce is taking active participation in the marketing of products and services. It leads to determine long-term success and derive valid outcome (Herstein, Herstein and Barnes, 2017, He and Lai, 2014). Digital and human interaction are also very important for the business to address customers' issues and provide them with the right kind of products and services. It aids to speed up the business activities, and the requirement of all related stakeholders can be met (He and Lai, 2014). Buil, Martínez and de Chernatony (2013) further explained that loyalty is associated only with the brand, and it is derived through active efforts of the corporation (Hall, 2016, Hur, Kim and Kim, 2014). However, in contrast to this, as per the views of Karunaratna and Crouch (2016), personal interaction and selling have a major impact on the individual rather than interacting with them on the digital platform.

An organisation cannot increase the loyalty of customers until are highly satisfied. At this juncture, the focus is on providing the right and valuable customers and offering extra benefits to regular or loyal customers. This further contributes towards strengthening the brand image (Dedeoğlu, van Niekerk, and Okumuş, 2020). Lastly, competitive awareness is another crucial

element of a branding strategy through which customers know current services' effectiveness compared to other companies (Chiambaretto, Gurău and Le Roy, 2016). This facilitates the business's success and grabs the attention of more and more customers effectively. Therefore, the branding strategy should be specific and thus more effective to be understandable to all. It is the only way to ensure the business's long-term survival as the number of customers will be increased day by day (Reimann and Wagner, 2016, Hutter and et al., 2013). This helps to derive a valid outcome and supports the corporation in meeting the long and short-term objectives in the right manner.

Apart from the above discussion, it can be said that branding is the most important concept that aids the business to focus more on enhancing the customer base and their satisfaction aspects (Chang, Kuo and Cheng, 2014). With the help of branding, companies need to focus on major elements such as quality, price and status of the product (Gürhan-Canli, Hayran and Sarial-Abi, 2016) These factors are also useful to entice the range of customers towards the existing products and services (Hutter and et al., 2013). It is often observed that customers who are highly concerned about their status focus more on purchasing branded products. This contributes to encouraging success and sales aspects and enhances business profitability (Wang, 2017, Zenker, Braun and Petersen, 2017). Thus, when articulating the above discussion, it is evident that a brand is not merely a logo or sign; it holds a valuable position in business management. The brand commonly contributes to amending the value of a business, and at the same time, it also helps enlarge business operations (Romaniuk, Dawes and Daedalus, van, 2014). For instance – with the help of brand management, any company can enter in new market places with new products with the surety of potential buyers (Sürücü, Öztürk, and Bilgihan, 2019). This helps the company to manage all business aspects appropriately through branding policies and strategies.

2.3 Importance of Branding to mid-sized businesses

Branding goes beyond an unforgettable logo that tends to enhance the firm's value to a great extent. In turn, it provides a directional base to the entire organisation by motivating the employees together for the pursuit of the specified direction (Hult, Morgeson and Fornell, 2017). It is also composed of several other benefits that lead to the growth of new customers in an effortless manner and results in fortifying the presence of existing consumers in the marketplace. On considering the above-referred points, Atwood (2017) stated a simple definition of a brand

representing the general perception of individuals of a company considering to brand itself. This involves some leading factors that need to be taken care of by the enterprise and reflect a direct relationship with their accepted branding strategy (Yigitcanlar, Guaralda and Pancholi, 2016). In contrast to this, as per the views of Zenker, Braun and Petersen (2017), mid-sized businesses can increase their brand awareness and presence in the market through advertisement (Zenker, Braun and Petersen, 2017, Yigitcanlar, Guaralda and Pancholi, 2016).

As elucidated by (Pittz et al. (2017), branding plays a significant role in the organisation's growth. The way can analyse this that it helps in creating brand awareness within the market. Also, it gives a clear view of the organisation, and on what target market should be focused on. Branding is useful in attracting people to buy goods and communicate with people so that their needs can be identified. However, this concept provides information obtained from the market so that changes can be made in goods and strategies. There is a vast difference between Branding and marketing. The way can analyse this that marketing is a completely tactical based concept, whereas branding is strategically based.

The company's customer service department and its reputation, publicity and trademark or logo of the establishment are involved while considering its brand (Plangger and Watson, 2015). Proper functioning of all the elements above defines a considered adoption of branding. (Dedeoğlu, van Niekerk, and Okumuş, 2020). On the other hand, this is specified that an unfavourable role of poor services to the consumers leads to a downcast of the organisations' brand image (Karunaratna and Crouch, 2016). Therefore, it has a very considerate role in maintaining the brand image of an entity where customers are a crucial part of almost all sorts of business establishments. In context to which, serving clients is stated to be one of the prime responsibilities of the workers operating in the enterprise with a key agenda of satisfying them to a definite level (Biedenbach, Biedenbach and Manzhynski, 2016, Karunaratna and Crouch, 2016). However, it is another prompt consideration of maintaining a long-term and steady relationship with the consumers. Companies can substantially continue in the marketplace with the achievement of their undertaken business goals and objectives.

Sürücü, Öztürk, and Bilgihan, 2019, has highlighted some major benefits of branding that make a strong impact on the business (see also Kear, 2014). This involves the improvement of recognition by together building an environment of trust and credibility. This carries forward into the marketing strategy of a business by directly supporting them in the process of

advertising. Walmsley (2014), where the distinct perception towards the significance of Branding has previously emphasised more upon the creation of financial value from Branding (Crewe and Martin, 2017, Jin and Cedrola, 2017). This, in turn, leads to the generation of newer customers whilst also ennobling the old set of consumers. Lastly, an effective branding strategy also inspires the employees to a great extent to achieve business goals and objectives over time (Jin and Cedrola, 2017). However, in contrast to this, as per Pittz et al. (2017), the main benefit of branding is that the company can increase its market share and thereby profits (Pittz and et al., 2017).

However, it is recognised to be a slightly distinct perception of branding that is, in turn, leads to motivating the employees to a great extent, as argued by Ponnam and Balaji (2015). In whose view, branding is referred to be a more customer-centric approach and must be done to attract a large set of consumers towards buying the company's offered goods and services. This leads to another principle concept of customer-centric marketing, which necessitates the business to adopt such effective strategies that lead to attaining the overall goals and objectives of the business (McCorkle and Payan, 2017). It is now directed to achieving increased profits and revenues, which is again argued by Leekha Chhabra and Sharma (2014). Stating the fact of long-term business sustainability, it is apparent that businesses must not concentrate on achieving huge earnings all the time (Suh, 2017, McCorkle and Payan, 2017). Instead, Companies should first consider making a definite relationship with the customers. On considering this fact, it can be said that a customer-centric approach is running the business with the consumers by provisioning them with an affirmative experience (Wang, Wang and Barnes, 2017). This should be continued even after selling the products and services to them and entitled after-sales services to the clients.

Cheung, Pires, and Rosenberger (2019), with a correspondent outlook towards it, have supported this tactic of a customer-centric approach where its successful completion leads to drive repetitive business with a loyal set of customers and a huge number of profits (see also Helm and Özergin, 2015). Also, such a customer-centric approach is apparent to grow over time (Frank, Enkawa and Schvaneveldt, 2014, Pittz and et al., 2017). Besides this, such a type of strategy is also known to set up a true digitally native culture. However, Pittz et al. (2017), with a distinct standpoint, have specified a customer-centric approach to be a challenging task for most of the businesses, where it not only means to offer outstanding customer service (Pittz et al.,

2017), but it also means to provide a spectacular experience for the customers from the very initial stage of awareness. After completing the purchase procedure, the company must follow the post-purchase process to continue providing extraordinary services to the users (Popp and Woratschek, 2016). This is recognised to be a strategy that is meant to prioritise the customers by putting them at the centre of the business, which defines a valuable position in the business. In contrast to this, as per the views of Ponnampalani and Balaji (2015), it can lead to an increase in the cost and may not prove to be cost-effective for a mid-sized company (Ponnampalani and Balaji, 2015, Strebinger, 2014).

Cheung, Pires, and Rosenberger 2019, have enlightened the aforesaid statement with some factual instances where the businesses undertaking a customer-centric approach are more apparently interpreting their clients and users (de Noronha, Coca-Stefaniak and Morrison, 2017). It also necessitates them to understand the real interest of the consumers and the activities in which they tend to engage more. This, in turn, assists the companies in making a prompt identification of the opportunities through which helps in considering to create goods for the closely analysed customers (Becerra and Badrinarayanan, 2013, Giordano, Manuti and de Palma, 2016). Customer lifetime value is yet another method by which the consumers can be segmented based on their spending power (Giordano, Manuti and de Palma, 2016). It is also based on worldwide research of companies associated with both national and international markets, where 60% of the enterprises that have adopted a customer-centric approach are more successful in business with others.

Ponnampalani and Balaji (2015), critiqued that it is a challenging agenda when it does not permit the firms to share their customers' valuable information across all their departments, which hinders their attempt to adopt a customer-centric approach (Ponnampalani and Balaji, 2015). Atwood (2017), with a similar standpoint, has supported this approach's resistance and have together suggested some prompt measures for the same (Atwood, 2017, Ponnampalani and Balaji, 2015). In accordance with this, establishments need to choose this approach to take care of some best suitable practices for its adaptation and follow a stepwise procedure (Folgado-Fernández, Hernández-Mogollón and Duarte, 2017). It is where brands that are factually committed to this approach must undertake a passionate attitude to serve the users. However, another prime belief must follow that the customers should always come first (Vasanthi and Vinoth, 2017, Özdemir, 2016). However, in addition to this, as per the views of Özdemir (2016), market research plays

an important role in this aspect so that the best can be delivered to the customers (Özdemir, 2016).

Samran, Wahyuni, and Putri (2019), have simplified this statement with some more precise considerations. The brands need to believe that the businesses cannot succeed in their business without prompting them (Whiteley and Whiteley, 2006). It simply means to see the globe with the eyes of the customers, with the principal role of the marketers to interpret this fact to realise the exact wants of consumers by using the information to capture the consumer's vision and share it across all the organisation (DiMartino and Jessen, 2016). Zhang and et al. (2013), with a different view towards it, have specified some other requisite measures where brands have a committed outlook towards adopting the customer-centric approach (Zhang and et al., 2013, DiMartino and Jessen, 2016). Companies must focus more upon fulfilling the realistic needs and demands of the consumers and further use it to develop their products and services following their interpreted demands (Özdemir, 2016). However, in contrast to this, as per Hafeez Foroudi and Parahoo (2016) views, orientation on the company's goals helps better understand the business's perspective. Companies are then aligned with the customers (Hafeez Foroudi and Parahoo, 2016).

Chang and Chen (2014) have considered building a relationship with the customers to play a more important role while adopting a customer-centric approach (Chang and Chen, 2014). This together enables the brands to reflect a more committed outlook towards serving the customers by together maximising their experiences (MA and LIU, 2016). In context to which, the brands with such a committed outlook are required to undertake a stepwise approach by analysing the strategy formed to serve the consumers by planning for it and implementing it (Erkan, Gokerik, and Acikgoz, 2019). This way, it will reflect the focus of the companies by keeping them surrounded by a loyal set of clients and users to help them stay profitable (Hafeez, Foroudi, and Parahoo, 2016.).

2.4 Concept of brand awareness and intention to purchase

Brand awareness is considered the prominent aspect behind the success of every organisation, which helps a business determine its upward direction (Giovanis, Athanasopoulou and Tsoukatos, 2015). It is the process to determine the extent to which buyers can recall a particular brand. According to Huang and Sarigöllü (2014), brand awareness is the probability that users or buyers are well familiar with the life and the availability of products and services

(Cerreta and Daldanise, 2017). This reflects that the association of consumers with a particular brand is higher or low. However, it can be measured effectively with the help of the ratio of the niche market, which contains the former knowledge regarding the specific brand. It includes recognition and brand recall (Walsh and Dodds, 2017, Odoom, Odoom and Boateng, 2017). Brand recognition is developed with the help of recognising the prior knowledge related to a brand, and consumers can easily differentiate between provided brands.

On the other hand, brand recall is that the specific brand remains in the consumer's mind when he or she is offered a particular product category. For this purpose, companies keep the brand's name very simple and easy to remember (Chang and Chen, 2014). This directly impacts brand recall and ensures a higher rate of return and greater profitability (Lee, Oh and Hsu, 2017). However, in contrast to this, as per Odoom, Odoom and Boateng (2017), the recall of the brand can be achieved through effective newspaper articles and repeating the name repeatedly to impact the customers (Tungate, 2019).

According to Hutter and et al. (2013) critiqued that brand awareness has two types; aided awareness and immediate brand recall (Hutter and et al., 2013). The former one shows that a customer can easily come to know about the product by viewing the category. This enables him to recall it immediately from the list or category. Owing to this, the brand's name must be simple and concise for the corporation's advantage (Tripathi, 2014). It helps to deliver a good quality of services to many buyers as the corporation would effectively increase the customer base (Zentes, Morschett and Schramm-Klein, 2017, Chhabra, 2017). The other type of brand awareness is immediate brand recall, under which the customer remembers the quality, features and other related factors of the brand.

In addition to this, the intention to purchase is automatically linked with brand awareness. However, what is important is keeping the customer satisfied with the available products and services (Tungate, 2019). This assists the corporation in attracting more buyers and keeping them loyal. However, customers will be satisfied, although the company does not get much better in the market until it perceives that a similar firm provides the necessary services and products to meet their requirements more effectively (Robertson, Hurst and Kieth, 2017). Then, the marketing department of the business plays an important role. In contrast to this, as per the views of Mohd Yasin, Nasser Noor and Mohamad (2007), the customer gets attracted to the

other brand if they are brand switchers and find other options which are convenient and better for them (Mohd Yasin, Nasser Noor and Mohamad, 2007, Wang, Wang and Barnes, 2017).

The company needs to focus on research and development to gather important information related to competitors. Thus, information collected from competitors would be highly beneficial for the business to update the current products and services (Wang, Wang and Barnes, 2017). It provides a higher level of satisfaction among shareholders also, due to the generation of greater return. Similarly, fund collection and other related aspects prove effective in the form of greater attention from customers (Johnson, Asare-Marfo and Birol, 2017, Hyun and Kim, 2011). This shows that a company is dedicated to buyers' expectations and wants and are provided with quick responses accordingly. If customers are not offered the right kind of information and given misleading data, the customer would likely switch to another brand.

According to (Tungate, 2019) brand awareness is important for keeping the firm around for ages (Hyun and Kim, 2011). It is only the brand image that ensures the presence of the business in the marketplace. Without applying the right kind of marketing strategy, Branding is not possible; hence, customers will not be attracted (Odoom, Odoom and Boateng, 2017; Bennett, Graham and Clemente, 2017). At the same time, purchase intention is decided based on the quality and variety of the brand. For example, a brand offering different kinds of products will be preferred by some users, but not by those who seek better quality (Heinberg, Ozkaya and Taube, 2016). For this purpose, a brand must consider both quality and variety. This is helpful for companies to focus on the important tactics of marketing through which a customer's attention can be gained, and the company's influence can be strengthened. The positive relationship between brand awareness and purchase intention brings out a fruitful outcome. In turn, the expectations of all related stakeholders can be met (Bennett, Graham and Clemente, 2017; Heinberg, Ozkaya and Taube, 2016). Therefore, event management companies effectively focus on building the brand and deriving from its valid outcome of the business's profitability. Hence, brand awareness is important for making a purchase decision.

According to Esch, Langner, Schmitt and Geus (2006), the brand image of an organisation showcases its value in the global or national market (Esch, Langner, Schmitt and Geus, 2006, Shamim, Ghazali and Albinsson, 2016). This represents that how the organisation is offering or treating its customers to meet their expectations. This helps to form the brand relationship as customers prefer the same products and services because of their specific bond

with the corporation (Shamim, Ghazali and Albinsson, 2016, Baumeister, Scherer and Wangenheim, 2015). The relationship based on brand is characterised by attachment, brand trust and satisfaction, whereby the firm is highly influential and becomes more recognisable in the global market. The author critically evaluated that the firm must maintain the brand relationship to impact the corporation in front of customers positively. In this manner, a business can shed light on a strong brand image by forming a positive relationship (Biscaia, Ross and Marôco, 2016). This kind of strong relationship works better to increase the purchase intention of consumers.

The event management sector must show its commitment towards the quality, type of services, and many other facts, and accordingly, Companies enter into a positive relationship with the customers (Tungate, 2019). The study conducted by Wang and Yang (2010) reveals that brand credibility strongly affects consumers' purchase intention towards the specific brand. This proves to be effective in competing with different activities and deriving the most suitable outcome for an organisation. It was found that effective managerial practices are important to make the brand highly visible (Marticotte, Marticotte and Baudry, 2016). For example, it is managerial action whereby business tends to focus on clients' prospects and opts for suitable strategies to increase their intention towards the brand.

(Tungate, 2019) reported that the brand equity dimension consists of three aspects: association with the brand, loyalty, and distinctiveness (Mohd Yasin, Nasser Noor and Mohamad, 2007). These different aspects enable corporations to consider the brand's value with regard to customers or clients (Chae, Ko and Han, 2015, Marticotte, Marticotte and Baudry, 2016). For example, how a brand is different from its competitors matters a lot to increase its value. It would significantly impact consumers because they would like to purchase such a kind of brand only. However, if competitors do provide more suitable or attractive offers, then customers like to switch. It is just all to do with the brand's value and other potential aspects associated with customer attraction (Shah, 2015). Hakala, Svensson and Vincze (2012) argued that excessive branding might lead to disputes and conflict in the localities (Hakala, Svensson and Vincze, 2012, Yang 2010). Any message or tagline developed by the organisation's management can lead to misrepresentation by the consumers. In the event management sector, it is very easy to make the customers loyal. For this purpose, purchase intention is created through forming a long-term relationship with existing customers and, accordingly, word of mouth is

created (Osman and Sentosa, 2013). Word of mouth works best in the event management sector. It is because new customers are added in accordance with the review and satisfaction level of existing ones. This way, many of the buyers recommend the brand to their friends or relatives. Hence, the brand strategy does affect the customers' purchase decision, so more competent companies focus on the same (Lin and Bennett, 2014). This further critically evaluates that if existing customers are not satisfied, a better firm will focus on the first to elicit a positive word of mouth. Otherwise, it will take a long time to promote the same in the marketplace.

Hsin Chang and Wen Chen (2008) critiqued that stressed on word of mouth is the best source to recognise the brand in front of many people (Hsin Chang and Wen Chen, 2008). This word of mouth is currently spread around the globe quickly due to the impact of social media and other related techniques (Wu and Wang, 2014, Lin and Bennett, 2014). For example, people share their views by using Facebook and accordingly, the fan page is displayed to large numbers of people. The online social network proves to be effective for reviving the brand in the market and raising awareness about it among customers (Kumar and Kothari, 2015). Another fact is that clients or customers need accessible information for making quick decision related to the purchase.

Though, it is important to note that brand awareness might have a negative result if a firm leaves a customer or client less satisfied. For this purpose, quick action should be taken to address the want or requirement of consumers. This helps raise profitability and make consumers more reliant on the brand (Roustasekehravani, Hamid and Pooladireishahri, 2014, Langner, Schmitt and Geus, 2006). Owing to this, online companies remain highly focused on raising awareness. Both negative and positive outcome can be derived through the use of the online mode of communication. Esch, Langner, Schmitt and Geus (2006) contend that branding increases an organisation's goodwill and reputation effectively and efficiently. Customers purchase branded products because of their quality and quantity (Langner, Schmitt and Geus, 2006, Porral and Lévy-Mangin, 2014). He further stated that the firm should form positive word of mouth by launching an appropriate scheme. Once customers are attracted, it would be easy to let them know the effectiveness of a particular brand (Knittel, Beurer and Berndt, 2016). Therefore, the business's competitive edge will be created, and related parties like shareholders, clients, or customers will also be highly contented. Thus, the focus is on strategies to effectively keep the customers happy and connected with the business (Porral and Lévy-Mangin, 2014).

Often, customers make a spontaneous decision related to the project to make it more visible to customers. Here, the firm ensures the showcase of its product and services effectively so that first impression can last for a long time (Dixon, Martinez and Martin, 2015, Kuo and Feng, 2013). This is also considered a very nice branding strategy and raises awareness among customers related to the particular brand. In such cases, consumers take the immediate decision whereby it becomes very easy to select the right kind of product and service at the right time (Xie, Peng and Huan, 2014). At the same time, staff and their set pattern's attitude also directly impacts the customers' purchase intention. For example, many brands have dedicated employees who influence their customers positively (Horner, 2016).

Therefore, the inclusion of skilled and competent personnel is also helpful to take quick decision related to the purchase (Reza Jalilvand and Samiei, 2012, Cheung, Zheng and Lee, 2014). It is found in most corporations that the workforce makes the customers ready even with no use product. This all happens just because of skills and their strategies to persuade client or consumers. This scenario remains a little different in the case of the event management sector under which clients need to understand everything related to time, price etc. (Kuo and Feng, 2013). So, employees or staff must be polite and clear towards everything associated with the services.

2.5 Importance of brand awareness for event management industry in the UK

According to Panchal, Khan and Ramesh (2012), brand awareness seems a very important factor behind a corporation's success as integrating employees and making them able to incorporate in decision-making procedure (Panchal, Khan and Ramesh, 2012). This facilitates the firm to adopt an appropriate strategy for promoting its brand and attract many buyers (Alwi and Kitchen, 2014, Sun, Tong and Law, 2017). The corporation builds its competitive edge only with the help of brand awareness as it is the way the firm come to know about the popularity of its products and services. If many customers know about the product, companies can easily expand their venture to cover large geographical areas. Malär and et al. (2011) argued that branding is essential for an organisation. It represents its worth, and customers are attracted more towards branded products than non-branded products (Malär and et al., 2011, Kasemsap, 2014).

In this manner, brand awareness is important for the corporation for its successful operation and a higher return rate. It can be critically evaluated by the study of Rubio, Oubiña and Villaseñor (2014) that brand awareness procedure requires to invest big budget on different

financing activities. This, in turn, a firm might suffer from a low rate of return at the initial phase and suffer from loss. It might be critical to face the competition in the marketplace, and some buyers might switch to another brand (Islam and Rahman, 2017, Malär and et al., 2011). Owing to this, a recognition strategy is applied so that the ratio of profitability remains stable and the firm can effectively get the competitive edge.

Hyun and Kim (2011) asserted that it is the only brand awareness that makes it possible for organisations to understand the requirements and expectations of buyers' preferences (Hyun and Kim, 2011). After delivery of the product, the customer also asked to rate the product and that their experience is shared by using the appropriate mode of communication (Martinelli, Belli and Marchi, 2015). This record-keeping procedure effectively introduces the product in the marketplace and caters to all related parties' requirements.

Sasmit and Mohd Suki (2015) explained that brand awareness is created by using varied strategies under which at first focus is laid on raising the awareness related to problem or need. It forces customers to search for the best suitable or effective solution to eliminate their issue or meet their expectations. In this manner, the firm also demonstrates the solution by shedding light on the problem (Cheung, Zheng and Lee, 2014, Rosethorn, 2016). It can be critically evaluated that an appropriate mode of communication must be selected and suitable marketing strategies to get to know about the brand accordingly. Luis Méndez, Oubiña and Rubio (2011) analysed that unique way can be adopted to make the buyers aware of the product and the positive impact it can have on their daily life routine or any specific purpose (Luis Méndez, Oubiña and Rubio, 2011).

For example, KFC introduced itself as a quality centre offering various products for buyers' tastes. This is the main reason customers can recognise this brand easily. Because of this, the firm is making huge profitability together with the retention of buyers (Sun, Tong and Law, 2017). The result can be seen in terms of their repeat purchase decisions. Furthermore, Buil, De Chernatony and Martínez (2013) asserted that brand awareness plays an important role in increasing the sales revenue of the corporation. This aspect contributes towards meeting the sales target and supporting all related parts of the business to deliver a higher quality of services to the end-users. Buil, Martínez and de Chernatony (2013) said that customers decide based on the branding of products and services. A branded organisation always leads to growth and development and guarantees its future success effectively and efficiently (Kasemsap, 2014).

According to Malär and et al. (2011), brand awareness is important just because of increasing the repeat purchase decision (Malär and et al., 2011). Owing to this, management puts efforts to deliver a good quality of services and advertise the business's brand image in the marketplace. At this juncture, a firm needs to focus on consumer behaviour to brand awareness can be created (Rosethorn, 2016, Wahab, Hassan and Maon, 2016). The business can easily handle varied activities to continue with production, understanding the needs and expectations of buyers. However, consumers have different types of behaviour such as knowledge, attitude and action. These three steps are identified to introduce the most needed brands for the expectations of all related consumers (Musa, Ab Rahim and Othman, 2016). Apart from this, brand awareness proves to be effective to highlight both the positive and negative behaviour of customers towards the particular brand. This helps to carry out all operational activities in the direction of the growth and development of the business (Zhang, Shabbir, Pitsaphol and Hassan, 2014, Rahman, 2014). This proves to be effective for retaining consumers and provides them with a good environment, leading to long-run success with the increased rate of return.

With the use of brand awareness, the corporation comes to know about consumer purchase decisions. It enables them to access good quality products and services provided by the business (Jahn and Kunz, 2014). This enables the firm to achieve consistent expansion and a higher rate of growth in the marketplace. In this manner, brand success is determined with the help of strong brand awareness whereby the firm tends to attract more buyers and gives them access to good quality products and services effectively. Gartner and Ruzzier (2011) asserted that a brand's strength consists of customer-brand relationship, brand loyalty and customer satisfaction. These three things are derived through brand only, which in turn assists the firm to secure its good image in the marketplace (Kim, Ko and Hoon Kim, 2014). At the same time, it proves to be effective to cater to the needs of all related parties. It is only the brand through which a business effectively contributes to organisational success and considers its expansion to survive in the international market.

According to Buil, Martínez and de Chernatony (2013), the brand's market performance is achieved by the awareness of the brand among buyers (Buil, Martínez and de Chernatony, 2013). For this purpose, various marketing activities are performed by the corporation. It can be critically evaluated those businesses put efforts to closely monitor their market-related activities for the promotion of varied products in an effectual manner (Ulfat, Muzaffar and Shoab, 2014),.

Marketing planning and the development of an appropriate strategy are the most important reasons behind the good performance of the brand. A suitable mode of communication is selected and used to raise awareness among consumers (Ladkin and Buhalis, 2016, Thomas, 2015). For example, a social media strategy is used to target a large number of buyers. In accordance with this context, Hakala, Svensson and Vincze (2012) said that to increase the market performance and market share; an organisation must create its branded image effectively and efficiently (Hakala, Svensson and Vincze, 2012). This proves to add value to both the product and company. By this strategy, the sustainable competitive edge of the business is generated along with an equal focus on long-term value (Wolny and Mueller, 2013). This supports the firm to deliver a better quality of services and makes it possible for the firm to expand its venture to introduce more new product lines. Kapferer (2012) critically evaluated that brand awareness is maintained by considering a product life cycle (Kapferer, 2012). Here, the management of the business considers each stage such as introduction, growth, maturity and decline. This aspect makes it more possible for the business to integrate all related stakeholders and provide them with a good working environment (Casidy, 2013). However, examples of event management companies can be appraised to see how effectively this helps in retaining their clients. For instance, Wonderland Events uses an appropriate strategy to promote its services, and accordingly, this gains popularity to survive its business for a longer period (Stan, 2015). Not only has this, but the network of clients is increasing day by day because of the appropriate brand image of the business. Group Seven Events also follow a similar branding strategy for meeting the expectations of all its clients and to satisfy them with a higher quality of services.

According to Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob (2011), brand awareness is essential for the communication process between an organisation and its clients (Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob, 2011). If a corporation does not put efforts into creating brand awareness, it will not be possible to communicate with its clients. For this purpose, the entire event management industry of the UK focuses on communication regarding their brands with the use of updated communication channels such as YouTube and various other social media (Elbedweihy and Jayawardhena, 2014, Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob, 2011). Social media plays a leading role as most information is passed through by using the same communication channel.

According to Juntunen, Juntunen and Juga (2011), the brand is considered a strong tool for the attraction of buyers. It enables them to access the products offered by the business

(Juntunen, Juntunen and Juga, 2011). Here, the firm focuses on designing logos and symbols which are easily recognised. This helps to support customers in making the right purchase decision by distinguishing the product or firm from another one (Gad, 2016). From this context, Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob (2011) argued that branding increases the goodwill and reputation of the organisation (Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob, 2011). It also promotes the growth and development of the organisation effectively and efficiently. It helps a company create its distinct identity to grab the attention of buyers and keep all related stakeholders highly satisfied (Laming and Mason, 2014, Keller, Parameswaran and Jacob, 2011).

Furthermore, a study conducted by Hakala, Svensson and Vincze (2012) revealed that a unique logo and symbol is created for a brand in accordance with a specific product or service (Hakala, Svensson and Vincze, 2012). It reflects the organisation's image, and thus customers get to know about the specific products and services. In this manner, the buyer's purchase decision is influenced by the business (Rathod and Bhatt, 2014). However, logos are considered the most powerful way to associate the company with consumers and emphasise creating the business's goodwill.

According to Hakala, Svensson and Vincze (2012), the perceived quality is enhanced for a particular product or service (Hakala, Svensson and Vincze, 2012, Juntunen, Juntunen and Juga, 2011). This enables a corporation to demonstrate its services effectively. Thus, customers perceive the quality of products and services and make the purchase decision (Khuong, Hoa and Nguyen, 2016). Hence, the brand's presence in the right manner is the appropriate method to gain the attraction of buyers and give them the ability to access good quality products.

Khasawneh and Hasouneh (2010) critiqued that brand awareness plays an important role in its success due to its direct contribution to sales turnover (Khasawneh and Hasouneh, 2010). It is an important factor in building the business image in the marketplace by raising awareness related to the same (Ambrose and Harris, 2017, Gad, 2016). All organisations try their best to get recognition related to their services to grab the attention of customers. Pride and Ferrell (2010) argued that as we are in an era of constant advancements in technology, brand awareness is especially important for every business (Pride and Ferrell, 2010). This is because people always have some computer in their hand, whether it is a smartphone, a tablet, or an actual laptop/desktop, which means the customer can quickly communicate with others in a matter of seconds (Hur, Kang and Kim, 2015). The application of perfect marketing strategies makes it

possible to recall the performance of the brand and influence buyers to make repeat purchase decision (Wilson and Hollensen, 2013, Hakala, Svensson and Vincze, 2012). If marketing activities are not performed correctly, management has to take strict action to boost sales turnover.

Astute marketing enables the business to integrate all its business activities and support the firm in delivering good quality services to many buyers (Close, Lacey and Cornwell, 2015, Pride and Ferrell, 2010). Consumers do not get the information related to the products and service until the firm puts efforts into grabbing their attention. In this regard, business activities can be integrated to support the organisation effectually, and consumers' decision as to which product is to be purchased is affected greatly (Chen, Lin and Chang, 2014). For this purpose, the business can apply important strategies to make the customers aware of the brand. It leads to determine the organisational success and integrating the workforce in contributing towards growth and development.

Pullman and Gross (2004) stated that companies associated with the event management sector must radically change their marketing strategies so that it becomes easy to integrate the business activities (Pullman and Gross, 2004). It proves to be effective to increase the sales turnover as clients will be retained (Martínez, 2015, Hur, Kang and Kim, 2015). This is because clients' needs will be raised to a greater level of concern. A business can use its organisational success to increase its attention towards its business activities. This facilitates contributing towards the further success of the business. Shimp (2010) argued that the choice of customers is determined through the application of successful marketing strategies. However, most buyers are mainly interested in the costly brand and admire to prefer it to show their interest (Qi, Qu and Li, 2015). For this purpose, the focus is laid on introducing appropriate strategies to float the information related to varied kinds of products. Brand awareness helps retain the customers and not only to attract them. This kind of scenario proves to be effective for businesses to ensure their successful expansion without focusing upon the potential impact on the cost strategies at this certain point in time (Lin and He, 2015). Tungate (2009) stated that fear of counterfeit products influences businesses to communicate regarding the brand effectively. Otherwise, companies might fail to retain the customers.

However, it is a fact that counterfeit products provide price benefit to customers along with easy availability of the same (Chang, Chiang and Han, 2015). At this juncture, the lack of

sufficient information regarding the particular brand does affect the impact of the actual brand. However, businesses fail to raise awareness of the product in a large marketplace. Thus, consumer-facing barriers to engaging with a particular brand, often consumers' would rather switch to another to save overall time (Šeric, Gil-Saura and Ozretić-Došen, 2015, Chiaravalle and Schenck, 2014). Clow and Baack (2010) contend that if a good marketing campaign is focused on a brand and business model, the organisation will more effectively narrow in on the target audience and encourage them to feel connected to and empowered by the brand (Clow and Baack, 2010). Apart from this, the experience of other people or such as friends etc. and relatives. affect the viewpoint or decision of a person to a great extent (Chiaravalle and Schenck, 2014). So, the business management must decide on the right kind of communication strategy that directly impacts the attraction of customers and the easy availability of important information related to the varied kind of services.

Pride and Ferrell (2010) stated that brand awareness and hearsays must be merged where business management needs to focus on the balanced approach (Pride and Ferrell, 2010). If excessive information is provided, hearsay's issue will be incurred rather than awareness (Kim, Kim and Youn, 2014). The application of a balanced approach contributes towards the long-run success of the business, together with the increased rate of return. Also, the firm can use modern modes of communication and outsource such kind of activities. This proves to effectively implement the balanced approach (Lee, Yao and Lambert, 2015, Hodge, Pederson and Walker, 2015).

On the other hand, Mooij (2010) explained that brand awareness reflects the difference between other products and their differentiated product. Therefore, strategies or promotional activities such as sponsorship, blogs and print media, and other modern technologies are used to disseminate important information regarding the services rendered by the event management sector (Noyan and Şimşek, 2014). Furthermore, the businesses are also organised to target a large mass of people simultaneously and show the reality of the brand to influence them.

According to Kurtz (2011), higher brand awareness is associated with better sales figures and determines the firm as the market leader. It is a well-known fact that favourable or positive impressions of the business would encourage customers to involve with the brand (Kurtz, 2011). It is the major reason why companies try their best to devote much of their time to spread

awareness among customers and get the best outcome out of the kind of marketing activities (Sandbacka, Nätti and Tähtinen, 2013, Cvijikj and Michahelles, 2013).

Clow and Baack (2010) stated that the attachment of shoppers is connected emotionally with the brand or product, which creates a good image of the business (Clow and Baack, 2010). Without the involvement or association of the workforce with the product, it might not be possible to provide the right track for business-related activities. Owing to this, integration is very important, as is the strategic action of the business (Hodge, Pederson and Walker, 2015). It indicates that the emotional connectivity of the employees is important with the brand and tends to affect corporate performance. It is made possible through higher sales turnover and a better relationship with the customers (Ruane and Wallace, 2013). The positive bond of the company and customers gives an upward direction to the event management sector. From this context, Herbig and Milewicz (2012) argued that branding could increase the sales and productivity of an organisation effectively and efficiently, thus leading to the growth and development of the organisation. This ensures more certainty and influences many customers to access cost-effective services (Apostolakis, Jaffry and Cox, 2015).

2.6 Impact of brand awareness on the intention of purchasing

Brand awareness is considered the most important tool that proves to be effective for recognition by the customers for a long period. (Glynn and Widjaja, 2015). The event management industry in the UK needs to bring a wide range of customers to the business and motivate them to come again. Further, if more people are aware of the brand, it helps create business for the event industry. However, the behaviour of brand awareness on intention to purchase can be understood with the help of consumer buyer behaviour (Cvijikj and Michahelles, 2013, Ng, Zhao and Rungtusanatham, 2014). The following mentioned process of intention to purchase consists of five procedures under which the first one sheds light on recognising the problem. For example, suppose a client wants to organise an employee award function to

appreciate personnel. In that case, it leads a particular person to search for information about which companies are there, offering services related to event management (Tungate, 2019).

The information search is a long procedure that also consists of both internal and external search.

Illustration 1: Consumer buying behaviour

(Source: Solomon, 2014)

Here, internal search is directly connected with a brand where the person tries to make a purchase decision based on experience (Yang and S. Mattila, 2014). This again shows which brand he or she preferred last time. It can be critically evaluated that the worst past experience might make the person move forward and search for good alternatives, value for money (Duma, Willi, Nguyen and Melewar, 2016). This aspect shows that brand image depends on an individual's experience, so if he has a good past experience, he can effectively search for the same brand. It reflects the purchase intention of the consumer.

On the other hand, the consumer is also willing to try a new product from external sources (Ng, Zhao and Rungtusanatham, 2014). This typically involves a search in the context of neighbours, family and friends, and others. Not only this but the official website of the business can also be referred to collect information. This is also considered the most appropriate way to understand the brand value, as customers review the feedback provided by existing users (Armstrong, Adam and Kotler, 2014, Cannon, Cannon and Andrews, 2014). However, the negative feedback affects their purchase decision to a great extent, and opt to search for another alternative.

Furthermore, positive feedback converts their intention to purchase into the actual decision of buying a particular brand. Therefore, an information search is the most important consumer buying behaviour where brand value is essential (Echambadi, Jindal and Blair, 2013). It enables a buyer to repeat purchase the product and accordingly show loyalty.

The third step of consumer buying behaviour is evaluating alternatives, which sheds light on assessing the brand's value. This evaluation procedure is completed with the help of a detailed assessment of customers' expectations and the effectiveness of the brand to meet the same (Cannon, Cannon and Andrews, 2014). Hence, an alternative to meeting the expectations of consumers might be considered the most effective. At this juncture, product recall, brand name and personal experience, and prestige are considered directly linked to a brand. (Tungate, 2019) asserted that brand awareness is the only factor that increases the attention of the customer to buy. However, few adventurous consumers like to risk and get fresh experience by trying the new brand (Sobihah, Mohamad and Ismail, 2015, Wang and Horng, 2016). This purchase decision might be associated with a very general kind of need or product used daily. Here, a customer might like to change the brand for a new or fresh experience.

The fourth stage of consumer buying behaviour is of purchase decision which reflects the buying value. This also consists of sub-stages such as which particular brand is best, which time is perfect, or not to purchase (M. Bizri, 2014). These options remain with the customer, and accordingly, try for particular brands. On a critical note, this fourth step of buying behaviour defines how the attitude of others, perceived risk and unanticipated situational factors are considered (Wang and Horng, 2016). These factors, too, are considered at the time of making a purchase decision. This proves to be effective for the corporation to communicate the positive factors related to the brand to influence others and increase the number of customers.

In addition to this, the last factor of consumer buying behaviour is a post-purchase decision where the value in use is considered (Punyatoya, 2015). At this juncture, clients of event management organisations compare their expectations with rendered services. This will have two outcomes, either satisfaction or dissatisfaction. Here, satisfaction results from a good experience or the right selection of the brand. On the other hand, dissatisfaction is the worst experience with a particular brand (Leyshon, Thrift and Webb, 2016). Beristain and Zorrilla (2011) asserted that the outcome affects the value personalities of customers and their communication and the repeat purchase decision. If a customer is satisfied with rendered services, then he will make a repeat

purchase decision. At the same time, communication would be greater as he can also recommend the particular brand to other people (Punyatoya, 2014).

Therefore, consumer buying behaviour is important and directly associated with the brand value of the business. This helps the corporation to deliver a good quality of services in accordance with consumer's requirement. The focus must also be laid on research and development activities to assess consumers' need and expectations (Alves, Fernandes and Raposo, 2016). This proves to be effective for implementing the right kind of retention strategy along with offering appropriate products. Thus, a business must consider the brand value to grab users' attention and stop them from switching to another brand (Kasemsap, 2015). Beristain and Zorrilla (2011) argued that by building brand awareness, the organisation could also increase its market share (Beristain and Zorrilla, 2011, East, Singh and Vanhuele, 2016). Suppose management are the first to the punch in getting the organisation brand fused into customers' minds. In that case, management will raise the barrier to other companies trying to enter the market.

According to (Tungate 2019), consumers generally give serious attention to the brand when purchasing decisions (Huang and Sarigöllü, 2014). It is because of perceived quality and other related features. Customers select a product or brand from a list in accordance with specific features such as price, quality and other related aspects (Pawaskar and Goel, 2014). For this purpose, customers find the product following their past experience and expectations. This would enable the corporation to engage the customers by meeting their requirement more effectively.

Apart from this, consumers are also asked to provide their feedback, and accordingly, the business addresses their issues. This makes their experience very positive and enables them to prefer a particular brand (East, Singh and Vanhuele, 2016). Tiago and Veríssimo (2014) asserted that the most popular brand has a higher chance of customer association than the one which is not popular. For this purpose, a firm uses appropriate marketing strategies and communication channels to have appropriate bonding with consumers (Simon, Simon and Fassnacht, 2016, Liat, Mansori and Huei, 2014). At the same time, the focus is laid on a particular brand and its unique feature to make it different from the one which competitors already offer.

In addition to this, loyalty driven consumer typology can be applied to the business. This can be understood by applying the Aaker model, which consists of five levels of brand loyalty.

Illustration 2: Aakar model

(Source: Annetonia, 2012)

The first element of this model is the switcher to the brand. It shows that buyers who are not loyal tend to use different brands every time. This kind of consumer believes in purchasing only the product at a relatively affordable price (Kim and Ahn, 2017). For this purpose, the event management sector tends to focus on price to attract such a user. It enables consumers to get a more suitable product in terms of a higher rate of return. However, such a kind of consumer creates an issue in meeting the brand image. This affects corporate image to a great extent. Owing to this, customers are targeted to get the product at the right price and ensure their retention with the particular brand (Liat, Mansori and Huei, 2014, Alavi, Wieseke and Guba, 2016).

However, the second level is habitual consumers who have no reason to change the product or brand. However, the second one reflects the customer's satisfaction or dissatisfaction (Kumar Mishra, Kumar Mishra and Das, 2016). At this juncture, buyers tend to focus on a particular brand from which they get a sense of satisfaction and might not think to change the brand. It can be critically evaluated that these customers might plan to change the product if gets an effective alternative (Melovic, Mitrovic and Vajčnerová, 2015). The third level reflects that satisfied customers incur a cost when switching to another brand. Tiago and Veríssimo (2014) argued that there are many ways organisations can go about boosting brand awareness amongst consumers and making a brand mean something to consumers when they look at it is just as important as a sales pitch (Tiago and Veríssimo, 2014, Alavi, Wieseke and Guba, 2016). Here, switching cost includes variables such as loss of time, acquired loyalty advantages and money,

and performance risk (Alavi, Wieseke and Guba, 2016). Because of this, the corporation gets the negative impact of switching buyers. This becomes critical for corporations to focus on the needs and expectations of buyers. Therefore, the management of Event Management Corporation makes sure that customers are not switching to other brands, and this can be easily handled by the firm (Calvo-Porrall, Martinez-Fernández and Lévy-Mangín, 2013).

The fourth level of the graph contains the buyers who like the brand. Here, customers like to be attached to a particular brand emotionally rather than wasting their time switching to another brand (Desmet, 2014). However, there is some base on which customer like the particular brand. It consists of a symbol, high perceived quality and the mindset of use experience. Owing to this, the customer gets attracted to a product. It also indicates that the long-term relationship of customers with an organisation aids to increase their retention rate (Hsu, 2014). A business can easily support all related customers by forming long-term relationships. It is helpful to accomplish long as well as short-term objectives. For this purpose, customers' emotional attachment with a brand is important through which it becomes easy to retain them for a longer period and provides them lucrative products and services (Jeon, Jeon and Baeck, 2016).

The fifth level of the loyalty pyramid shows the committed customers. Here, customers are proud to have a particular brand and would like to show it off. This emphasises the importance of the brand, its quality and price, and other related features. Customers do not like to switch to another brand (Claudiu-Catalin, Dorian-Laurentiu and Andreea, 2014). Companies should focus on using the particular one, and this is called the last stage, where customers react positively to the products, brand and services, and variety. Therefore, the fifth level of customers is considered the most important, reflecting their loyalty towards a particular brand (Jin and Weber, 2013, Fujiwara and Nagasawa, 2015). This proves to be effective in catering to the requirement of all buyers and increases their satisfaction level to a great extent.

According to Henry Assael, there are four types of brand loyalty driven consumers. The first factor shows that complex loyal tend to focus on researching the new brand (Papasolomou, Crowther and Capaldi, 2016). Consumer focus on developing strong beliefs and attitudes towards the brand to make a perfect choice. On the other hand, the habitual loyal mainly decides based on the brand's familiarity and keeps on buying the same. It can be stated that this enables them to be loyal for a longer period following a specific brand (Fujiwara and Nagasawa, 2015, Al-Dmour, Zu'bi and Kakeesh, 2013). Variety seekers tend to become less involved with a

particular brand. It all depends on the incorporation of a suitable brand through which customers get attracted. The behaviour of individuals matters a lot, and accordingly, a decision is taken to deliver the most suitable project (Roncha and Radclyffe-Thomas, 2016).

It shows that brand awareness is very important for grabbing the attention of particular customers and enabling them to access the brands offered by event management companies (Calvo Porral, Martínez Fernández and Lévy Mangín, 2015). The aspect of brand awareness focuses on whether a customer can be loyal to a brand or not. Customers do not have to take a decision related to variety or pricing, but most of the time, quality matters a lot (Al-Dmour, Zu'bi and Kakeesh, 2013, Jung and Kim, 2015). Thus, businesses try their best to opt for the most effective strategy to retain their customers.

Another model of Keller's brand equity can be applied in the organisation, divided into four steps. The business considers these four steps to understand the situation effectively and handle all related issues (Sujchaphong, Nguyen and Melewar, 2017, Jung and Kim, 2015). The first step of this model is salient to which reflect the identity or awareness. This stage reflects that customer recognise a particular brand fulfilling their needs and expectations. From this, it can be said that it enables them to decide according to their requirement. At this stage, the management of the event management sector needs to understand the customers and their choices and research services offered by competitors (Jung and Kim, 2015). The second step is of the brand in which customers are offered products in line with their requirements. In this situation, buyers are happy with having the product align with their requirement (Cossío-Silva, Revilla-Camacho and Palacios-Florencio, 2016). It would be effective for a firm to deliver services that fulfil requirements and expectations.

The third step indicates brand response whereby the corporation targets factors like quality, consideration, superiority and credibility (Habibi, Laroche and Richard, 2014). The corporation considers these factors to select the most suitable product. The business needs to make sure that they consider all these aspects so that they will be able to develop positive perception within the minds of customers (Ryan and Silvanto, 2013). Because the decision related to quality, consideration and superiority is taken only based on buyers' expectations, it is the major reason that the third part of Keller's model helps in gaining the attraction of more buyers. Brand resonance is the last aspect of the model wherein categories such as community, attitudinal and behavioural loyalty are considered (Mishra, 2014).

Along with that, active engagement is also considered. All these aspects reflect how customers are connected with the brand. This assists a firm to involve the customers in the decision-making process and enables the firm to develop the products and services according to their requirements.

According to Leek and Christodoulides (2011), brand awareness is the result of purchase intention because when a person has a need, he will look for a certain brand. Hence, to get the appropriate one to cater to his requirement (Leek and Christodoulides, 2011). Therefore, purchase intention is linked with brand awareness, perceived quality and customer loyalty (Folgado-Fernández, Hernández-Mogollón and Duarte, 2017). From this, it can be evaluated that the profitability derived through brand results from the purchase intention. Owing to this, the focus is laid on strong purchase decisions, which makes it possible for the corporation to address the issues faced by the business (Chen, 2015). On the other hand, Booth and Matic (2011) studied the premium price of the products' products and services results from the brand. It helps the corporation to build a strong brand image and grab the attention of all buyers.

It is made possible only with the help of the link between the purchase intention and the effectiveness of the brand (Breugelmans, Bijmolt and Wunderlich, 2015). However, a brand consists of several factors such as perception and trust as well as its recall. It is the major reason companies use appropriate market strategies whereby buyers can be targeted in a relatively less period. However, the premium price is the single component carried in most customers' minds (Jiang and Zhang, 2016). When the price of the products and services is high, customers can shift to other companies. Generally, brands remain costly and focus on the attention of the customers. It can be critically evaluated that the brand of well-known products positively impacts customer preferences to effectively promote the respective products and services (Ramiz, Qasim and Khurshid, 2014). This reflects that brand awareness is very important for creating a positive impact on consumers and endorses their purchase decision.

Khasawneh and Hasouneh (2010) asserted that the concept of celebrity endorsement is very effective to build the brand image as people get highly inspired through their role model or famous personality (Khasawneh and Hasouneh, 2010). They start to feel like that person they admire is also accessing the same kind of services (Liu, Huang and Chen, 2014). This gives them a sense of achievement, and they like to change their decision accordingly. However, it can be evaluated that it is very important to select only the positive personalities connected with

many people. It might be costlier for the business but still would be effective to boost the sales turnover drastically.

Thus, the selection of a brand ambassador should be perfect for aiding in achieving the long and short-term objectives of the business (MacGillavry and Wilson, 2014). At the same time, the requirement of stakeholders is met through the association of the right kind of people for promoting the services offered by the event management sector. The firm needs to understand the requirement of stakeholders to get to know the issues or problems they face. As per the analysis made, steps should be taken to overcome these problems (Almeida, Mazzon and Müller Neto, 2013). Apart from this, a well-designed logo should be prepared with an appropriate message that would effectively cater to all related parties' requirements. For this purpose, the language and images used in the advertisement should perfectly portray the organisation's image for the related stakeholders (Veljković and Kaličanin, 2016). Pullman and Gross (2004) reported that the project's tagline should also be mentioned properly to build the business's brand image.

For this purpose, a better relationship is important with the customers to create a positive image of the firm and influence its competitive edge in the marketplace (Daou, Karuranga and Su, 2014). These unique aspects must be incorporated into the business's strategy to build its brand image. For this purpose, companies can easily access the most important information related to customers by using appropriate modes of communication (Kondasani and Panda, 2015). Such kind practices determine the long-run success of the business with the use of clear communication with clients. In this manner, a sense of satisfaction is developed among clients, and they are provided with a comfortable work environment to meet the expectations of related stakeholders (Magatef and Tomalieh, 2015).

Shimp (2010) asserted that brand image effectively develops trust among customers by offering them a reputed brand in accordance with their desire (Shimp, 2010). There are certain sets of expectations which individuals/customers hold. When these are satisfied, they can develop trust for the services and products delivered to them (Davies and Freathy, 2014). They become highly involved in the purchase process and like to buy high-technology products. It is the major reason that event management companies must focus on customers' decision making with the impact of the strong brand image (Desai, Lianos and Waller, 2015). The brand image is

created by introducing the right kind of product or services via the most suitable mode of communication.

Businesses suffering from low sales turnover must investigate the availability of counterfeit products as, most of the time, such brands affect the performance of the actual brand (Boukis and Gounaris, 2014). For this purpose, a sense of satisfaction is derived by applying the right kind of products and services, enabling the buyers to access cost-effective products and the perfect quality of the product. In this manner, management aids in producing the brand image and creating a competitive edge in the marketplace (Shamim and Mohsin Butt, 2013). Therefore, the role of brand image is important for the success of the business and its direct impact on creating the brand image in the marketplace.

2.7 key factors influencing the intention to purchase

According to Hutter, Hautz and Füller (2013), different factors influence purchase intention. Organisations focus on increasing brand awareness among people all over the world. This is necessary because it helps in encouraging customers to buy a particular company product and services. A firm can increase brand awareness with the help of social media tools and techniques (Pike, 2013). In the modern era, people worldwide become familiar with different social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter, Linked In, etc., which all helps make people aware of particular brands. Firms can develop a strong relationship with customers, and they can know the issues they face with the services and the products (Shams, 2015). If a firm continuously advertises its products on different social networking sites, people are eager to buy its products. Firms can also use different types of strategy for grabbing the attention of customers. If a company uses discounting pricing strategy, it can easily get consumers' attention toward the product and services (Tabaku and Zerellari, 2015). Further, there is a great impact from brand awareness on the intention of purchasing by the customer.

If people continuously know about a particular company, they may think to buy from it. This helps increase the organisation's sales, thus boosting the firm's overall profit (Tsai, Joe and Shen, 2015). Brand awareness is the ability of the consumer to recognise and recall a brand in various situations. It plays a significant role in consumers' purchase intention and familiarity with a particular product (Govers and Go, 2016). For example, if any product gains a high level of brand awareness, that company may receive high customer preference, and from this, it can be

stated that this leads to an increase in market share. Some people are attached to a brand due to its high-quality services or price (Temporal, 2014). There are different ways a firm can easily create customers' intention for purchasing its products and services. Along with this, trust in the brand helps to increase the sales and profits of the organisation.

According to Round and Roper (2012), a purchase decision is taken based on the aspects of customers related to a particular brand due to its particular characteristics (Round and Roper, 2012). This is helpful for the corporation to purchase a particular product in some specific condition. It proves to be effective in catering to all related parties' requirements and supporting the business objectives in a most effective manner (Chen, Yen and Capistrano, 2016). If customers take frequent purchase decisions, then it becomes very easy to create the competitive edge of the corporation in the marketplace with the increased rate of return. Other firms focus on delivering their customer's similar products and services (Todor, 2014). In other words, there are many competitors, so it provides the opportunity for customers to choose other products and services that other firms deliver. On a critical note, the customer purchase decision is very complex due to their influence from several factors associated with a particular brand (Malone and Fiske, 2013). It consists of several aspects such as the attitude of customers, their perception and behaviour. However, all products consist of other kinds of features which might be different for several parties. Spry, Pappu and Cornwell (2011) critically evaluated that the buying process can be predicted using the customer's intention to purchase.

However, purchase intention might be different due to factors such as price, quality and value. For example, Marriott Hotel charges higher prices for its product, but customers remain ready to pay them just because of its brand value (Kujala, 2014). On the contrary, any hotel operating at the start-up level cannot change the higher prices because it is not well known. However, when customers seek a lower-priced product, they become ready to compromise with quality. For this purpose, consumers' buying behaviour is focused on their exact requirement, and an appropriate decision can be taken to purchase the right kind of product offered by the business (Vaishnavi, Ganesh and Thomas, 2014). At this juncture, companies shed light on creating suitable products so that these can be designed to meet the expectations and requirements of consumers effectively.

According to Lu, Chang and Chang (2014), a brand's image helps portray the brand's overall personality (Lu, Chang and Chang, 2014). Brand attitude is in relation to the advertisement, which directly impacts the attitude toward the brand. When deciding to purchase, the customer moves under five stages: Problem recognition: At this stage, the problem is recognised, and the buyer needs to satisfy his requirements (Yang, 2017). It is the beginning of the buyer decision process. Information search: this information is searched for which product can satisfy their need and want. The organisation that has built its image in the market or creates awareness of its product may first choose the product. Alternative evaluation: There are different alternatives available for the buyer. From different alternatives, the buyer may choose one after researching them (Varey, 2015). Purchase condensation: At this stage, the buyer makes a particular decision for buying the product. The customer goes with that product and service whose brand image is good in the market.

These are all the consumer buying decisions that help make a proper decision by the customer. If any firm continuously creates awareness of its brand, it is set in people's minds, leading to increased sales. Also, a consumer has a higher purchase intention if he becomes familiar with a particular brand (Malhotra and Kubowicz Malhotra, 2013). A brand purchase may lead to the repurchase of the product and services. If the positive customer is feeling toward the brand, it will produce a purchase decision. To promote the consumer's brand loyalty, the firm should create high awareness and good images. If the brand has a good image in the market, people will buy that product without further thought, but if its image is negative, people avoid buying that company's product (Wallace, Lings and Sheldon, 2014). In addition to this, if any company does not advertise its product or promote its brand, people will not be aware of it and not buy the product. So it can be stated that firms must create brand awareness among people for increasing sales and overall profits of the organisation (Lin, 2013). A company can use different tools and techniques for creating brand awareness to impact the intention of purchase of the consumer.

According to Herbig and Milewicz (2012), brand awareness and purchase intention can be understood with the help of the two most important variables. The first is the independent variable brand awareness. It enables a business to cater to the requirements of all related parties such as shareholders, employees and customers. At this juncture, the brand is recognised with the help of marketing strategies. For example, social media, the internet and other related strategies

are applied, which aids to cater to the need of all related parties (Trudeau and Shobeiri, 2016). Here, the independent variable brand awareness facilitates taking a purchase decision effectively.

This enables a corporation to integrate all business activities and supports the business to carry out all activities, which aid in delivering a good quality of services to many buyers. Hyun and Kim (2011) reported that factors like brand recognition, recalling, top of the mind, and brand name dominance must be considered in the line of purchase intention (Hyun and Kim, 2011). Here, the corporation puts efforts to acquire the necessary resources and utilise them to produce a valid outcome and accomplish long and short-term objectives (Wahab, Hassan and Maon, 2016). Here, the company commissions its marketing manager to allocate the necessary resources. In this manner, the corporation can effectively communicate the relevant message to all its parties and have the appropriate brand management aspect. When a customer considers a particular brand, they tend to use the suitable approach to inform their relatives (Rahman, 2014). This is done with the help of word of mouth as they share their recommendations with their relatives in order for them to get the best suitable product in accordance with their requirement.

Purchase intention is considered as the dependent variable. It would be effective for business to shed light on specific aspects through which the attention of customers can be gained (Thomas, 2015). Aspects like internet marketing are applied along with other marketing strategies, which contribute towards selecting the most suitable method for attracting more buyers. It helps support all related customers and effectively carry out their purchasing process (Jin, Park and Li, 2015, Kumar, 2013). Hence, the connection between brand awareness and the loyalty it evokes seems the most important factor for the growth and development of the business.

According to Aaker and Joachimsthaler (2012), brand strategies are considered the most significant tools derived only from the marketing department. This is because marketing has a strong connection with the brand of the business. It was proposed that branding is just an iceberg that reflects that the surface must be pushed up to make the brand visible to its related parties (Mohan Kathuria and Gill, 2013). On a critical note, an organisation that cannot make its brand visible suffers from poor organisational culture and customer experience.

Businesses face challenges in coping with changing scenarios and face several issues in creating a strong brand image. The concept of Brand Corporation presents itself to the

organisation (Goyal and Srivastava, 2015, Keohane, 2014). They further asserted that brand is considered the strongest asset for the business, which is developed only with the help of improving the service quality and meeting customers' expectations effectively. The representation of the company is done solely with the help of its brand. The company with a strong brand image possesses an appropriate market share and a pool of customers who stay connected with the business and support it to increase the overall rate of return.

Illustration 3: Branding iceberg
(Source: Vadhani, 2017)

The above branding iceberg shows several elements seen by the customers and not seen by them. This model represents how the company build its image or brand value by satisfying the customers. Here, two major components must be considered, such as what can be seen by customers and another part which they do not see (Beverland, Wilner and Micheli 2015). However, from this, it can be evaluated that the bottom surface of the model shows key assets and competencies which any others cannot see except the competitors. It includes high quality, efficient production, low-cost operation and a strong supply chain. Using a strong supply chain ensures its low-cost operation and makes it possible to offer the product relatively low (Subramanian, Gunasekaran and Gao, 2016, Lam, Ho and Law, 2015). At the same time, aspects related to the supply chain include effective policies and long-term contracts with suppliers. It is the fact that a well-established contract with suppliers is the key to the success of the business

because then a consistent flow of production is maintained without incurring huge cost (Fleury, Cardoso and Marques, 2014, Carter, Wright and Klein, 2014). This is considered the most important aspect behind reducing operations and adequately supporting product-related activities.

The model of the brand iceberg also includes research and development and high service levels as well as effective selling. These components remain the basic level of the model to effectively carry out all operation activities (Kaufmann, Kaufmann and Manarioti, 2016, Rosenbaum-Elliott, Percy and Pervan, 2015). With the help of the activities mentioned above, the business can effectively expand in the global marketplace, and in turn, the obstacles related to its operation can be reduced. This can be done when proper research is undertaken to evaluate the country where the business is to be expanded. This is because research and development provide insight to the marketing department and, accordingly, the company as a whole (Carter, Wright and Klein, 2014). In this manner, products and services are offered in accordance with the requirement of the customers. These integrated below the surface elements facilitate the company to make the appropriate decisions and cooperate with the related department to accomplish the business activities effectively and accomplish their long and short-term objectives (Lam, Ho and Law, 2015).

Balakrishnan, Nekhili and Lewis (2011) asserted that each organisation must maintain key assets and competencies to focus on the branding strategy and observe the significant impact of the same in terms of a higher customer base and competitive edge of the business (Balakrishnan, Nekhili and Lewis, 2011, Chen, 2015). This would be effective for the business to deliver a good quality of services to end-users and ensure sustainable growth and development of the business in the marketplace (Keohane, 2014). On the other hand, the top surface of the iceberg model is more important because all parties see it but only based on key assets and competencies. Owing to this, the major focus is laid on the competencies and key aspects of the corporation to strengthen the business's internal operation. Therefore, the internal operation must be strong and sound from which the business's competitive edge is created in the marketplace (Mosley, 2014, Bruhn, Schoenmueller and Schäfer, 2012). Braimah and Tweneboah-Koduah (2011) critically evaluated that the lack of financial resources and others harms the corporation's performance (Balakrishnan, Nekhili and Lewis, 2011). Therefore, the business must resolve

potential issues that the business faces; then, the firm can effectively maintain its strong presence in the marketplace (Kumar, 2013).

There are several marketing factors such as symbol, brand name and prices as well as advertising. Also, presentation is another crucial aspect that is considered by the management to create the strong goodwill of the firm for meeting the satisfaction level of customers (Siala, 2013, Larsen, 2014). These aspects are focused on by the firm in order to create the brand. At the same time, a strong impact is created in terms of price and advertisement; appropriate trends of advertisement such as social media and celebrity endorsement are used (Pongjit and Beise-Zee, 2015). Thus, a specific title is given to a brand, and the company puts efforts to make it renowned through the construction of the most effective type of advertisement.

Kapferer (2012) reflected that creating the most suitable advertisement is the important aspect in which a business comes to know about the potential market and then accordingly passes on the important message (Kapferer, 2012, Lumsdo, 2016). This integrated approach of different components contributes towards visualising the brand and catering for the requirement of all related parties effectively (Monfared, 2015). Therefore, both aspects are focused on the branding iceberg's help and making the brand known in the national and international markets.

An appropriate pricing strategy is another crucial aspect through which customers make a purchase decision. Also, the advertisement influences the client of event management companies to access the good quality of products and services (Lumsdo, 2016, Mohsin and Lengler, 2015). By this, the firm's goodwill is created, and the company enhances its market share effectively. This, in turn, reflects that brand strategy and purchase intention are positively related. Therefore, suitable branding strategies are also important, along with sales tactics (Larsen, 2014). These strategies would be effective for companies to approach the customers and support them in creating the most suitable model for attracting more customers.

According to Bruhn, Schoenmueller and Schäfer (2012), companies must conduct their self-analysis to identify how strong their brand concerns the customers' response (Bruhn, Schoenmueller and Schäfer, 2012). This would collect valuable information and bring positive changes in the overall work of the business. The brand's contribution is very important in creating a positive impression among customers (Chen, 2015, Monfared, 2015). This would help them take the purchase decision because they are offered a varied range to select the most suitable product that best meets their requirement and supports them to contribute to the

business's success. The business applies the appropriate product positioning formula and dynamic brand. New customers can be invited, and the current ones can be retained for a longer time- span (Rosenbaum-Elliott, Percy and Pervan, 2015). It leads to determine the success of the business and increased rate of return along with a strong brand image. Here, the company must keep in mind that the advertisement must be focused on the colour scheme and design layout to keep the brand known.

Here, the brand reflects the perception of customers how effectively they can interact with them and capture their attention effectively (Mohsin and Lengler, 2015, Kapferer, 2012). Thus, the company creates a positive impact through which buyers find it feasible to take a quick purchase decision. However, customers do not always rely on the marketers, but their experience associated with a brand makes a significant difference. The overall focus is on quality improvement and a wide range of goods for the customers. By the use of branding strategies, the company can accordingly grab the attention of the customers.

Dolbec and Chebat (2013) reported that advertisement is the only means of communication-related to a brand for the buyers' information (Dolbec and Chebat, 2013). It is not always helpful for them to take a quick purchase decision, but the role of references and friends is important. It is because experience influences an individual to purchase a particular brand (Mosca, Bertoldi and Giachino, 2015). Therefore, branding creates a unique position for event management companies and enables them to create a strong presence and retain many buyers. Still, promotional activities are kept at the centre to make it possible to attract the attention of buyers and provide them with suitable information to take frequent purchase decisions.

2.8 Effectiveness of customised sales strategy influencing purchase intention of target customers.

According to Buil, Martínez and de Chernatony (2013), they must influence their customers with their differentiated sales strategies for all companies. These strategies and tactics include social media and effective promotional events. All sales activities which the company is conducting must be very effective so that more customers could be attracted towards them. The Event Management Company should formulate proper and good planning for all its activities to attract more people.

Punyatoya (2014) stated that the sales strategies would attract customers only if companies put in their best efforts. The purchase intention of target customers' needs to be first identified so that the company is working according to it and gaining more customers.

2.9 Branding strategies

Planning helps in strategically analysing the pathway, which helps a company to brand itself. Modern-day consumers have a general perception that branded products and services have excellent quality (Badrinarayanan, Sierra and Taute, 2014). Despite their high prices or moderate quality, a brand holds its unique place in the eyes of consumers. In line with Jaikumar's and Sahay's (2015)'s thoughts, branding is one of the essential attributes that help in meeting consumer requirements and emotions. Increasing competition is tackled with greater effectiveness and consistency through a systematically planned branding strategy. In consonance with the research produced by Veloutsou and Guzmán (2017), an emotional impact on a consumer's perception is like a triumph card for the respective company. The sales and profit margins of the company increase on a directly proportional ratio.

The knowledge of the target consumer is quite essential for brand identity development and the implementation of the branding strategy (Vu and Huan, 2016). A company's strong position is created when customers' demands and needs are met with corresponding products and services. In line with Williams and Williams (2017), the respective event management organisation's objectives need to be aligned with a respective strategy. Critical reflection of such attributes in the campaigns and events help in making better connections with the audience. The target customer does not find it difficult to focus on the capabilities and competencies of the brand (Oliveira and Rodrigues, 2015). This improves effectiveness. As per Mann and Kaur (2013), the company's identity becomes relatable with a higher value proposition.

Communication is said to be the most important element when business strategies are developed and implemented. The platform provided through branding helps build communication channels with the customers so that necessary feedback, reviews, and opinions for the concerned service are gained at hand (Kumar and Pansari, 2016). Furthermore, the purpose behind the organisation's functioning and administering of the event is fulfilled through branding strategies, as Punyatoya (2014) mentioned. Progress can be created by an organisation only when continuous innovation is achieved. Event management organisations cannot use the same theme or structure for every cause and client. This would create monotonicity and reduce

the audience's interest (Bijmolt, Krafft and Viswanathan, 2018). Innovation is a branding strategy that enforces the audience to get involved with the respective company and explore new dimensions of creativity, as Zenker and Jacobsen (2015) stated.

Social media marketing and search engine optimisation are key tools that are used in internet marketing. The use of these tools for branding helps develop the brand image amongst consumers who are more active in the virtual world (Karjaluoto, Mustonen and Ulkuniemi, 2015). According to Punyatoya (2014), flexibility is an important tool that has to be involved in branding strategies (Punyatoya, 2014). The goals and objectives developed by the event management company can only be accomplished if there is flexibility for respective changes in the demands and supply of consumers or competition. Seizing opportunities for acquiring maximum consumers is performed through traditional media, mails, telemarketing and promotional events. However, the influence of these traditional sales process has reduced over time (Kato and Schoenberg, 2014). Currently, branding strategy is more oriented toward campaigns that are either initiated online or organised in the form of live events.

In line with this, Jayakumar and Sahay (2015) stated that social media and business development go hand in hand (Jaikumar and Sahay, 2015). The use of social media platforms widely helps in marketing and branding all the company's products and services, which further helps competitive positioning. Customers' prospects are centralised, and campaigning's overall motive and purpose are achieved successfully (Faryabi, Sadeghzadeh and Zakeri, 2015). The major advantage of branding is its presence amongst customers irrespective of whether they purchase services.

2.10 Role of branding in marketing

It is in accordance to Gallucci Santulli and Calabrò (2015), branding is recognised to play a very important role in marketing, where it significantly assists the organisations to get into such marketing practices that, in turn, fulfil the realistic needs and demands of their customers (Gallucci Santulli and Calabrò, 2015). Branding in marketing plays a leading role in the companies associated with the arrangement of events, mostly recognised as event management firms (Larkin, 2013). These types of ventures present themselves as promotional companies by getting into the various strategies incorporated by marketing. There is a greater role of branding in their accepted marketing practices. This is also due to a high level of competition among such establishments (Mrkosová, Dufek and Majer, 2014, Sun, Tong and Law, 2017). This duly

necessitates them to adopt some unique practices that in turn give appealing recognition to their brand.

Williams and Williams (2017) have stated that this realisation has a potent impact on organisations' undertaken strategies that reflect the prime importance of branding in marketing (Williams and Williams, 2017). However, it is linked to yet another likely aspect of creating effortless measures for customers by which they can easily relate the brand to their proposed goods and services. Branding in marketing does not symbolise the name and logo of the organisation to typify the brand (Tong and Wong, 2014, Luis Méndez, Oubiña and Rubio, 2011). However, together they represent the face of the establishment that is being envisioned by a consumer while referring to its offered goods and services.

Punyatoya (2014) has referred to a vital reason that states the significance of branding in the marketing procedure that involves a clear message delivery (Punyatoya, 2014). The branding strategy can be used as a communicative measure to interact with the clients without disbursing a huge amount of funds. It, however, requires a well-designed brand to deliver likely messages to them (Candelo, Casalegno and Civera, 2014). Due to this, branding has shown vital importance in marketing, where it mostly aids in carrying out an uninterrupted relationship with the customers. Besides this, customisation of the brand is also considered a facet that defines a strategic approach to interact with the customers (Chang, Lee and Yen, 2015). It is by branding the commodities according to the choice of the consumers that in turn results in reaching the targeted point of success. This, in turn, leads to motivating the buyers by connecting them with the offered goods and services and creating a strong relationship between them. Nolan (2015) has a discerning outlook towards the signs mentioned above in marketing towards creating a credible business (Nolan, 2015). However, it must be followed by a continual association of the brand with that to the proposed goods and services (Vinh, 2016). It necessitates the firms to produce inventive goods that provide a top-grade service to the customers with dependable commodities, with a special event management entity.

Research gap

It has been identified that there exists a gap in the market due to which companies are not able to identify the purchase intention of customers and how they need to make them aware. Besides that, it is determined that brand awareness is not linked with purchase intention. Hence, it is necessary to find out how brand awareness results in influencing customers' purchase

behaviour. Thus, the present study has been conducted to analyse the impact of brand awareness on customers' purchase intention. It enables companies to assess those factors through which customers can be attracted towards the particular brand (Burmam and et al., 2017). It enables the management of the business to apply the most effective strategies for the promotion of their brand and make the customers aware of it.

Conceptual Framework

The study of consumers' purchase intention towards brands does not limit to certain factors. However, all the factors cannot be covered in one study, Therefore, this study attempts to build a conceptual framework that uses a combination of some important factors to explain the variation in consumers' purchase intentions towards brands. With the help of the literature review, a simple yet effective conceptual framework has been developed to investigate the factors affecting consumers' purchase intentions towards brands.

The purchase intention of a customer is an attitude-like judgement following a purchase or a series of consumer product interactions. The customer decides whether he or she is satisfied after purchasing an item or after experiencing some kind of service encounter with a representative of a company. Customer satisfaction comes from the quality of service delivery that is expected by the customers during the act of purchase and while being served especially in this research which concerned with the buying of products such as Tickets from a mid sized company.

Customer satisfaction of a product is often measured with specific attributes that describe the product features. Comparing experiences to earlier expectations is also common. Similar elements of assessing the features of physical goods have been taken into models that describe how service is experienced. Due to this development, there have been debates in literature, whether there is a difference between service quality and customer satisfaction and if so, is the quality experienced first and satisfaction follows or vice versa. Logical analysis proves that this debate is irrelevant. Service quality is experienced first, followed by either feeling of satisfaction or dissatisfaction.

Customers have certain standards and expectations in mind before consumption, they observe the service performance, compare it to their standards and finally, form a satisfaction judgement when comparing with earlier expectations. These judgements can be labelled either negative confirmation when the service is lower than expected or positive confirmation when the service exceeds expectations or simply confirmation when the service is just as expected.

However, it is believed that perceived service quality is only one component of customer intention toward s brand. Satisfaction and quality have things in common but certain underlying causes are different. Purchase intention is a broader concept whereas service quality has specified aspects of service. Hence, perceived service quality is an element of customer satisfaction.

2.11 Summary

The motive of the literature review is to establish the theoretical framework. In this context, the researcher has provided detailed information about branding by using different theories and concepts. The researcher has also discussed the importance of branding to mid-sized businesses by providing plenty of examples. The concept of brand awareness and intention to purchase has been elaborated by the researcher in this chapter in a detailed manner. The Importance of brand awareness for the event management industry in the UK has been identified. The key factors influencing the intention to purchase and branding in marketing have been examined in this thesis. Furthermore, there are different types of strategies that companies use to raise brand awareness and these form the communication channel, which helps to be an effective element that helps people to know about the goods delivered by the company. When the amount of information people has about the product is high, it positively helps raise brand awareness.

STRUCTURE OF RESEARCH WITH OBJECTIVE

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter is about research methodology, which is a method to ascertain the results of a presented difficulty on a particular affair that defines the problem statement of the research work. Research Methodology is used to determine how the investigator can consider solving the identified statement of the issue where it also presents various alternatives to choose from. This is about the techniques required to carry out the study that moves to MCI UK Limited. It is also referred to be a considerate approach for addressing the problem by lastly reaching its undertaken goals and objectives. However, this part is also apparent to show discerning results due to the surveyor's selected tools that are often different.

It, therefore, depends upon the chosen subject matter on which basis the surveyor has framed the aims and objective of the study. A prompt selection of techniques to conduct the study by attaining its defined aims and objectives is also considered a considerate task for the investigator that requires many considerations. Thus, in methodology, the researcher uses distinct criteria for resolving the framed research question. It is also important for the researcher to continually go through the problem statement of the undertaken investigation. Also, it is another fact where various sources are known to use various methods to solve an issue.

Considering the actual meaning of term methodology, it is referred to as how an investigation problem is being analysed and resolved. Besides this, some secondary research has proven another substantial meaning of research: to reply to unanswered queries by exploring such things that presently do not exist. In accordance with this, this indicates a cautious research work that is enquired by scrutinizing newer facts in any subdivision of knowledge (Tsai, Joe and Shen, 2015).

Whereas some refer to research to be a systematic effort made to increase one's cognition level. In an investigation, the researcher is always required to search for pertinent answers to the framed question that necessitates a systematic procedure to reach a justified conclusion at the end. Likewise, it also necessitates the surveyor to undertake one's mode to achieve the aims and objectives. However, the researcher may also face numerous issues while exploring the questions and their answers that can be effectively resolved by choosing the most appropriate tools and techniques to carry out the study.

Research methodology is the important part of the thesis or dissertation that provides the entire process used to collect information and analyse the same. Generally, research is considered a systematic approach or process for completing a certain topic or study based on a set pattern. With clear evidence of research methodology, the effective structure of the dissertation or study can be provided to attain the stated aim and objectives. The application or selection of the most suitable method would contribute towards bringing the appropriate outcome for the investigation (Sam and Daniel, 2011). The research methodology section provides a better idea to the researcher which methodology or technique is more suitable to derive the valid outcome and several alternatives. In this manner, research methodology can be considered the pathway to ensure systematic completion of the study by keeping into account the selected research problem.

This third chapter of the thesis entails different aspects such as research design, approach, data collection methods, and techniques applied to analyse data. However, every research or study is based on a certain pattern, so that section of research methodology provides evidence and a detailed description of the same. Furthermore, research methodology provides a general explanation of methodology and offers justification for the selected one (Saunders and et al., 2009). Apart from this, some specific methods that are not related or specific to the study are also described, along with the rationale that they are not being selected. In addition to this, drawbacks and positive aspects associated with each research method are explained or described more clearly to present the outcome of the thesis in a more precise manner. In the current study of the impact of brand awareness on purchase intention, the following methodology has been used.

3.2 Data collection methods

Data collection is the part of the research methodology in which the researcher decides to select the most suitable technique for collecting the information required to answer the research questions. Generally, two types of information are collected, such as primary and secondary. Primary data are collected first-hand for the investigation's specific purpose, whereas secondary data is collected from the existing material. The collection of primary data is time-consuming, for the researcher needs to arrange several things to complete the process (Marlow, 2010). There are several methods used for collecting primary information, such as questionnaire surveys, interviewing, observation methods, experimentation, and variations of these fundamental

techniques. However, it is important to select the most suitable method for gathering the information in the current research aim. At this juncture, the questionnaire and interview methods have been selected to meet the specific purpose of the investigation.

Additionally, sources such as journals, books and online articles are selected to collect secondary information about the impact of brand awareness on purchase intention. They provide in-depth information about the topic under investigation and assist the researcher in meeting the research objective. Moreover, past research reports and other specific or relevant information have also been considered for the investigation (Singh, 2010). In total 100 questionnaires have been collected from five companies, 20 from each company. To select the 20 customers from the five companies, the researcher asked permission from the company's management, who hold the information concerning their customers. The researcher then contacted those customers through telephone and provided them with information about the research; after gaining their consent, the researcher provided the questionnaire to them to complete and return it to the respective organisation for the researcher to collect.

Data collection holds much importance in the research proposal as that aids the researcher to obtain appropriate data from specific sources. With the help of data collection, the researcher has enhanced the research procedure by focusing on diverse sources. In the present study, both primary and secondary sources have been used in different contexts. In addition, the researcher is focusing mainly on primary sources because that allows the use of original, accurate and relevant data. The use of both primary and secondary sources is helpful for the researcher in many ways. Using primary sources, the researcher has ensured that appropriate participants are involved in the research procedure to collect suitable data. On the other hand, secondary sources are also used to complete the section of the literature review. It will give insight into the views of the previous author about brand awareness and purchasing.

Secondary sources such as books, journals, and articles are being used to ascertain the appropriateness of the content. Previous literature is also used in the study to explore the concepts behind the subject matter. Secondary sources include data published in books, newspapers, journals, magazines and online portals. The abundance of data is available from sources that have previously been the research subject (Govers and Go, 2016).

The primary data was gathered by a mixed-method questionnaire survey and semi-structured interviews. Research instruments, in the form of a questionnaire and interview

schedule, were provided to the participants by the researcher in order to collect suitable and valid data about the subject matter. Several questions were included in the questionnaire given to 100 customers of five companies in the event management industry. Customers were selected who know the exact aspects that changed their purchasing decisions. Five mid-sized event management companies were selected that operated their businesses in the UK. Each entity was asked to collect data from 20 customers. Questionnaires were distributed through e-mails; they were appropriately collected after finishing the entire process.

Questionnaires included both close-ended and open-ended questions, as the researcher aims to collect quantitative and qualitative data. At the same time, interviews were also carried out to collect more information about the subject matter. Therefore, in the present study, mixed methods have been used. Five structured interviews have been conducted with the marketing managers who were working in the five mid-sized event-based companies. This source was used to identify the challenges faced by those companies when developing effective sales strategies (Round and Roper 2012).

Interviews were carried out at the office premises of each company during lunchtime, thus saving time. From this discussion, it is clear that the use of both sources is quite useful in enhancing the validity and creditability of the research procedures. The primary data collection method is divided into parts, i.e. quantitative and qualitative; both have been used together in the study.

The use of both qualitative and quantitative methods have been used in investigating the topic of study. The conducting of highly structured interviews with the respondents, 5 managers of mid-sized companies, one from each of 5 companies in the events management sector, has effectively assisted in effectively carrying out the qualitative analysis: the data obtained is likely to assist in getting the desired results as per the formulated aim and objectives of the study. All this type of data will be helping the research to establish their thinking and critical analysis. So, this will play a very important and essential role in collecting data and its analysis. Conducting highly structured interviews will help analyse the ideas and thinking about brands and sales strategies within event management companies.

3.3 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is a specific aspect of the study in which the scope, nature and development of knowledge are facilitated. The process is essential as it includes knowledge as a

major dimension of completing the research study. This is also useful for collecting valid and appropriate data regarding the subject matter. It will also aid the researcher to get answers to the research questions and, at the same time, it also helps in creating new knowledge. The research philosophy section is based on several beliefs and assumptions, and such things need to be considered while formulating the research procedure. The research onion model was developed to show that different tools and philosophies are being used to conduct the research procedure (Tabaku and Zerellari, 2015). A consumer is always hesitant of buying new products. Before buying anything a wise consumer will always do the market research or ask someone he trusts and after being well aware of what, how, and where to buy? He will buy the product. If a person comes to know any unfavourable information about a product, he will not buy it. Therefore, we can say that building a positive image of their brand companies have to try very hard. To keep the consumer aware of their brand and to sustain their customer a company will have to keep triggering its brand and advertise more and more to let a large number of people know about their brand.

Every stage present in the research process is based on diverse assumptions about several sources that enhance knowledge's nature. Therefore, it can be said that research philosophy is a vast subject that aids the investigator in using several aspects to reach the study's aim and objectives. Practical implications impact the choice of a specific philosophy, and this also focuses on different facts and numbers, which enhances the suitability and validity of the research procedure. The categories of research philosophy are Interpretivism, Positivism, Realism and Pragmatism.

Pragmatism research philosophy uses many ways to interpret things, and it is also useful in suitably undertaking research aspects. Therefore, multiple realities can be applied in a single term of managing the research contexts. According to this research philosophy, the most important dimension is the research question. It can also combine both positivist and interpretivism research philosophies within the scope of single research. This also defines the specific nature of the research question. Additionally, it integrates many research approaches and research strategies within a single study.

Interpretivism. The researcher is linked with reality and is inseparable from it. In this knowledge is based on the abstract descriptions of meanings, formed of human experiences, case studies, interviews, phenomenology, ethnography, ethnomethodology. Whereas *Pragmatism is*

*linked where reality is ambiguous, but based on language, history, and culture respect knowledge is derived from experience. Therefore, it helps to restores subjectively assigned and “objective” meaning of other actions Interview, case study, survey and **Positivism** linked with where reality is objective and perceived. Acquisition of knowledge is not related to values and moral content Survey, experiment, quasi-experiment. Although the paradigm has already been mentioned, for the researcher, to understand different combinations of research methods, it is necessary to analyse the basic concepts and to perceive the philosophical position of research problems.*

The scientific research paradigm and philosophy depend on various factors, such as the individual's mental model, his worldview, different perception, many beliefs, and attitudes related to the perception of reality, etc. Researchers' beliefs and values are important in this concept to provide good arguments and terminology for obtaining reliable results. The researcher's position in certain cases can have a significant impact on the outcome of the research.

Research philosophy refers to gathering only facts and figures through observation. The findings are quantifiable as data is collected objectively. This enables in getting an empiricist view of knowledge as per human experience. Based on the general overview, positivist studies adopt a deductive approach wherein the researcher must concentrate on facts. (Singh, 2010).

Inductive philosophy

This also includes a discussion about inductive reasoning that is specifically used to develop a statement. At the same time, it can also assist in testing research criteria during the research process. Therefore, logical aspects should be used in this respect to judging the criteria of the research procedure. This also denotes a study that has a direct relationship between diffusion of theoretical and conceptual aspects. According to generalised aspects, research involves theoretical dimensions to develop hypotheses, further tested while conducting the research process. It also relies on two distinct variables to showcase the interrelationship.

Realism is another category of research philosophy that relies on the independence of reality from the human mind. It is also a branch of epistemology as it is based on the scientific

approach assumption. At the same time, it leads to the development of knowledge from several grounds; hence the research validity can be specified accordingly.

In the study, Interpretivism philosophy has been used because it allows the researcher to interpret the elements of the study in a suitable manner. It also assumes that access to reality is acquired only through social constructions, including shared meanings and instruments. At the same time, it is also associated with the philosophical position of idealism; hence, it is used to group different approaches in the study. As per the philosophy, the researcher operates as a social actor, which allows the appreciation of differences in people. Moreover, this is also used in the present study because it usually focuses on the meaning and may also employ multiple methods (Marlow, 2010). This is typically used to reflect different aspects of the research issue.

At the same time, the Interpretivism approach is based on a naturalistic approach to data collection; hence, different primary and secondary methods were considered in the research process. Secondary data is also used in the research study to secure more data about the research process. In such studies, meanings are usually derived at the end of the research process; several variations can be considered.

The interpretivism philosophy has been done, which is regarded as another form of research methodology. Henceforth all the real figures and associated facts are going to be discussed. As an outcome of this, a small sample of respondents has been undertaken to evaluate in detail, thereby enriching the quality of obtained data (Sam and Daniel, 2011). Thus, the interpretivism approach will help the researcher build up the theories and concepts related to companies' brand awareness and purchasing intention. This is used because it will help formulate proper planning and achieve all of them towards the end of the research.

3.4 Research approach

Research philosophy is the most important part of the scientific study, and it usually does not focus on any specific research area. There are three major categories of research approaches: deductive, inductive, and abductive, and all three categories have different aspects to consider. The basic criterion that differentiates all the three categories is the relevance of the hypothesis. The deductive approach tests the validity of assumptions; however, the inductive approach contributes to developing new theories. The present thesis has been following the deductive approach for collecting survey data. Afterwards, a research strategy is has been designed to test the hypothesis (Tungate, 2009).

Deductive also means reasoning from general to specific; hence that allows the researcher to enhance the validity of research aspects. If a causal relationship occurs between variables, it might reach the defined aim and objectives. Similarly, a deductive design is also useful in testing if there is any relationship between general circumstances. It is effectively explained by focusing on hypotheses that are used to test theories. In other words, the deductive approach is also used since it is concerned with producing specific conclusions from value propositions. In the present thesis, the deductive approach is selected because it initiates with expected patterns that can further be tested against observations (Saunders and et al., 2009).

The deductive research approach also aids in exploring a known theory that proves to be valid in various circumstances. The researcher used this approach to follow the path of logical values that are highly integrated. Chiefly, this reasoning starts with a theory, and after that, it leads to the development of a new hypothesis. Afterwards, this hypothesis is put to the test by considering it with observations and data, leading to confirmation or rejection of the selected hypothesis. Therefore, it can be said that the researcher has used this technique as it starts from reasoning, which moves from general to specific (Uribe, 2016).

The other category is the inductive approach which starts with an observation from which theories are proposed at the end of the research process. An inductive approach has been used in the collection of qualitative interview data. This is also a useful process as it involves search patterns that come from observation. Hence, after that, explanations are developed by focusing on theoretical aspects. Theories and hypotheses are not required to develop in inductive studies, especially at the start of the study. Therefore, the researcher must emphasize theoretical grounds to reach back towards research questions and objectives in this context. Specifically, this approach aims to develop meanings from the collected data, which also aids in identifying patterns and relationships to emerge meanings that are the basis of new theory (Wang, 2017).

At the same time, the inductive approach does not start with the researcher using existing theory to answer the research questions to be explored. It is also based on learning from experience; hence in different studies, it is used accordingly. Therefore, it can be said that patterns, resemblances and regularities are observed when concluding. It begins with a detailed observation of the world; therefore, it focuses on developing theories and concepts. While using such an approach, the researcher always develops empirical generalisations to identify preliminary relationships while proceeding in the research. This does not require the formulation

of a hypothesis at the initial stage of the research as the investigator has no idea about the type and nature of the research findings.

This is why inductive is being used as a phenomenon that describes the exact pattern of the research work. Therefore, it can be said that several patterns are required to be searched as a researcher has to reach valid conclusions. The researcher has used this approach because inductive reasoning is based on learning from experience; varied new dimensions are being researched in the subsequent study. Similarly, patterns, resemblances and regularities in experience are being observed to reach a valid conclusion. The researcher also defined that inductive reasoning starts with detailed observation of the world, which moves from specific ideologies to generalised concepts. Following the inductive approach, the researcher focused on empirical generalisations and preliminary relationships by conducting progressive research (Wang and Yang, 2010).

In the study, hypotheses were not developed at the initial stage of the research, as the researcher was unsure about the type of the study. Thus, while carrying out the entire research work, close observation was focused on building relationships. This was also useful in terms of depicting suitable pictures of the research phenomenon. The inductive is also associated with grounded theory; however, it can be applied with qualitative and quantitative research. The selection of deductive approach has helped the researcher comprehend the dynamics, robustness and resilience focussed on individual behaviour. This is also useful in constructing an alternative dimension for the study (Tungate, 2009).

In the present study, the deductive and inductive approaches have been used. This is because hypotheses related to the topic of branding concepts were generated. This approach is most suitable since the current study examines a particular phenomenon that fits the expected outcomes. Since it involves the generalisation process going from general towards specific, the current study used it appropriately. The general theory related to branding has been taken into consideration. As both deductive and inductive approaches have been utilized in the overall data collection approach it can be described as a mixed method abductive approach for the entire work.

3.5 Research Design

Research design can be described as a general plan that aids the researcher to get a suitable answer for the defined research question. Specifically, it is divided into two types, Exploratory and Conclusive. An exploratory design is useful for ascertaining the specific dimensions of the research study to meet the research outcomes. However, it does not reach a specific conclusion; but still, it aids the researcher to focus on the defined research question. While using such a design, the researcher can also change the direction of the study to a certain extent. Therefore, it can be said that as per the changes implemented, new evidence related to the research process can be grabbed accordingly.

Experimental design is a method of collecting data to determine the impact on the dependent variable. The scholar divides participant into different groups and then gather data.

Cross-sectional design is a method in which scholars measure outcome and expose participants of the study simultaneously. It is a type of observational study. Moreover, it describes characteristics that exist in society.

A longitudinal design is a method of gathering data continuously. The participants are observed over a particular period. It can be either qualitative and quantitative. This variable may change over a period of time.

In the case study design researcher investigates research in a real-life context. Here, case studies are used to do in-depth analysis and gather data and information. This enable scholar to identify relevant data by analysing case studies (Tsai, Joe, and Shen, 2015).

The comparative research design method contains comparing two or more things to discover something new. The variables can be of different or the same groups.

The cross-sectional design is used in the current research, enabling the scholar to gather data from survey and interview. This is because it will be useful in analysing how purchasing intent of customers and its impact on branding. Moreover, what is the outcome of brand awareness due to a change in purchasing intent of customers?

It is also regarded as the initial research, which also forms the basis of more conclusive research. It is highly useful in determining research design, sampling technique and data collection methods. Henceforth, it can be said that the use of such a design aids in collecting more specific and accurate data. The unstructured interview is the most prominent method through which a wide range of data can be collected under primary research. Therefore, the

exploratory research design is useful in searching for new materials integrated into the research work.

At the same time, it is also useful for exploring and defining new research facets that contribute to enhancing the validity and reliability of the research procedure. In the present research study, the researcher has used this research design as it is highly flexible and enables it to adapt to new changes while carrying out the research procedure. Such a design helps the researcher save much time and resources, which can also be applied in other processes. Hence, the design is worth using in the research study (Ulfat, Muzaffar, and Shoaib, 2014).

However, the other research design technique is conclusive, aiming to generate findings that are practically significant to reach towards the specific conclusion. At the same time, it also involves applying quantitative methods under data collection and data analysis. Moreover, it tends to include all the aspects of a deductive study, and the research objectives are achieved through testing research hypotheses. It is further divided into two categories such as descriptive research and causal research. Descriptive is used to specify some of the functions of research phenomenon wherein further outcomes can be acquired. Case study, case series study, cross-sectional study, retrospective study and longitudinal study are some of the categories of descriptive research.

Here, the cross-sectional method is used where an interview will be conducted with 5 managers.

Then, a questionnaire will be used to survey 100 customers. Through this, it will be easy to identify that how purchasing intent impact brand awareness.

The descriptive research design is most suitable as per the current study since the managers' interview would be depicted accurately. Such type of designs is very helpful in in-depth studies regarding a particular topic. With the aid of this research design, the concept of branding for mid-sized companies will be studied effectively. Furthermore, the study is supported by the naturalistic observations obtained from the study. This is a scientific method, which involves the observation and description of the behaviour of the whole subject of the study, without any influence from other external sources (Marlow, 2010).

3.6 Sampling

Sampling is a method that is employed for choosing the participants in the study. There are two types of sampling methods: probability sampling methods and non-probability sampling

methods. Both these methods have their own sets of requirements for their use. Probabilistic sampling is also known as random sampling, in that the samples are selected randomly from a large population. On the other hand, non-probabilistic sampling is a method in which the researcher's preferences are used to select the samples. Convenience sampling method is a non-probability sampling technique in which the subjects are selected due to their accessibility to the researcher. Non-probability sampling focuses on sampling techniques that are based on the judgement of the researcher. A convenience sample is simply one where the units selected for inclusion in the sample are the easiest to access. This is in stark contrast to probability sampling techniques, where the selection of units is made randomly. In the present research study, interviews were carried out among 5 managers for the qualitative interviews and 100 customers for the questionnaire survey. Because of the need to secure the views of experienced respondents and also time constraints, convenience sampling was used. 5 different firms were considered, and from each of the firms, there are 20 customers, and 1 of the manager was selected, so the total is 100 customers and 5 managers. These respondents were selected by convenience sampling because they have a proper understanding of the research topic. Managers understand the strategies applied by the firm and customers who use the services delivered to them. In this context, a proper selection of respondents is made so that they can provide adequate data. Hence the use of knowledgeable respondents is both convenient and more productive in eliciting the necessary information for the study at hand. This will assist in obtaining data that would be authentic and relevant to the aim and objectives of the research. That is helpful enough to provide adequate answers that can enable us to develop the appropriate outcomes. If they do not have proper knowledge, it becomes difficult for the researcher to determine the appropriate outcomes (Tungate, 2019).

Reason for selecting convenience sampling

For the current research, convenience samples have been used because there are non-probability samples, where the elements of selection are based on ease of accessibility. They are the less reliable from a formal statistical point of view but cheaper and more convenient to conduct when selecting from all of the sampling schemes available. In the present thesis, this method of sampling is used for gathering data from managers through interviews. As it is easy and efficient to use, convenience sampling has been used. It helps in obtaining data regarding the study effectively and efficiently.

3.7 Data analysis

This is another important consideration for a researcher to generate viable information from analysing the collected data set. It is a procedural method that uses step-wise measures to analyse the collected information using relevant measures (*Analysis*, 2006). This involves inspection, improvement, transmutation, and modelling of the gathered data to ultimately result in the disclosure of helpful information, which suggests some refined conclusions that support the researcher in making justified decisions related to the overall achievement of the studies' aims and objectives.

The data collected from various resources involves unprocessed information, which the researcher must analyse to complete the entire research work. Before this can be done, the researcher needs to consider the prior stages of social research effectively. This involves some ambitious yet essential steps like defining the research problems, developing and implementing an illustrated plan. This is done by conceptualising the undertaken methods to test them to create a functional plan (Uribe, 2016).

After completing all these procedures, data analysis is used to evaluate the assembled data accumulated from distinct sources, in this case both quantitative and qualitative data. After successfully completing the above phases, to implement data analysis, it is necessary to split it into three leading steps, namely the preparation of data by describing the statistics and testing the same at the end of the analytical process.

The first stage, namely data preparation, is usually done to arrange the collected information in an orderly manner. This leads to the refinement of applicable data to be used for the continuance of the analysis.

The second stage is to create descriptive statistics, which are a set of statistical measures used by the researcher in the last stage, creating inferential statistics. This is the stage where the researcher is almost finished with the analysis of the information, which is now ready for interpretation in order for the researcher to produce relevant conclusions from the data. It is referred to as one of the most efficient methods for the appraisal of the data collected from primary resources to judge the thoughts of the undertaken sample for the study (Uribe, 2016).

Commonly, there are two customary methods for data analysis that involve qualitative and quantitative analysis. Both of these methods use measures to analyse the collected set of data. It, however, depends upon the nature and type of the study. Qualitative research that uses

focused group interviews to gather data requires specific analysis techniques, like thematic analysis. Whereas, to analyse the data concentrated in a quantitative study, quantitative procedures for the critical evaluation of the interpreted statistical data are usually required.

Quantitative methods are typically based on mathematically based calculations in varied formats. It is typically used for specific analysis and interpretation: correlation and regression, mean, mode, and median are some of the measures used. This market research technique revolves around surveys, questionnaires, and polls, and the data collected is evaluated numerically, statistically, mathematically to form better strategies and marketing plans

The qualitative method, which does not involve numbers or mathematical calculations, although frequencies are sometimes used to count the number of different responses, is closely associated with other elements of the study which are less quantifiable and more subjective and interpretivist.

It holds significant importance in the research study because it aids in analysing the collected data and findings through suitable methods, which can also aid the researcher to specify which valid aspects are being considered in the research study. Moreover, in this context, the focus is also on adopting the appropriate method so that suitable findings can be depicted accordingly. Data analysis is the most vital aspect of the study, and the use of quantitative and qualitative methods ensures that all facets of the study are depicted. It also allows the researcher to focus on all such materials to enhance the validity and reliability of research procedures and findings. These can be suitably denoted as meeting all the research dimensions (Sam and Daniel, 2011).

A specific set of techniques was selected to analyse the qualitative data with common themes associated with the data from the sample group members related to the codes of the research procedure. It also includes other non-quantifiable elements such as events, behaviour and activities which are suitably coded in the research procedure. This has also been used because a set of techniques can aid the researcher to identify associated themes, patterns and relationships in the data from the sample group members. These are the most effective methods of qualitative data interpretation.

The researcher has also used a quantitative method that requires statistical methods to analyse the data. The main objective of using quantitative research design is to employ statistical models and theories to reach the specific research aims. Hence, quantitative data is numeric, and it is analysed through applying statistical tools. It is used to test whether a research hypothesis

can be confirmed or not. Manipulation of variables is another significant benefit that can be derived by applying the quantitative analysis technique.

SPSS has been applied to analyse quantitative data analysis section to analyse the data acquired from the respondents. In the research study, only two data types (numeric and text) are defined, representing different aspects of data collection i.e., qualitative and quantitative. The acquisition of a reasonably large convenience sample by the researcher, 5 interviews and 100 questionnaire responses, enables the researcher to provide specific answers to the research questions. Therefore, it can be said that with the help of statistical tools, the researcher can capture the appropriate outcomes of the quantitative part of the study (Sam and Daniel, 2011) and through content analysis the quantitative part of the collected data.

Since the researcher has utilised qualitative and quantitative methods, mixed methods, interviews and surveys, enriched high-quality data was obtained when examined in combination. With the aid of this methodology, the findings obtained provided an effective contribution in the field of branding in the event management industry. Also, the qualitative data can be further used in exploring the quantitative findings of the research.

3.8 Accessibility Issues

The investigator needs to minimise the likely number of limitations experienced in carrying out the research procedure. Therefore, there must be adequate consideration acknowledging research limitations not to affect the entire process. While formulating the research aims and objectives, the researcher broadly classified every aspect to develop clear concepts. The level of focus should be enhanced so that clarity can be developed throughout the research. While collecting data for the present research study, the investigator ensured that all the relevant and accurate materials were accessed, enhancing the value of the research procedure.

Additionally, several websites were not subscribed to and hence unavailable without considerable cost; hence, the researcher could not access these sources. This not only impacted the research procedure but also affected the secondary data collection procedure. Further, lack of adequate financial resources is another constraint prevailing in the study, which also affected the research procedure. The budget also increased because numerous additional activities were involved in the research procedure. Typically, there must be suitable consideration given to implementing the action plan as the involvement of any irrelevant step can affect the overall procedure (Plangger, and Watson, 2015).

Focus is also required to be laid on the discussions concerning things that should be included so that the validity and reliability of the research procedure could be enhanced. This is also essential in terms of meeting the research outcomes and defined objectives. While accessing diverse sources of data, the researcher has focused on valid and reliable materials to enhance the accuracy of the thesis. Moreover, it can be said that of the several dimensions that were accessed; a few had irrelevant data; therefore, it had changed the research dimension.

Several websites gave confusing results to the investigator; hence some of the research aspects are not clear. In order to make the study more clear and concise, the researcher scheduled that all the activities were arranged in the same way. However, even after managing all such aspects, the researcher experienced various constraints. Therefore, it is clear that research accessibility affected the overall study dimensions and changed the research procedure's flow. Henceforth, it can be contended that while accessing different sources, the researcher needed to ensure that all research facets are being included appropriately. This not only enhances the validity of the study but also encourages research procedure.

3.9 Ethical consideration

When developing the research study, it is crucial to emphasise ethical aspects that enhance the value and authenticity of the research procedure. Ethics hold more significance in the research procedure because the value of the study can be enhanced. Moreover, adequate consideration of ethical values enhances research validity and helps in discouraging any associated issues in the research procedure. Previously, the term ethics was related to the consideration of valid and reliable aspects only; however, this phenomenon has been changed a lot, and varied new dimensions are being included in ethical considerations. Under ethical aspects, the researcher ensured to collect data only from relevant and germane sources, which has also contributed to encouraging the value of the research study. In this facet, it can be contended that the researcher obtained their consent before involving participants in the research procedure (Plangger, and Watson, 2015).

It is essential to acquire appropriate consent from the participants as consent from the participants is crucial because they possess the right to participate or not in the research procedure. At the same time, the researcher has also given the right of withdrawal to the participants under which they can withdraw from the research process anytime they wish. The researcher considered all the rights and obligations of the participants as this helped the

researcher reduce all research issues and challenges. Furthermore, consideration has also been given towards the confidentiality and secrecy management wherein the researcher did not disclose any aspect of the research without obtaining the consent of the participants. Thus, voluntary participation of the researcher in the study is crucial and according to that researcher focused on these dimensions.

Data related to the research study has been protected in the database of the company, and accessibility authority is only given to those people who were concerned with the research procedure. This is essential for safeguarding research prospects in an accurate and relevant manner. Moreover, it is also crucial for the researcher to disclose only specific information to the concerned parties. In the same way, the identity and responses of the participants should not be disclosed without their consent, as this would be unethical. Participants have the authority to ask for secrecy management; however, the investigator had already focused on confidentiality reports. The aim and objectives of the study have not been exaggerated, and focus has been laid on only specific research materials. In the same way, the investigator emphasised using only relevant and authentic sources that contained only quality material (Ulfat, Muzaffar, and Shoaib, 2014).

Moreover, Ethical consideration has been taken from the UWS before carrying out this research. It will help ensure that study is done fairly and ethically with university professors approval.

Therefore, it is evident that all the defined research terminologies were required to consider in the thesis to support the reliability rate of the study. While collecting responses from the questionnaire, the investigator ensured the use of only specific modes of communication to reduce all sorts of miscommunication in the research procedure. In addition to the same, offensive, discriminatory and unacceptable language was avoided as that deeply affects the research procedure. While asking questions, the researcher ensured that appropriate language was being used in all domains to make the research procedure clearer and more concise. Transparency management is also crucial in the present study; therefore, the researcher took care of this in the present thesis. All the aspects related to research work are being communicated to the concerned people in accurate terms. Hence, honesty, integrity and accuracy were required to be maintained in all domains (Sam and Daniel, 2011).

Apparently, every research work requires the researcher to use different sources and previous studies. However, the investigator must acknowledge the work done by others so that their contribution can be valued; only authentic and reliable sources should be used while specifying authors' work in the reference section. This is also crucial in terms of maintaining the highest level of objectivity in discussing research matters. Therefore, concluding it can be said that the chief emphasis has been given towards the primary data collection process. Besides, the investigator conducted a thorough analysis of every aspect to include only accurate things. In-depth analysis was also carried out to maintain the value of every aspect of the research.

3.10 Conclusion

Thus, coming up to the end of the methodology section, it can be said that all the feasible and reliable methods were used in the research work to meet the determined aims and objectives. In the research study, SPSS has been used to analyse the collected data quantitatively. The method was used so that the researcher could ensure numerical accuracy in the calculations, and it also aids in managing the section of data analysis. Charts and diagrams have been used to depict clients' responses, making the study more presentable. Thematic content analysis was used for the qualitative interview data. Moreover, in conclusion, it can be said that two years were correct for the study as all the activities were carried out within the stipulated period. Henceforth, it is clear that all the methods used in the thesis proved useful in deriving suitable outcomes. It ensured that the proper information was gathered to enable the research to carry out a proper analysis and form an in-depth understanding of the research topic. Two types of methods for data collection were identified; both had their own set of benefits and disadvantages. Further, when selecting the appropriate method is done for data collected, it is also important that appropriate analysis is made. Under all these aspects, suitable methods must be implemented to ensure that viewers can understand the information gathered effectively.

Validity and reliability

It means the extent to which the researcher has used the right elements is conducting research and interpreting data. It is necessary to use the right tools so that outcomes will not get affected. Research validity is divided into two, i.e., internal and external. Internal refers to how findings are related to reality, whereas external results will be simulated outside the environment. Here, research consideration has been kept by the researcher. This is an important part of the study. It has helped in looking for the extent to which research could be carried out most

effectively and efficiently. Also, the researcher has maintained the validity of findings by ensuring that data has been collected from authentic sources. The data analysis tools were tested and then used. It was useful in validating the data and obtaining outcomes.

Limitations

The present study is limited to London, which is where the researcher has had management experience in event management. London was chosen because it is also a major event management centre in the UK. The researcher was also able to gain access to respondents which included management for interviews and through them customers for the questionnaire survey used. There is no certainty that the findings are applicable to other areas of the UK such as Manchester or Leeds. However, there is no reason to believe the findings are biased in any way and that they may have general applicability outside of the capital. In fact, is it probably true to say that the findings discussed in this work are generally applicable to event management situations wherever they are located, certainly within the UK? The researcher has used a sample not a census, but the sample has been carefully selected with the intention of making a representative selection of customers and management. These are customers who contact the various ticket offices used in the sample and the management of the ticket office companies selected. Hence, while identifying certain limitations, the researcher considers the research findings of this study to be generally commercially valuable and possibly of practical help to managers working in the event management sector. The researcher's overall opinion, having conducted this research study, is that the work has made a valuable and practical contribution to the subject in this area.

3.11 Summary

In the research methodology chapter, the researcher has provided a brief introduction to the topic. The researcher has discussed the data collection methods, research philosophy, approach, and design. The method used for sampling has been explained, and data analysis has been exemplified in this chapter. The researcher has discussed the ethical issues and accessibility issues in a detailed and explicit manner. More specifically, the researcher has used both primary and secondary data to gather the appropriate information. The use of interviews and questionnaires was done for primary information, and secondary books, journals, online sources, etc., were used. Further, the investigator has used thematic analysis and SPSS for identifying the most appropriate outcomes from this research.

CHAPTER 4: DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

This is an important part of the dissertation as it enables the proper analysis of the information gathered from respondents. According to the research, there are different types of identified issues, from which it can be stated that brand plays a vital role in increasing the organisation's sales and profitability. The brand is developed when a firm can satisfy all the needs and requirement of customers. Furthermore, the type of marketing conducted by the organisation also plays an important role as it enables individuals to know more about the product. Thus, the brand image is developed. Different people have a diverse set of perceptions. In this context, managers and customers are taken into consideration. Managers are the ones who have a proper understanding of the type of strategies that the firm uses to raise the brand image. On the other hand, customers are enabled to know the perceptions that the organisation carries out. More specifically, 20 customers were selected from 5 companies making 100 in total and 1 manager selected from Each 5 companies. Both managers and customers were helpful enough to come up with an appropriate outcome for the research.

4.2 Interview carried out by the managers of 5 mid-sized event companies

Theme 1. There exists a direct relationship between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention.

At the time of asking this question, event managers said that there exists a direct relationship between the brand of the company and the customer purchase decision. They also added that customers usually get services only from those familiar to them and find them more profitable and valuable. In this context, the manager Elizabeth said that “yes, the customer usually prefer to go for brands while they have to organise events”. In addition, the manager of another company articulated that “most of the customers are brand conscious and as a result, they prefer to get services from those entities only whom they get services frequently”. In respect to this, another manager said that “brand helps the customers to get the satisfaction that they are getting suitable and quality products only. With the help of branded products, a business can give assurance to the customers regarding the delivered services”. Another manager said that “brand helps them maintain their existing customer base. It is also useful for getting more recognition from other entities”. Lastly, the manager of TICKET DESK said that “with the brand identity, they can attract many customers towards their services”.

Theme 2. There is a direct link between the brand and the sales strategy of the business.

This aspect of the thesis has given information about the brand and the sales strategy of the business entity. Therefore, the manager of Ticket Desk, Elizabeth said that “brand is termed as a major strategy through which sales degree can be enhanced”. Further, in this context, the manager also articulated that “because of branding strategy, the organisation can enhance the customer base and provide other necessary benefits”. The manager of another company said, “when sales strategies are applied, employees can develop strong relationships with customers”. At the same time, they also contended that brand aids the business entities to improve the overall quality of the services; hence this directly contributes to encouraging success and growth dimensions. Besides this, the manager of a company said that “focusing on brand aspects helps them to expand the services and operations in different areas and at the same time it also assists in enhancing the scope of services”. Moreover, the manager of another company said that “focus on brand helps them to encourage customers towards more purchase and it is also useful in amending the ratio of customer loyalty”. Lastly, managers said that through a branding policy, they amend the efficiency of service delivery procedure and maximise their market share.

Theme 3. Quality services drive customers towards repetitive purchase.

This was one of the apparent questions that made it clear that quality services drive customers towards a repeat purchase, leading them to promote the services to other end users. In this respect, the manager of Ticket Desk, Elizabeth said that “quality services drive customers towards repetitive purchase. It is the factor that aids in increasing the productivity of the organisation”. On the other hand, the manager of LSBO said that focus on promotional events aids the customers to know about the service provision. As a result, they can match their requirements with the company’s services”. In this context, the manager also said that “it is important to make sure that there is proper quality of services delivered. When the service quality is high, then there are repetitive purchases”. At the same time, it also aids in developing the ratio of profitability and sales. The manager of LIFESTYLE TICKETS said that “status is one of the major factors that lead customers to focus more on repeat purchase. Most of the customers prefer to get services from the brand because they are highly concerned about their status quo”. In this respect, another manager said that “different people have the diverse type of preference some may be focused on quality and some may prefer to price”.

Theme 4. The brand makes a huge contribution in maximising the scope of targeted customers.

When asked this question, the manager of Ticket Desk, Elizabeth said that “branding strategies aids them to maximize the scope of targeting many people like nowadays, people have become much conscious about brands”. In the same context, he also added that “because of huge focus on brand, customers feel more valued in terms of services”. Other than this, the manager also said that “many customers can only be targeted if the business entity is highly concerned about end users' requirements”. A manager in this realm said that the “branding strategy of the company possess the power to grab the attention of different customers and at the same time, it also aids in maximising the scope of benefits”. The manager also said that “brand enables to develop positive perception within customers' minds and make them purchase the products and services”. Moreover, in the same area, a manager added that potential customers always assist the business entity in enhancing the profitability ratio by remaining loyal with the service provider”. Lastly, a manager contended that “with the help of the brand, the firm can develop a unique place within the mind of customers”.

Theme 5. Brands can be best promoted through social media.

Social media has become one of the major tools through which brands, products and services can be promoted to a higher extent. Therefore, in this domain, a manager said that “social media is a powerful tool for organisation that aid in promoting the products and services of the organisation efficiently and effectively”. Another manager said that “social media is not an appropriate tool through which business products can be promoted. In the same context, although they added that “social media involves various aspects which are not relevant and which cannot be applied in all business dimensions”. Apart from this, a manager said that “they use social media on greater extent because a large pool of customers is available on the same source”. They also added that “through social media, awareness can be generated among customers regarding the availability of different products and services”. Besides this, a manager said that “social media aids in promoting the brand value through focusing on larger market segment”. Lastly, a manager contradicted this by stating that “with the help of social media, business services can promote the amenities on higher extent; however at the same time, it can also lead to customer switching to other brands”.

Theme 6. Advertising is not the only way through which brand promotion can be facilitated.

With the help of advertising, business services and brand aspects can be promoted to a higher extent. It is also useful in enhancing the customer base and satisfaction aspects. Advertising is referred to play a considerate role in the branding strategy where it is also specified to be a means that directs the application of the branding strategy. Following this, almost all the respondents have favoured this method to promote a company's brand name. As per one of the manager, “advertisement is essential but not the only way to promote the organisation. There are methods such as the reputation of the brand, customer’s feedback, etc. However, very few participants have contradicted this measure of advertising to brand the company's goods and services and rather proposed some other ways of promoting the brand. Further, another manager stated that “there are other sources that can also be used for brand promotion”. This involves some more effortless ways in which one can refer to promote their brand". One such example creates a brand logo rather than spending it on the process of advertising. It follows those who are in approval of taking fewer efforts to promote the brand than those who agree with the branding strategy.

According to those who are largely in favour of it, branding leads to the fulfilment of organisational goals and objectives to a great extent. The organisation must make a substantial investment of funds as per the requirement of the adopted strategy. This will enhance the profitability status of the overall firm and automatically lead to the attainment of disbursed funds. Therefore, it is important to invest funds in branding where advertising is considered one of the most applicable methods. Apart from this, some have also supported yet another strategy of promoting the brand by developing a close relationship with the clients and users. Thus on referring to the acquired information from the secondary resources, it can be said that advertisement is one of the most suitable methods for the promotion of one's brand. Despite being quite an expensive affair, it could benefit the firm in several ways.

Theme 7. Adopting networking using different social media sites is one of the most suitable branding strategies for an event management firm.

Event management is the most active business in today's era, leading to attaining a vital success rate. This also leads to an enhanced acquisition of profit at times. However, many business people think it to be a seasonal business and thus do not consider directionally putting

their efforts. According to one of the managers, “social media are a highly effective and very important source in this modern world to get in connection with customers”. This leads to a mediocre business occurrence, with no effective marketing attempted to satisfy the customers who are every day coming up with different types of demands. Therefore, to fulfil their distinct needs and requirements, the companies need to undertake certain inventive ways to develop a different set of ideas and present them to the customers before they even think about it. Some managers think that social media is the only effective way to develop the brand.

This will, in turn, lead to enhancing the base of their customers and result in the promotion of their brand. It is accepted to be a strategic approach for promoting the brand. Almost all participant bodies represented by the managers of 5 mid-sized businesses operating in event management have supported social media networking sites. They agreed that they practice such approaches and which result in attracting a large set of users. Also, it helps them to enlarge their business by getting into several other areas of event management. The manager of one of the firms further elaborated it with some specific reasons where networking results in producing numerous ideas that assist managers in implementing various innovative measures to fulfil their tasks.

Theme 8. Branding has a vital contribution in marketing goods and services.

On considering the responses of most of the study participants representing the managers of mid-sized event management companies, it can be said that most of them are in agreement with the contribution made by branding in marketing the offered products and services. According to the response given by one of the managers, “it can be stated that there are firms that deliver their customers with a similar set of products and services. In order to be different from others, branding is a helpful aspect”. It is also in accordance with their own acquired experiences that made them understand the link between branding and marketing. However, very few of the respondents have denied this fact and have specified the branding tactic to be more linked with content marketing. Therefore, considering the information obtained from the literature review representing the secondary data set, one can assure a direct link between branding and content marketing. The normal marketing strategy is less equivalent to that of the accepted strategy of branding. Further, another manager stated that “branding enables to develop the unique identity of the goods and the firm”.

Branding and marketing are different from one another, where branding is stated to be more strategic. However, marketing, by comparison, requires some more tactical approach. Also, marketing is known to activate more buyers than the results that one can acquire from branding that generates loyal consumers. Therefore, by comparing the information collected from both primary and secondary sources, one can now clearly distinguish between the functions of marketing and branding, where branding results in the marketing of commodities but in a different way. This query distinguished two different types of marketing: branding is more akin to content marketing that enables the managers to interact by publishing in various social media sites and company websites, etc.

Theme 9.Pricing and Quality are the factors that best describe the purchase intention of buyers.

This is about considering the most potent factors that best influence the buying intent of individuals who are proposing to choose from the services of event management companies. Based on the gained experiences of the managers, where a majority of the respondents supported that the quality of the services is the influential factor that directly impacts the purchase behaviour of a large number of consumers. As per the manager's response, "quality and pricing are important factors to make customers make purchase decisions". In this accord, it becomes important for them to consider providing good quality services, with a major role in specifying it in their branding process. This increases the interest of many customers where they often do not consider the cost of the proposed services. Another manager stated that "pricing and quality are not just the only factors".

However, another set of respondents has come up with a different set of experiences. They have mostly dealt with such types of customers who are more concerned about pricing the offered commodities and even forget to consider their quality. Whereas, a certain number of managers have also specified that both the quality and price of offered services matter for many consumers. Most of them demand an affordable service with appreciable quality. The information gathered from the secondary resources has together depicted a similar consideration by the third set of managers who have specified a correspondent outlook towards provisioning a good quality service within an affordable pricing structure. This strategy is much more progressive in attracting numerous consumers than other activities, as mentioned earlier plans.

Theme 10. Branding is directly related to the purchase intention of consumers referring to buy a commodity.

Branding is known to directly correlate with the buying intention of users, where it defines the purchasing alternatives for the buyers. However, considering the study participants' responses, it has been found that this requires a veracious branding strategy. One manager said that the “mind of customers could develop positive perception for the services and products delivered by the business”. In terms of which, the promises made to the client must be fulfilled with no fallacious marketing for the promotion of proposed goods and services. Branding in marketing is a considerate approach that necessitates the managers to design it in a manner that leads to the accomplishment of their real goals and objectives of sales. From the facts and findings acquired from the examination of secondary resources, it has been found that branding, done in the form of content marketing, necessitates the managers to mention the terms that will be satisfying in fulfilling the real needs and demands of the customers.

Further, the manager stated, “branding is not directly related to purchasing intention of customers”. Also, their written terms must not contradict selling the products that might also lead to deter the overall image of the enterprise to a great extent and could lead to negative consequences. Hence, it is proven that branding directly leads to an impact upon the purchase intention of the buyers.

Theme 11. Volatility is amongst the best-suited role of branding in an event management company as per most participants' experience.

A large set of study respondents have favoured the presence of volatility in their accepted strategy of branding. Therefore, it is in accordance with them where volatility is termed to be one of the best-suited roles of branding in an event management firm. One manager stated that “Yes, volatility is among the best-suited roles of branding”. It is referred to as the cause of acceptance by the customers substantially increased by a proper application of branding strategy. However, many of the respondents have denied that branding could directly lead to benefit the organisation to such an extent. Following them, branding cannot be applied without any supportive element and thus requires another channel.

In context to which, the respondents linked the tactic of branding with that of the marketing practices where they are interrelated to one another. Therefore, it refers to the information obtained from secondary resources that one can discern the two distinct ideas given

by the participant respondents of the study. On which basis, both applications have a substantial role in the business, and whether applied directly or indirectly, they lead to give definite results to the organisation. On considering this fact, neither of the concepts is proven to be erroneous in either way. Whereas, on comparing the primary results with that of the information generated from the secondary collection of data, one can easily relate to the efficacy of branding where its volatility is apparent in attracting the interest of an enormous number of customers.

Theme 12: Employees are important in raising brand loyalty

In accordance with the response given by managers, it can be evaluated that the majority of them think that brand loyalty towards the firm increases when there are skilled and knowledgeable workers. As per the response of a manager, “employees have direct interaction with customers. They can understand the issues or the problems faced by each of the customers and so they are helpful to raise the brand loyalty”. Employees are the face of the organisation as they present the products and services that the firm delivers. It is important to make sure that they understand the types of roles and responsibilities they play. As per one of the managers of Encore Tickets, it is identified that customers have different type of doubts, and it is the responsibility of employees to make them clarify. When workers themselves have doubts, it creates issues to make sure that all the doubts that service users have been solved”. Another manager stated that “when employees cannot effectively perform their roles, it affects customers' perception. So brand gets affected with employee's performance”. Customers then develop negative perceptions about products that the organisation delivers. Another manager stated that “employees are valuable assets by which competitive advantage can be achieved. The management needs to identify the areas in which improvement need to be provided for employees”. From the findings made, workers should be delivered with training and development as it helps with their in-depth understanding of the services and products delivered by the firm. In addition to this, the issues faced by service users will also be determined, doubts can be cleared, and brand loyalty can be raised. One of the managers of Elizabeth does not think that employees are important to increase brand loyalty.

Further, another manager stated that “employees should be trained to understand customers' requirement as the brand gets affected through employees”. Brand loyalty is raised when the firm focuses on the quality of services and the implemented marketing strategies. In addition to

this, strategies are helpful that enable to attract customer's attention and ways such that they may not shift to services delivered by other companies.

Theme 13: Price plays a vital role in developing brand loyalty of the organisation

Different people have diverse perceptions, and individuals tend to use the services delivered to them at a low cost. However, some people think that the quality of a product increases when the price is high. According to one of the responses given by a manager, "it is identified that there are a certain set of expectations that are carried out. As per managers response, "when prices are low, then customers tend to make use of the services and products that are delivered by the business". In this context, it includes when the price of the product increases, then customers develop the perception that the quality of the product is high. However, one manager states that "price does not have much of impact on raising brand loyalty, but it depends upon the satisfaction level that is attained by customers when product or service is used. Many comparisons are made by the service user in which price is considered one of the factors. Many companies deliver customers with a similar set of products and services". Another manager stated that "price of the product should be kept comparatively low when compared with competitors. When any of the firms keep the price of the product or service is low, customers who are not focused on quality will prefer to purchase it. On the other hand, when individuals who tend to purchase the product that is of high quality, then they will prefer to buy those products or services which are of high rate".

From the response given by a manager of LIFESTYLE TICKETS, it was stated that "price is an important factor that needs to be considered by the organisation. Comparison to be made among the price that competitors deliver and low price must be selected. However, the quality of the product or service must not be affected. This is an effective way to increase brand loyalty by making price changes".

Theme 14: Engagement of customers is important in raising brand loyalty.

There are different types of strategies applied by an organisation to attract more and more customers. When individuals develop interest, they can make their perception positive over the products and services that the organisation delivers. As per the response, "when employees are engaged, then it becomes favourable enough to develop a strong relationship with customers". All the managers of different firms stated that the engagement of customers is important for

raising brand loyalty. As per the response given by one of the managers, “it is identified that effective way to engage customers is with the help of providing them with discounted offers. Similarly, there are different type of strategies that organisations develop. When there is high engagement among customers, they tend to develop positive perception within this mind”. One of the managers stated, “there are special offers provided by the firm, in which free gifts or additional services are delivered. This is helpful enough to develop curiosity among customers, and they tend to make use of the offers. This way people get attracted, and there is engagement among them”. Another manager stated that “engaging employees help to make them understand about the quality of services and products that are delivered”. Further, from the analysis made, it can also be evaluated that the ultimate aim of any firm is to gain maximum profit. This is only possible when they can understand the needs and requirement of customers, with the help of which sales can be raised, and brand loyalty can be developed. One manager states that “when customers are engaged, then it becomes helpful in determining the areas due to which brand loyalty is getting reduced”. From the findings, proper analysis can be made, and necessary steps can be considered with the help of which issue can be solved.

Theme 15: Role of quality of service in purchase intention of customer

From the discussion with the managers of companies, it was noticed that most of them indicated that all sorts of service provided by the need to be in a proper manner and of quality. The quality of service is playing in the decision of purchase intention of the customer is very much important. It could be noted that the service must be of very good quality as this will have the power to change customers' intention in the way of regulating consistent visits to the store. One manager also indicated that “customers majorly focus on the price of products and not be concentrating mainly on quality of products or service”. However, still, it was concluded that managers agreed to point to the importance of the role of service quality within the purchase intention of their customers.

Theme 16: Company is taking feedback from client or customers coming to attend events

By Taking or conducting feedback from customers and clients, the company could include all sorts of changes that customers request. Managers of event management companies concluded that their company takes feedback from customers, which helps them improve their functioning and operations. This feedback is taken from almost all customers or clients who are attending events held by the company. One of the managers noted that “feedback is taken from

customers, but it is not updating the changes within their management or operation work”. One of the managers added that “his company is neither taking feedback from customer nor from clients so that they could do required changes. The company must be taking feedback from clients and customers so that their demands and needs are identified, and then modification is done accordingly”.

Theme 17: Factors that are considered as important for buyers except for quality and price

Price and quality of products are among the most important factors that all customers consider when buying any product or services, such as packaging, brand, familiarity, etc. So one of the managers included that “their customers would be considering brand image most important before they buy products or services. As brand image will surely represent both qualities of product but at higher prices, the company must also ensure that its brand image is maintained within the market. Suppose the customer is dependent upon the trustworthiness of the products and service which they are buying. In that case, it will be possible that they are retained for a longer duration of time”. Another manager stated that “packaging is that one factor that is most important for customers is then considered it while making the purchase. Customers would be attracted to those products or services that are coming in reusable packaging. However, while for a company like that of event management, packaging will not be there, their customers would not be dependent upon any packaging. While it was also included that customers would also be considering brand or product and service familiarity. This means that all customers will be attracted towards those products that are more familiar to them as they have a strong resemblance to their own self”.

Theme 18: Importance of brand awareness for a company

Brand awareness will be very important for a company, including an event management one, as this means that all customers know what the firm is selling to them. As this will be to the extent to which customers can recall or recognise a brand by only seeing its logo, it becomes very important for the company to have good branding. This will surely help to promote their brands and products as well. So one of the managers included that “brand awareness is very important for sustaining within the market. Some customers are choosing companies based on brands and products as well. Social media like Facebook and Instagram have many users who are adding them up more during these times. So brand awareness is very much essential as will be based on products and service of event management companies”.

Theme 19: Effectiveness of sales strategy of the company is attracting a sufficient number of customers from the market

Then the managers were asked whether their companies' sales strategies are effective or not in attracting more people or customers towards their companies. So most of the managers concluded that their sales strategies which used by the company are very much effective. Sales strategies are prepared by the sales and purchase department of a company, which helps them regulate and look forward to its marketing plan. Good sales strategies will help the company attract more customers as customers will only get to know the company after watching their promotional advertisement.

Theme 20: Do you think that brand perception will influence the purchase decision of event industry customers?

The following answers resulted from this question. Brand perception will influence the purchasing decisions of event industry customers. Brand perception is nothing to do with influencing the purchase decision of the invent industry customers. Yes, the Brand perception will be influencing purchase decision which customer is taking of event industry. Yes, the Brand perception will be influencing purchase decision which customer is taking of event industry. Brand perception will be resulting from customer experience with the purchase of the product.

4.3 Questionnaire collected from customers

Theme 1: Always go to the branded organisation

<i>Do you always go to the branded organisation?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Yes always	18
Never	21
Only when quality is important	34
Rarely	27

Description: Following the findings, it is identified that customers consider certain sets of consideration when purchases are made for any type of services. From the questionnaire gathered from service users, it can be stated that there are 18 of the customers who always tend to make purchases for branded products. When individuals purchase branded products, they require to have a proper understanding of the services delivered by each of the organisations. Further, 21 of the service users among 100 do not prefer to make purchases of branded products or services. Individuals who use branded products or services tend to buy them when they get high quality. When the firm's quality is not high, and people prefer to make purchases of quality products, then there are conditions in which the customer will shift to other companies that deliver high-quality services. The price of the services or product cannot be included as the services that contain high brand value is of high price.

Further, there are 27 of the service users who have rarely used branded products. In addition to this, out of 100, 34 customers prefer to make purchases from a branded organisation when quality is important. Further, it can also be stated that organisations need to focus on the quality

of products and services as this enables them to raise the brand quality and loyalty towards services.

Theme 2: Brand impact on purchasing power

<i>How brand impact your purchasing power?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Very effective	38
Effective	32
Average	22
Not effective	8

Description: Different people have diverse perceptions of the conditions that are faced or given. From the analysis made with the help of the questionnaire, it can be stated that 38 customers think that purchasing power gets affected due to brand. From this, it can be determined that organisations need to make a proper evaluation. The areas in which they lack should be determined, as this will enable reviewing the areas in which improvement needs to be made. Further, organisations' perceptions need to be identified by organisations. When they are not favourable, appropriate steps can be taken to improve the quality of products and services delivered.

Further, it is identified that 32 of the customers think that brand has an effective impact on purchasing power. However, 8 individuals think that brand does not affect much. These can be determined to be individuals who do not prefer to make purchases from the products or services with high brand value. In addition to this, 22 out of 100 think that brand has a high impact on purchasing power.

Overall, it can be stated that the majority of individuals think that brand has a high impact on purchasing power. This shows that organisations need to take appropriate steps so that they will be able to develop positive perceptions within customers' minds.

Theme 3: Competitive Pricing is essential to develop a good brand image

<i>Which of the following, according to you, essential to develop a good brand image?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Quality	43
Communication strategies	26
Free trials and discount offers	17
Competitive Pricing	14

Description: As per the questionnaire conducted from 100 customers of 5 different companies, it can be stated that there are different types of important aspects, and this needs to be considered. In this question, four different options are given in which brand image is considered. From the customers' perceptions, it can be stated that there are 14 of them who think that price is important and the organisation should consider this. Some people focus on price. When the price is low, then the rate of purchases made will be high. 26 customers think that communication strategies are important, and this needs to be considered. When the rate of communication is high, then customers develop positive perceptions about the brand.

With proper communication, trust and confidence are developed, and the type of issues that customers face are also identified. This way, management can develop positive perceptions within the minds of customers 17 of the customers selected discount offers and free trials that enable to development of a brand image. Some people tend to make use of services only when they get free trials. This generally happens when many organisations deliver customers with a similar set of products and services. If people do not get an option or there is no other substitute, they do not prefer to use the services that the firm delivers. From the overall findings, it can be stated that individuals prefer to make purchases for the brand products and services that are delivered to them with high quality.

Theme 4: Trust toward the brands

<i>Do you trust your branded organisation?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Yes	18
No	21
Somewhat	34
Don't Know	27

Description: The survey was conducted to determine the level of trust of customers towards the brands and the organisation. As per the questionnaire, 18 out of 100 customers trust their brand and the organisation. Their trust depends on the quality and services provided by the organisation. Moreover, brands positively impact customers, as they feel good while choosing the product of a branded organisation. 34 customers have somewhat or very little trust in brands. They are those customers who do not bother about the quality of services. They want to complete their goal of purchasing the branded products. 21 people do not trust the company brand. Customer satisfaction also plays an important role. Suppose the organisation can satisfy its customers. In that case, the trust level will increase, and if they provide worthless services by charging a higher price, their trust and loyalty will decrease eventually. 27 customers do not know whether they trust the brands or not. From the analysis, it can be clear that most people somewhat trust the brands and the organisation. This is due to the lack of product quality or high pricing strategy applied by the organisation. In addition, these customers do not focus on quantity or marketing; they just want to get their task complete by choosing those products and services. It can also be concluded that it is the responsibility of the branded organisation to improve the packages of the products in a way that can be cost-effective and satisfy the customer by providing generic quality products and services.

Theme 5: Rating of the branded organisation

<i>On a scale of 1 to 5 star, how you will rate branded organisation?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
1 star	15
2 star	10
3 star	25
4 star	35
5 star	15

Description: Rating of the brands by customers shows the intensity and level of the organisation. Customer prefers to choose those brands whose ratings are always high and efficient. The survey was conducted from 100 customers in which they have to rate the brands on a scale of one to five. It can be analysed from the questionnaire that 15 customers rated 1 star to the brands and their organisation. One star shows that there are various areas in which the organisation has to focus on improving the quality, quantity and price of the products and services. It can be identified that 10 customers gave a 2-star rating to the branded organisation. The two-star rating denotes that the organisation has to improve the quality up to the mark, which meets the customer's requirement in accordance with its price structures. 25 customers

gave a 3-star rating to the organisation. It seems like customer reactions were neutral, and the organisation needs to improve its overall strategy to improve the quality of the branded products and services. It can be seen that 35 customers rated 4 stars to the branded organisation. This represents that customers like the products and services of the organisation, but there is little more requirement of improvement in the efficiency and effectiveness of the products. It can be identified that only 15 customers gave a 5-star rating to brands and organisation. 5 star is the highest level an organisation aims to achieve. It means that the organisation can fulfil all the desires and needs of the customers and are fully satisfied with the brands they choose. From the analysis, a maximum number of customers gave 4 stars to the organisation. It seems like these organisations need improvement in the quality and quantity of their products and services.

Theme 6: Benefits of choosing branded products

<i>How do you benefit from choosing branded products?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Very Much	38
Average	32
Not much	22

Do not Know	8
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Description: Choosing branded products sometimes benefits the customers or sometimes leads to losing their money, time and efforts in the survey, where 100 customers were chosen

who purchased branded products from different organisations and were asked about their benefits after purchasing the branded products. As per the analysed questionnaire, 38 customers were very much benefited by the branded organisations. These benefits include customer satisfaction, high-quality products, more quantity, efficient build quality, according to the taste and preference of the customer, efficient after-sales service. If the brands and the organisation maintain these qualities, they can provide efficient benefits and support to the customers. It can be identified that 32 customers are benefited, but not that much. Their reactions were neutral in terms of benefits and advantages. The organisation needs to raise the qualities and quantity of the branded products according to their price to benefit from them. From the analysis, it can be identified that 22 customers are not much benefited after purchasing the branded products of the specific organisation. It means that the organisation fails to fulfil the customers' requirement and charges highly for services that are not necessary. This can lead to a major drawback for the organisation, as they will lose their precious customers. The organisation has to consider the overall improvement of quality, quantity and price of the products. In addition, they have to focus on the requirement of customers first, rather than informing them about their worthless products and services. It can be seen that 8 customers do not know whether they get any benefits or not. This can also lead to a negative impact on the image of the organisation. If the customers are unable to judge, then the organisation fails to provide efficient and effective products to customers. From the analysis, it can be concluded that the majority of customers are benefited from purchasing the branded products and services provided by the organisation.

Theme 7: Key Factors Considered while choosing branded products

<i>What key factors do you consider before going for any brands?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Quality	43
Quantity	26
Price	17
Brand Image	14

Description: When a customer purchases a branded product instead of local products, then various factors influence them to purchase those branded products. These factors vary from the quality of products to the organisation brand image and marketing strategy. In a survey, 100 customers were asked what factors influence them to purchase branded products. As per the questionnaire, 43 customers say that the quality of branded products influences them to purchase them. It seems that quality plays an important role in influencing the purchase of the customers. Branded products are famous for their quality. In an event management industry, the organisation needs to maintain their quality to retain and attract customers. From the analysis, it can be identified that the quantity of the products influences 26 customers. Quantity is an important element of an organisation. It determines how many benefits an organisation can provide at a specific cost. An organisation needs to provide as many benefits as possible so that the customers' requirements can get fulfilled and generate profits. It can be identified from the analysis of the questionnaire that 17 customers voted for price factors. Price is an essential

factor, and some customers prefer price over quality. These segments of customers include middle class and lower class people who want branded products and consider the price factor. The organisation which produces branded products and services needs to keep in mind these segments of the customers and specific goods should be produced so that these customers' requirements are also fulfilled. From the analysis, it can be clear that 14 people consider the brand image as the factor influencing their purchase. In conclusion, it can be identified that the majority of the customers consider quality as an important factor when considering their purchase of branded products and services.

Theme 8: Brands different from their competitors

<i>How is the brand different from its competitors?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Very Different	38
Somewhat Different	32
Not Different	22
Don't Know	8

Description: Brand and product differentiation are essential to survive in competitive markets. A survey where 100 customers were asked about how the brand they purchase is different from its competitors: it was found that 38 customers say that the brand they purchase

was different from other branded products of different organisation. Product differentiation is based on the quantity, quality, marketing, and price or based on brand image. Usually, customers always require something different from the organisation. Further, it can be identified that 32 customers found only a subtle difference between the brands they purchase and the available brands in the market. This is due to the quantity factor. As some organisations provide the same quantity at the same price, they change, modify or alter the quality or marketing strategy. It can be identified that 22 customers do not find any difference between the brands they purchase and the available brands in the market. This is the fault of the organisations, as they do not focus on product differentiation and are only focused on profit generation. The organisation has to focus on the quantity, quality and price of the products to find any difference between them and the competitors.

Further, it can be analysed from the questionnaire that 8 customers do not know whether their brands are different. It seems likely that they did not know about the substitutes or do not want to compare their products with any other organisation. From the analysis, most customers found a difference between the products they bought and the products that are available with the competitors.

Theme 9: Sources of marketing of brands.

<i>How did you first hear about the products?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
TV	20
Newspapers	25
Internet	35
From a friend/relative	20

Description: In a survey, 100 customers were asked what source they heard about the brands or how to source organisations prefer marketing their products and services. In accordance with the questionnaire, 20 customers say that they heard about the importance of the branded products via television advertisements. These advertisements were frequently shown on TV on some specific channels from which the organisation can attract customers. These are very effective but costly methods. Further, it can be identified that 25 customers know about the particular brand and product through newspapers. They received some pamphlets attached in the newspaper describing the organisation and the quality of its products. It can be further analysed that 35 customers were informed about the brands and the organisation via internet broadcasting. The organisation makes bonds with various applications, enabling them to advertise their products and services on the World Wide Web. It can be identified that their friends and relatives recommended 20 customers about the particular brand products and organisation. It is the moral

duty of an organisation to lay an efficient impression on the customers to help in the free promotion of their products and services. From the analysis, most customers got to know about the branded products of the organisation through the internet and its application. Organisations need to focus more on developing strategies to promote via the internet.

Theme 10: Recommendation to anyone about the brands

<i>Would you recommend anyone about the brands?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Definitely Not	18
not sure	22
Probably	44
Definitely	16

Description: In a survey of brand awareness, 100 customers were asked whether they would recommend the branded products they purchase from the organisation to their friends, relative, or other entity. In accordance with the questionnaire analysis, 18 customers deny that they will recommend the products they purchase from some particular organisation. It seems like organisations cannot make a good impression on the customer, or after-sale services provided to the customer were not efficient. It is also identified that 22 customers are not sure whether to recommend anyone about the brands or not. It can be seen that they face some issues with the products and are not fully satisfied with the brands' overall quality. The organisation has to improve the quality and quantity of the products and services to the customers. It can be seen from the analysis that 44 customers will probably recommend the branded products and the organisation whenever they get the opportunity. It depends upon the mood and thoughts of the

customer only. If he is satisfied with the quality, quantity, and price, he will assist an organisation in promoting its brands and products. 16 customers will recommend the brands and products of the organisation to their friends, relatives and any other entity. It seems like the organisation can give an effective impression to these customers in all sectors, from quality to customer satisfaction. From the analysis, it can be concluded that the majority of the customers will probably promote the branded products of the organisation.

Theme 11: Purchase of brand in future

<i>How likely are you going to buy the product in the future?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Very Unlikely	17
Somewhat Unlikely	26
Very likely	43
Not likely	14

Description: In a survey of brand awareness, 100 customers were asked how likely they will purchase brands from the same organisation in the future. This depends on the organisational policies and strategies which assist them in the attraction and retention of customers. In accordance with the questionnaire analysis, 17 customers will not purchase the brand from the same organisation. The company was unable to satisfy the customers’ requirements, or the service provided by them was not up to the mark. It can be analysed that 26

customers were in doubt whether to purchase from the same organisation or not. The organisation fails to fulfil all the qualities which the customer wants in the branded products. It can be identified that 43 customers will willingly purchase the same brand's products from the same organisation. The organisation succeeded to impress the customer by providing them with an efficient quality of products and services. The company marketing and branding strategies assist them in attracting and retaining customers. From further analyses, it can be seen that 14 customers will not purchase the products and services from the organisation. The organisation failed to impress the customers and require major improvements in the overall quality and services. From the analysis of the questionnaire, it can be concluded that the majority of the customers would willingly purchase the following brands from the same organisation, as the company was able to provide them with all the benefits and ability to increase customer satisfaction.

Theme 12: Quality affects them negatively

<i>According to you, what impacts the brand negatively?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Quality	34
Price	31
Quantity	16
Marketing	19

Description: There are different types of listed factors, which negatively impact the brand. As per the questionnaire collected from the customers, it is identified that people have a diverse set of perceptions held by people dependent on the situation given to them. In this respect, it can be stated that there are 16 of the customers who think that quantity hurts the brand. When customers do not get the expected quantity, it affects the brand image negatively. Further, there are 19 customers; from the type of perception that they have, it can be determined that marketing plays a vital role. Over time there are different types of changes that have taken place concerning the sources that are implemented to market the products and services delivered by the firm. In this respect, social media is highly helpful and beneficial for marketing and raising awareness about the goods. 31 individuals think that price is important, and when a firm does not make use of its strategies properly, it harms the business. Companies make use of pricing strategies to develop interest and willingness among customers. Service users generally prefer to use the products and services delivered to them at a low cost. Lastly, it can be stated that the organisation's quality needs to be considered. From the findings, it can be stated that customers think that when the quality of the products or services is not properly maintained, it affects the brand. More specifically, 34 of the customers think the quality is the main factor in negatively impacting the brand when firms do not consider it.

Theme 13: Price impact positively for brands

<i>According to you, which factors impacts positively for brands?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Quality	23
Quantity	17
Price	45
Marketing	15

Description: The questionnaire was conducted from 100 of the customers were selected from 5 different companies. Different factors are identified that can positively affect customers. From this, it can be stated that there is one main factor that has a high positive impact on the brand. More specifically, 45 of the customers think that price positively affects the brand. Some firms conduct event management. These events are helpful enough to develop a positive perception with the majority of customers. As per the research, it is identified that service users generally tend to use the products and services delivered to them at low price. In this context, companies that want to raise their brand loyalty should focus on using a pricing strategy in which the cost is low. Then it will be favourable enough to make customers feel positive about the services delivered to them. Further, 15 customers think that marketing is highly beneficial as it enables them to provide proper information about the products and services. Furthermore, people think that it enables to develop a healthy interaction with customers. This way, the firm's management gets to know the issues or the problems that are identified. As per

the findings, steps are taken to overcome them. There are 17 of the customers who think that quantity is favourable enough to raise customer’s loyalty. Lastly, 23 of the customers, from whom it is identified that quality is the important area that positively impacts a customer’s perception of the brand and enables to raise the brand loyalty of service users. However, most people are focused on price, which they think positively impacts brand loyalty.

Theme 14: Brand inspire loyalty

<i>Does brand inspire loyalty?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Definitely not	9
Probably	14
Definitely	58
Not sure	19

Description: Certain sets of perception are held by individuals from which considerations are made before product or services are purchased. The organisations must understand the requirements and take appropriate steps to fulfil them. From the questionnaire collected from customers, it can be stated that brand does inspire them to make purchases. In order to buy a product, customers generally consider price, quality, brand. This way, the brand is also a factor that individuals consider, and from the analysis made, it can be determined that brand does inspire loyalty. Service users tend to be loyal when the purchases made by them can satisfy their need and requirements. When these are fulfilled, then it becomes favourable enough to become loyal towards the product or services. For example, in event management, when there are many

types of services used by customers, which do not live up to expectations, they will develop a negative perception. They will also share their experience with others. The condition is just the opposite when customers are satisfied.

Further, their experience, which is shared with others, will also be positive. 9 customers think that brand does not inspire loyalty. Out of 100, there are 14 of them who perceive that there are some changes in loyalty due to brand. There are 19 of the customers who are not sure that the brand inspires loyalty. Lastly, as it was discussed, it is identified that the majority of individuals do think that loyalty is inspired with the help of a brand. Firms must take up appropriate steps to raise the brand issue. This is possible when management focuses on quality and price mainly.

Theme 15: Brand can fulfil the desire

<i>Can the brand fulfil your desire?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Very Unlikely	3
Somewhat Unlikely	41
Not sure	34
Very likely	22

Description: As stated above, certain sets of expectations are carried out by customers before purchases are made for products and services. With this respect, consideration is made for

the brand. When a branded firm's services are produced, it is generally done to get a high quality of services. In this respect, the price that is set for the services will be generally high. As per the findings made, it can be stated that there are 3 of the customers think that brand is very unlikely to fulfil their desires. When customers purchase products or services, they prefer to show off to others when they are branded. From the analysis made, it can be stated that brand is helpful enough to fulfil their desires. More specifically, 22 of the customers think that brand is very likely to fulfil their desires. The data shows that with the brand alone, individuals are not able to achieve their desired satisfaction. There are other sets of factors that are also considered; the brand is just one way to raise the satisfaction level. There are 34 of the customers who are not sure that brand is helpful to fulfil their desires. Lastly, 41 respondents think that a brand is somewhat unlikely to satisfy their desires. Accordingly, it can be stated that management needs to focus on all the factors that are considered by individuals through which they tend to fulfil their needs and requirements. This way, the level of satisfaction will be raised effectively.

Theme 16: High quality is what customers want from an event management industry

<i>What do you want from the event management industry?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Provide high-quality facility	52
Loyalty	18
Low price	16
Customer care	14

Description: There are different type of expectations that individuals develop, and this depends upon the type of services or products that one is willing to buy. As per the research topic, which is about event management, it can be stated that there are four different types of preference from which the customer can choose. There are five different types of organisations included that deliver services related to event management. From the findings, it can be stated that there are 16 of the customers who focus on low price for the type of services that the firm delivers. When the price is low for the services, these customers will use the services delivered by event management firms.

Further, there are 14 of the customers, who, according to them, when a firm focuses on customer care services, then these are the expectations they have from an event management industry. The expectations of customers are different when their perception is that considerations are made differently. Moreover, 18 of the customers prefer that the industry of event management needs to be loyal. There are different sets of requirements that customers need. The firm needs to

understand them and take appropriate steps so that service users are satisfied. The majority of the customers prefer to get services that are delivered to them at high quality. This is only possible when the event management considers all the requirements of service users and the quality of services delivered by them is of high quality. This way, it becomes helpful enough to satisfy the customers. Overall, it can be determined that quality is the factor considered mainly by the event management industry.

Theme 17: Key factors that influence the intention of purchase

<i>What are the key factors that influence your intention of purchase?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Brand Value	20
Services quality	37
Low Cost	29
User feedbacks	14

Description: The intention for making purchases for the product or services will be different for individuals. The organisation is benefited when they identify the requirement of services and can deliver goods accordingly. It is also important that management focuses on identifying the need for services and the main aim for which the products or services are purchased. From the findings, it can be stated that 14 of the customers make use of the services delivered by the organisation depending upon the feedback given by users. From the individuals who have made use of the products, it is useful to know about their experience. This way, the

issues that were faced or the satisfaction level that they attained can be determined. From this knowledge, 14 customers made their purchases. There are 29 of the customers who make purchases depending upon the cost. When the cost of services delivered by the event management firm is low, they will use it.

Further, some people consider brand value. When the brand's value is high, then there is automatically a positive perception developed in which customers think that the quality that will be attained is high. In addition to this, 37 of the customers think that when the quality they get is low, they will not make purchases. The firm needs to ensure that all the types of services delivered are of high quality. Therefore, the focus needs to be on the quality of services. This enables the development of a positive perception within customers' minds to use the services delivered.

Theme 18: Feels positive after utilising service of branded products

<i>How do you feel after utilising the service of branded products?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Positive	33
Negative	23
Neutral	29
No feelings	15

Description: When branded goods are used, it creates a positive perception and a good feeling. In branded products, the price to the customer is high. Because of this, the positive

perception is that they will get high-quality services. From the analysis made, it can be stated that there are 15 of the customers who did not have any feeling. This generally happens when people are loyal to the firm and know that their purchases will be effective.

Further, 23 of them do not feel good. This generally happens when the expectations they have before the purchases were made were not achieved. There are also conditions in which the purchases will not be made again when the desired goals are not achieved. 33 individuals feel highly good or have positive feelings when branded products are purchased. The majority of people know that when branded products are purchased, the quality of services will be high. In this respect, the companies should make proper consideration so that they will be able to determine the issues that are faced, even after branded products are bought. This is a type of condition in which customers may not prefer to make the purchase, and the experience shared will also not be effective.

Theme 19: Environmental protection measures followed by brands.

<i>Does your brand follow all the environmental protection measures?</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
No	3
Somewhat	41
Yes	34
Do not know	22

Description: An organisation needs to follow all the environmental protection measures for sustainable development. In a survey of brand awareness, 100 customers were asked whether the brands they purchase from organisations follow all the environmental protection measures. According to the questionnaire provided to customers, 3 customers say that the brands purchased by them do not follow the environmental protection measures. These organisations do not follow the environmental norms prescribed by the government, which leads to an increase in carbon emission and pollution in the country. It can be identified that 41 customers were not sure that the brands they purchase from the organisation use measures to protect the environment. The organisation fails to inform the customers about their practices to protect the environment for sustainable and green development. The company's responsibility is to raise awareness in customers about the corporate social role followed by them, and the measurement is taken to preserve and restore natural resources. From further analysis, it can be identified that 34 customers were sure that the practices followed by the organisations possess all due measures in

order to protect the environment. The practices include reducing carbon emission, air pollution, noise pollution, protecting natural resources. It can be identified from the analysis that 22 customers do not know about the environmental protection measures taken by the organisation from their purchases. These customers were only interested in the products and services and did not bother about practices followed by the organisation. From the following analysis, it can be concluded that the majority of customers remain in doubt as to whether the organisation follows the environmental protection measures or not.

Theme 20: Recommendation for improvement regarding the brand.

<i>What is your recommendation regarding the brand</i>	<i>Frequency</i>
Focus more on quality	45
Focus more on quantity	15
Focus more on price	23
Not required	17

Description: In a brand awareness survey, 100 customers were asked for suggestions and recommendations to improve their branded products. In accordance with the questionnaire, 45 customers suggested that the company has to focus more on the quality of the products and services, as quality is an important factor for any product segment. Further, it identifies that 15 customers recommend improving the quantity of the branded products in accordance with their

price. It seems that these customers were not getting enough quantity according to the price they were paying. From the analysis, it can be identified that 23 customers want the organisation to focus on price according to the quality and quantity of branded products and services, and 17 customers have no recommendation and suggestion regarding brands. It seems that either they were satisfied with the products or did not bother to suggest. From the analysis, most customers want the organisation to improve the quality of branded products and services.

4.4 Chi-square test

For the present research, the researcher uses SPSS tools such as the Chi-square test to develop valid conclusions.

There are two types of Chi-square test, and both statistics and distribution are for a different purpose.

A Chi-square goodness of the fit test assists in determining the sample data which matches a population.

A Chi-square test for independent help compares two variables in a contingency table, which helps in noticing if they are related.

A low value for Chi-square means that there is a high correlation between two sets of data.

However, if the expected values are equal, then chi-square will be zero

Reason

The Chi-square test is intended to test how likely an observed distribution is due to chance. It is also called a "goodness of fit" statistic because it measures how well the observed distribution of data fits with the expected distribution if the variables are independent. The reason for selecting The Chi-square test is that it provides degrees of freedom. It can be stated that the researcher filled the number of cells that are required to be filled. Along with this, it is extremely sensitive to sample size when the selected sample size is too large.

1.

Gender * Does brand inspire loyalty? Cross tabulation

Count

		Does brand inspire loyalty?				Total
		Definitely not	Probably	Definitely	Not sure	
Gender	Male	6	9	37	15	67
	Female	4	5	20	4	33
Total		10	14	57	19	100

As Per the above-given table, it can be stated that there are 37 of the male respondents who have selected definitely, which shows that brand does inspire loyalty. On the other hand, it can be stated that there are 20 of the female respondents who have stated that the brand does inspire loyalty.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.607 ^a	3	.658
Likelihood Ratio	1.699	3	.637
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.038	1	.308
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 2 cells (25.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.30.

In order to undertake hypothesis testing, the researcher needs to express the research hypothesis as null and alternative hypotheses. The null hypothesis and alternative hypotheses are statements regarding the differences or effects that occur in the population. When the findings are above .5, then it can be stated that the alternative is rejected and the null is accepted. Here the chi-square calculated value is less than the Chi-square critical value. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. In accordance with the findings, it can be stated that .658 is more than 0.5, and so the null is accepted, and the alternative is rejected. This shows that there are significant differences in the type of perception carried out by male and female.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.127	.658
	Cramer's V	.127	.658
	Contingency Coefficient	.126	.658
N of Valid Cases		100	

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

There are considerations made for the brand as it can get affected by the firm's price or quality. With this respect, all these aspects need to be considered before products or services are delivered. Further, the data shows that male and female respondents show significant differences.

2.

Gender * On a scale of 1 to 5 Star, how you will rate branded organisation? Cross tabulation

Count

		On a scale of 1 to 5 Star, how you will rate branded organisation?					Total
		1	2	3	4	5	
Gender	1	11	7	15	25	9	67
	2	4	3	10	10	6	33
Total		15	10	25	35	15	100

From the above table, it can be stated that 9 of the males have selected 5 stars as their option for the cited firm. On the other hand, 6 of the respondents from the female side who have chosen 5 stars have their option. When compared with both male and female, the majority of them have given 4 stars.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.510 ^a	4	.825
Likelihood Ratio	1.501	4	.826
Linear-by-Linear Association	.213	1	.644
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 3 cells (30.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 3.30.

From the above-given table, it can be stated that Chi-square is more than .5, and so the alternative is rejected, and the null is accepted. More specifically, the value identified from this test is .825.

Symmetric Measures

		Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal	Phi	.123	.825
	Cramer's V	.123	.825
N of Valid Cases		100	

- a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.
- b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

There is a significant difference between the responses that males and females give. The type of perception carried out by these two respondents differs.

3.

Gender * What key factors you consider before going for any brands? Cross tabulation

Count

		What key factors do you consider before going for any brands?				Total
		Quality	Quantity	Price	Brand Image	
Gender	1	30	16	12	9	67
	2	13	10	5	5	33
Total		43	26	17	14	100

The findings show that 12 of the male respondents think that price is considered before any brands are purchased. Further, there are 5 of the female respondents who think this way. There are 30 of the males think that the main factor that is considered before going for any brands is quality. On the other hand, there are 13 of the females who think the quality is considered first.

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.645 ^a	3	.886
Likelihood Ratio	.640	3	.887
Linear-by-Linear Association	.069	1	.792
N of Valid Cases	100		

a. 1 cells (12.5%) have an expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 4.62.

The Chi-Square identified it is .886, which shows that the alternative is rejected and the null is accepted.

Symmetric Measures

	Value	Approx. Sig.
Nominal by Nominal Phi	.080	.886
Cramer's V	.080	.886
N of Valid Cases	100	

a. Not assuming the null hypothesis.

b. Using the asymptotic standard error assuming the null hypothesis.

As per the response given by males and females, it can be stated that there is a significant difference. These are different factors that people consider before any purchases are done for branded products.

CHAPTER 5. Discussion

The research conducted on the firm managers' side shows a strong relationship between customers' purchase intention and the business's brand. In this context, Shukla, Banerjee and Singh, (2016) state that when individuals have a different set of perception or imagination when they hear of any product or name of the organisation (Alwi, Ali and Nguyen, 2017). This depends on the experience that they had with the firm or the services used, or the experience shared by others who have used the services or products of the firm (Johnson, Asare-Marfo and Birol, 2017, Hyun and Kim, 2011). In this context, it can be stated that the organisation needs to make a proper focus on the brand so that customers develop positive perception within their minds (Sürücü, Öztürk, and Bilgihan, 2019). The brand is highly effective in determining the image developed by service users in relation to the products and services (Gatrell, Reid and Steiger, 2017). Customers tend to make purchases only when they make sure that they will get satisfaction from the type of factors or the desires that are determined are achieved (Odoom, Odoom and Boateng, 2017, Bennett, Graham and Clemente, 2017). As per Tingchi Liu, Anthony Wong and Brock (2014), purchase decisions are made when individuals identify the need, and from the need, they aim to find out the products or services that will enable them to fulfil them. Further, evaluation is made based on price, quality, brand. When all these aspects are delivered, then the selection process takes place in which the best alternative is identified ((Sürücü, Öztürk, and Bilgihan, 2019). This way, there is a direct relationship between customers' purchase intention and the business's brand.

According to Hew, Lee and Lin, (2016), the ultimate aim of any firm is to gain maximum profit. This is only possible when they can understand the needs and requirements of customers and appropriate steps are taken to satisfy them. When requirements are fulfilled, an increase in sales is identified (Bennett, Graham and Clemente, 2017, Heinberg, Ozkaya and Taube, 2016). Sales are directly linked to when customers' satisfaction with the products and services that the firm delivers is high; then, it is favourable to raise sales (Grainer, Noble and Boltzmann, 2014). Further, customers' minds make them think positively when their understanding is high in relation to the firm and its services. This way, it can be stated that there is a direct link between sales strategy and brand (Esch, Langner, Schmitt and Geus, 2006, Shamim, Ghazali and Albinsson, 2016). From the analysis made by the manager, it is identified that there is a close link between sales and brand.

As per (Dedeoğlu, van Niekerk, and Okumuş, 2020), repetitive purchases are made when individuals know that their requirements are satisfied by the product or services provided. Despite that, many other companies deliver their customer's similar goods. The customers are well aware of their requirements and the type of quality that they will receive. This way, service users do not prefer to make purchases from other companies (Chae, Ko and Han, 2015, Marticotte, Marticotte and Baudry, 2016). In this respect, repetitive purchases are identified, and these are the customers who become loyal to the firm. From research conducted with 5 managers, it was identified that all of them understand that when a firm delivers their customers with quality products, then the rate of purchases made increases (Hakala, Svensson and Vincze, 2012, Yang 2010). In addition to this, other factors are considered, such as price or brand. When the quality is high, and the price is also high, customers may not prefer to make purchases. Different types of research are conducted, and it is identified by (Dedeoğlu, van Niekerk, and Okumuş, 2020) that people tend to make use of the services delivered to them at low cost but with high quality. When companies follow this, it enables them to develop positive perception within the minds of service users.

From the interview conducted with the firm managers, it is identified that when customers' perception increases positively, they raise the brand value (Janssen, Vanhamme and Leblanc, 2017). The business needs to make sure that customers face all the issues are identified, and appropriate steps are taken to develop a positive perception. As per Bilgihan (2016), there are target audiences made so that strategies are made according to their taste and preference. This way, when the brand contributes to the firm positively, it maximises the scope of targeted customers. One of the effective ways the brand can be developed is by understanding customers' requirements and delivering them services accordingly (Goyal and Srivastava, 2015, Keohane, 2014). In this context, the rate of desires of service users are satisfied and fulfilled (Hajli, Shanmugam and Richard, 2017). As a result, brand loyalty increases and the targeted customers also increase.

Chang, Kuo and Cheng (2014) stated that many changes had occurred regarding interaction or connecting with customers with time. When individuals have the proper information for the type of services and products delivered by the firm, people will tend to use the particular goods delivered by the firm. Different types of social media are helpful enough to have direct interaction with customers (Subramanian, Gunasekaran and Gao, 2016, Lam, Ho and

Law, 2015). This also provides the opportunity to understand the type of issues that individuals or customers face. According to the findings, it helps to develop strategies that can enhance the loyalty of service users. Furthermore, firms can provide information about new products or services introduced by the organisation (Cheung, Pires, and Rosenberger 2019). From the findings made, it can be determined that all the managers understand the benefit that they get from social media, so they do make use of the internet to increase brand awareness (Biedenbach, Bengtsson and Marell, 2015).

As stated above, there are many different types of identified tools that are highly beneficial in increasing brand loyalty. There are many sources available in context with advertising, including television, radio, newspaper, social media, etc. (Miquel-Romero, Caplliure-Giner and Adame-Sánchez, 2014). These enable to development of positive perceptions in customers' minds so that management can convey the proper information to service users related to their products and services. Apart from this, some advertisements are displayed on other websites, or there are also pop-ups. These are helpful for the individuals to get information and are also considered effective ways with the help of which brand value is raised (Fleury, Cardoso and Marques, 2014, Carter, Wright and Klein, 2014).

From the analysis of the findings made, it is identified that managers of different firms use various types of advertising sources that enable them to deliver proper information. According to Coleman, de Chernatony and Christodoulides, (2015), there are discount offers or free gifts that are provided by event management firms so that customers tend to develop willingness and interest and they make purchases (Hannibal and Rasmussen, 2017, Tingchi Liu, Anthony Wong and Brock, 2014).

There are different types of method used in social websites that make networking possible through which customers get to reach out for the services or the goods delivered. It requires proper innovation or creativity to attract customers (Shukla, Banerjee and Singh, 2016, Hew, Lee and Lin, 2016). Word of mouth is something that highly affects the sales and profitability of the organisation. When individuals are willing to organise any event, the firm must have a proper presentation for the requirement and needs of the customers (Cheung, Pires, and Rosenberger 2019). When these are not properly addressed and what was expected by the clients is not achieved, it develops negative perceptions. When a customer asks another about the company and states that their type of experience was not effective, individuals will not prefer to

make purchases from that particular organisation (Chow and Shi, 2015). A proper network is developed through a social media site that makes people reach out for services.

When a firm brand image is high, and the firm's services are also good, it enables the management to market their goods effectively. Purchases are made according to the type of perception held by customers (Tingchi Liu, Anthony Wong and Brock, 2014, Ghose, Heiman and Lowengart, 2017). Half of the products are viewed favourably when the firm has brand recognition. The other half depends on the quality of products and services delivered (Chang, 2017). From the interview conducted by managers, it is identified that the rate of sales and profitability increases when there is high brand recognition. This is possible when management makes use of marketing strategies. Management needs to focus on the issues faced by people so that they will be able to list these issues (Hew, Lee and Lin, 2016, Wirtz, Den Ambtman and Kandampully, 2013). As per the findings made, the proper analysis should be made to solve problems effectively (Marland, Lewis and Flanagan 2017).

As per Grainer, Noble and Broetzmann, (2014), different sets of factors that individuals determine before purchases are made. These include brand, quality, pricing, quantity, etc. From there, the main focus is made on quality and price. When the quality delivered by a firm is high, and the price is also high, customers will prefer to shift their consideration to a company that delivers them with a low price but high quality (Ghose, Heiman and Lowengart, 2017 ToHan, 2017). Service users prefer to make purchases from a brand recognised firm when they cannot compromise quality (Samran, Wahyuni, and Putri, 2019). Customers prefer to obtain services that are delivered with high quality. When this is not received, then there are issues faced. The intention for purchases becomes positive when the price is low and the quality delivered is high. The response given by managers shows that they understand the requirement of customers. However, there are issues that they cannot reduce the price as it depends on the materials or equipment used (ToHan, 2017, Casidy and Wymer, 2015).

Some people will prefer to purchase products that are of high price, and some may not. It is essential to ensure that management understands customers' requirements (Casidy and Wymer, 2015, Liao, Wu and Lin 2017). In the service industry, employees must have a proper understanding of the services that the firm delivers. When they lack proper information, then customers will not be able to receive data for the event that they prefer. As per Chang and Chen (2014), employees face organisation as they directly interact with customers. They are the ones

who recommend the products and services to users. If they do not have a proper understanding of the services, they will not clarify their doubts. Management needs to provide their workers with proper training so that they will be able to develop strong perceptions in the minds of customers (Liao, Wu and Lin 2017, Bilgihan, 2016).

Changes need to be made in all different type of aspects. It requires management to understand customers' requirements and deliver services (Samran, Wahyuni, and Putri, 2019). Customers' requirements are unlimited, and there are frequent changes identified. When the firm's management does not make changes in line with the needs of service users, they will not be able to satisfy them. Customers prefer to make sure of the services that are delivered to them, which contains improvement. For example, when the services delivered in the year 2010 and by 2017, there were no changes made, then management will not maintain the growth or sales (Hajli, Shanmugam and Richard, 2017, Anselmsson, Vestman Bondesson and Johansson, 2014). With time, changes need to be made, which enables developing positive perception within customers' minds. In accordance with the findings from managers, it is identified that volatility is important in event management to deliver proper experiences to customers.

Chang, Kuo and Cheng (2014) stated that a certain set of skills is required for an individual to perform a certain set of tasks. When it is not there, then one is not able to perform effectively. Conditions need to be made for managers to monitor their workers to identify the areas in which development is required. In this context, training and development are provided so that they can enhance their skills and capabilities. This is also helpful in clarifying the doubts that employees have regarding the services or the products provided by the firm (Anselmsson, Vestman Bondesson and Johansson, 2014, Miquel-Romero, Caplliure-Giner and Adame-Sánchez, 2014). Employees need to have a strong interaction with customers so that all the requirements for organising the event can be maintained effectively and efficiently. When there is proper interaction, it develops trust and confidence among the service users.

As per (Samran, Wahyuni, and Putri, 2019), when employees are engaged, management can make sure that the plan is properly enacted to their requirement. Further, engagement enables the determination to develop positive perception and also increases brand loyalty. Further, it is identified that regular purchasing customers become loyal to the firm when additional services are delivered. Organisations make use of different types of strategies that enable individuals to get involved with the firm. Some of the strategies include discount offers, special offers, free

gifts, packages, etc. (Miquel-Romero, Caplliure-Giner and Adame-Sánchez, 2014, Coleman, de Chernatony and Christodoulides, 2015). These types of strategies develop curiosity in customers to make use of the offers, and this way, the rate of sales and profitability increases. From the findings, it is clear that people are willing to use services when they get additional benefits, and the rate of engagement is high with the response given by managers.

Customers are the stakeholders on whom management focus to identify the requirement, and services are developed accordingly. From the research conducted with customers, most of them will prefer to make purchases from high-quality brand products (Coleman, de Chernatony and Christodoulides, 2015, Pansari and Kumar, 2017). There is a perception in which people think that high brand value products have high brand recognition. When these products do not perform according to customers' expectations, this harms the business. In this case, with the help of word of mouth, people will spread negative data about the experience they had when using the services or products. The proper focus must be on the services in which they maintain the quality as this makes sure that individuals develop positive perceptions.

There are different types of pricing methods that can be implemented by the firm so that they can increase sales (Pansari and Kumar, 2017, Shukla, Banerjee and Singh, 2016). Similarly, other related strategies like focusing on quality, communication strategies, providing free trials, etc., that contribute to raising brand image or loyalty towards the firm. When individuals get free trials, they can develop confidence in the goods as they know how effective they are or the level of satisfaction. When the product's price is kept the same, customers' focus will be made on quality. If the quality is also the same, then quantity is considered. On the other hand, when there are conditions in which all the firms have kept the price the same except for one, then customers will make purchases of the service or product where the price is low. It is important in event management to focus highly on quality, and low price is kept low so that they will be able to attract more and more customers (Erkan, Gokerik, and Acikgoz, 2019).

Further, the trust rate of individuals is also high as they know that branded products and services are highly effective to satisfy all their requirements and desires. The questionnaire gathered from customers found that they somewhat trust the branded products (Shukla, Banerjee and Singh, 2016, Pappu and Quester, 2016). However, most individuals are not sure as the management tends to adopt the strategies only when they get to know the requirements and needs of the customers.

There are different types of benefits that individuals acquire when they make use of branded products. From the research conducted, it is identified that most people or the respondents are satisfied when they make use of branded products. Consideration needs to be made by management that if the quality is not properly maintained, the business faces a high negative impact. Individuals develop negative perceptions about the company. There are some issues faced by customers when the quality is not properly maintained. In this context, the firm also needs to take time to research the problem, which is an effective way to understand the needs and requirements of customers. From the findings obtained, proper strategies can be developed to boost the sales and profitability of the organisation (Erkan, Gokerik, and Acikgoz, 2019).

Customers only purchase branded products and services if they find any benefits and satisfaction with them. In this research, it is identified that most customers are highly benefited by purchasing branded products, as these products increase the standard of living and assist in providing full self-satisfaction. According to Lee, Moon and Mun (2015), an organisation's production only achieves success when its goods can satisfy the customers' needs and demands and help gain the maximum benefits out of the products and services. It is vital, especially for the event management industry, as customers' expectations are very high in quality and services. From further analysis, it is identified that various customers cannot get any benefits or only minimum benefits after buying the branded products and services from various organisations (Pappu and Quester, 2016, Ene and Ozkaya, 2014). Thus, management's responsibility is to improve quality, quantity, or price to get maximum benefits by purchasing quality and branded products.

From the research conducted with customers, it is identified that the major factor which influences the customer to purchase branded products is quality. Quality plays an important role in determining the efficiency of products and services. As per (Erkan, Gokerik, and Acikgoz, 2019), quality can differentiate a product segment from local to brand. Branded products are efficient in quality and quantity. These products can easily attract more customers and help an organisation improve its sales and increase revenue generation. It can also be identified that many customers prefer quantity, price and brand image as factors that influence them towards the purchasing of branded products. Event management industries need to maintain the quality of services and products so that maximum customers can be attracted and existing customers can be

retained (Ene and Ozkaya, 2014, Biscaia, Correia and Maroco, 2013). To maintain the quality of products, the organisation has to work progressively in research and development to improve quality from time to time and according to the consumers' taste. This will lead to an increase in the growth and development of the organisation.

In this context, the research aims to identify the awareness of brands in consumers. As per the research, it is evaluated that major sector of customers find a difference in their brands and other organisations' brands. It is a positive sign for any company to make unique products and establish distinctive services from its competitors. (Sürücü, Öztürk, and Bilgihan, 2019), Stated that product differentiation is essential for an organisation in order to sustain itself in a competitive environment. Any company can develop uniqueness in its products by modifying, altering, or making subtle changes that are different from other brands available in the market. This will lead to productivity and growth in market share, and the organisation can easily penetrate the competitive marketing conditions. Further, it is also identified that many customers found no difference between the brands they own and brands available from the different organisation (Biscaia, Correia and Maroco, 2013, Chang and Chen, 2014). In event management industries, it is very important to maintain and offer branded products that have some distinctive quality, which makes them different from other brands and organisations, which attracts more customers and eventually leads to the growth and development of the organisation.

From which sources, customer gathers information about the brands and organisation is identified in this research. The source of marketing is very important for an organisation; it helps in communicating the products an organisation has to the customers. In this context, it is identified that most customers use the internet to collect information regarding the branded products and services provided by the organisation. According to (Sürücü, Öztürk, and Bilgihan, 2019), marketing plays an important role in the development and growth of any organisation. In the present era, the internet is very useful to share and gain any information regarding any organisation's products and services. Thus, the organisation must focus on more improvement regarding its products and services online to attract more customers. This will eventually lead to the growth and development of the organisation. It is also identified that various customers prefer sources other than the internet, such as newspapers, television advertisements, and suggestions from friends, relatives, etc. (Chang and Chen, 2014, Lu, Gursoy and Lu, 2015). Thus, for an event management organisation, it is very important and critical to choose its

marketing source after carefully analysing and proper surveying in the market. The company has to make a proper action plan, select an efficient source and work according to the action plan to achieve maximum profits at minimum cost.

Suppose an organisation can give customers a good impression by providing them with efficient products and services. In that case, that customer will recommend the experience to his friends, colleagues or any relative. In this research, it is identified that the majority of customers will probably recommend others about the organisation's products and services. It is analysed that the organisation needs to improve in some areas where it lacks fulfilling customers' requirements. As per (Cheung, Pires, and Rosenberger 2019), the company has to focus on all the sectors to maintain its position in the market. It has to ensure that all elementary things are in order from producing to packaging and marketing to selling. Customers only recommend that any organisation generate maximum benefits and experience satisfaction from the branded products (DaSilva and Trkman, 2014, Kim and Cho, 2014). In this context, many customers will recommend their friends, relatives, etc., about the quality products they purchase from an organisation.

Any customer will only purchase the same brand in the future when he can generate maximum benefit from it. In accordance with the research, it is identified that the major portion of customers are impressed with the branded products which they purchased from the organisations. This can be considered a positive sign to any company: they can attract and retain customers. According to Kiaie, Safari and Ghanbari (2013), retaining a customer is essential to any organisation as it determines the company's worth. The organisation has to focus on various key areas such as quality, quantity, and price to get the maximum benefit from it and purchase the branded products in the future (Pappu and Quester, 2016, Ene and Ozkaya, 2014). For any event management organisation, the company needs to build an effective relationship with customers to increase retention and attract the organisation.

Any company needs to maintain the quality of branded products; if the organisation fails to maintain the product quality, it will negatively impact its business. As per the research, it is identified that majority of customers voted for the quality factor, which can impact negatively on an organisation. (Cheung, Pires, and Rosenberger 2019), stated that an organisation has to work progressively to maintain effectiveness in the quality of branded products and services. It is even more essential for event management industries to develop quality up to the mark that satisfies

customer's requirement and needs. It can be observed from the research that many customers also consider factors such as quantity, price and marketing, which can affect the organisation brand negatively (Lu, Gursoy and Lu, 2015, Chan, Leung Ng and Luk, 2013). In order to eliminate the negativity, an organisation has to work hard to surpass these factors. Customers only purchase those goods and services which are high in quality, optimum in quantity and efficient in price.

The price of the product should be set according to the quality and quantity of that particular brand. In accordance with the research, it is identified that the majority of the customers voted for the price factor, which impacts positively for any organisation. According to Godey, Manthiou and Singh (2016), price is an important factor determining the brand and organisation. It should be set according to its worth. The price factor estimates the overall productivity of the organisation. In event management industries, price plays an important role in the attraction and retention of customers. The price is set according to the materials of which a branded product consists. The organisation's pricing strategy should be capable enough to generate profits and satisfy all the customers' needs and wants. It is further analysed that various factor such as quality, quantity, and marketing can positively impact any event management organisation (DaSilva and Trkman, 2014, Kleppe and Mossberg, 2015). Thus, they have to focus and work progressively to get more positive results and overall development.

The main aim of the branded products is to inspire loyalty from customers. Most customers say that brands inspire loyalty (Erkan, Gokerik, and Acikgoz, 2019). An increase in loyalty results in an increase in business turnover. Loyalty shows the commitment of the customers towards a particular brand and organisation. An event management company needs to provide efficient service and quality products to the customer, increasing loyalty and commitment. It is the responsibility of the organisation's management to develop the quality of products and services, which assists them in increasing the loyalty of customers towards the specific brand of the organisation (Kim and Cho, 2014, Fatema, Azad and Masum, 2015). In this context, many customers disagree that the brand inspires loyalty. The quality and price of the branded products inspire them towards purchasing the particular branded product.

Customers buy branded products only if they find that they will fulfil their desires and provide them maximum satisfaction. The research identified that branded products are not fulfilling the customer's desires in various respects. As per Lee, Moon and Mun (2015), if an

organisation fails to provide satisfaction to customers, it will eventually lose its market share in the competitive environment. Thus, they have to focus more on providing maximum customer satisfaction, either by increasing the quality of products or improving the after-sales service programmes. Any event management organisations need to fulfil all the customer's requirements to generate maximum benefits from it. It can be further identified that many customers are fully satisfied with the quality of branded products, and all their desires are fulfilled (Pappu and Quester, 2016, Ene and Ozkaya, 2014). Thus, the responsibility of management is to work progressively to improve the overall areas of the segment of branded products.

High quality is what customers want from an event management industry. The research identified that customers want high-quality work and product from any event management organisation. Saleem and Raja (2014) stated that quality plays a vital role in increasing the productivity and profitability of the business for any apex organisation. Providing an efficient quality of the product is the main responsibility of the organisation dealing with the event management business. Though increasing quality, they also need to consider that other factors such as quantity, price, and customer satisfaction are also important. Many customers want a low price, loyalty, and optimum after-sale service from the organisation (Ene and Ozkaya, 2014, Chan, Leung Ng and Luk, 2013). This implies that an organisation has to focus on production areas for better improvement in growth and development.

Various key factors influence customers' intention to purchase branded goods and services from an organisation. The research shows that the quality of service is the major key factor that influences any customer towards purchasing branded products from an organisation. This implies that customers are more focused on service quality rather than any other factor or element. According to (Dedeoğlu, van Niekerk, and Okumuş, 2020), the quality of service provided by the company will determine its future market position in the competitive environment. The further analysis identified that customers also focus on user's feedback, brand value, and low cost of the branded products and services provided by the organisation. Thus, management has to focus on improvement in all the organisation sections, i.e., from ground level to top-level activities.

The research identified that customers feel positive after using the branded product purchased from an organisation. The majority of customers perceives the feeling of positivity after using the products from branded organisations. According to Biscaia, Correia and Maroco

(2013), customers' feelings and satisfaction are two important elements to be fulfilled by the companies. They are the vital elements for an event management organisation, as customers always want something extra and beneficial from these organisations. It is the role of management to work on the overall structure of the organisation, which helps them increase customer satisfaction. It helps attract more customers and retain existing consumers (Chan, Leung Ng and Luk, 2013, Kleppe and Mossberg, 2015). The main aim of the event management company is to provide efficient quality products and services which aid them to accomplish the desires of the buyers and helps them to increase productivity, loyalty and profitability, which eventually leads to the growth and development of the organisation.

The research assists help in identifying the environmental protection measures taken by the event management organisation from the viewpoint of customers. An organisation needs to follow all the environmental protection measures for sustainable development. According to (Dedeoğlu, van Niekerk, and Okumuş, 2020), the organisation should work accordingly to increase its productivity and sales to preserve and preserve natural resources provided by mother earth. In accordance with the research, it is identified that organisations work to protect the environment only to some extent. The measures taken by the organisations are not enough to avoid the depletion of natural resources. The majority of the customers stated that the brands they purchase from an organisation do take many initiatives to protect the natural resources. From further analysis, it is visualised that many customers are aware of the various practices taken by the organisation in the preservation and restoration of natural resources (Kleppe and Mossberg, 2015, Fatema, Azad and Masum, 2015). Thus, the organisation has to improve its corporate social responsibility practices and participate in various environmental protection activities to improve the overall environmental condition.

An organisation should always seek suggestions for improvement from its valuable customers. The majority of the customers recommended that organisations improve the quality of products and services sold by them from the research. As per Kiaie, Safari and Ghanbari (2013), customer feedbacks should be taken as treasure by the management of organisations. This valuable feedback helps improve the quality of products and aid an organisation to increase the attraction, commitment, loyalty, and retention of customers. The event management industries need to focus more on improving the quality provided to the customers. If the customers are not fully satisfied, they will not buy any services in the future from the same

organisation but seek some alternatives and substitutes. From further analysis, customers also recommend that organisations focus on areas other than quality, such as price, quantity and marketing (Fatema, Azad and Masum, 2015). It would increase overall productivity and profitability and overall growth, and the organisation's development.

5.1 Summary

In this chapter, the researcher has analyzed the collected data most appropriately and efficiently. The researcher has carried out analysis by using a thematic form for analysing both qualitative and quantitative data. Chi-square test and contingency coefficient analysis have been undertaken by using SPSS by the researcher to test the hypothesis. Different people have a diverse set of perceptions that individuals hold. In this context, the findings show that people prefer to make purchases for branded products as they meet up the requirements and preferences of people. Apart from this, the price of products also affects the perception held by customers. When the price of the product is low, then it is assumed that quality will be low. Thus, it is generally identified that people make purchases according to their needs. It requires the business to understand customers' needs and take up initiatives with the help of which they can achieve their set of goals and objectives.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Conclusion

From the research made on a critical investigation on how brand awareness impacts customers' purchase intentions in the UK event management industry and determine how mid-sized event-based companies located in the UK can develop effective customised sales strategies that influence the purchase intentions their targeted customers. It is understood that brand awareness in customers impacts the overall working of the organisation. There are many key factors that aid to promote the customers' purchase decisions to a great extent. These factors can vary from the quality of products to the marketing strategy implemented by the organisation. Other factors such as intelligence, creativeness, and trustworthiness also influence buyers to purchase a particular product or service. These factors are essential in improving the organisation's performance, leading to its growth and development. As per the results generated in the research, it has been concluded that brand awareness has a positive significant relationship with the consumer purchase decision. Whereas, social media content marketing has a moderate positive significant relationship with the consumer purchase decision. The findings reveal that social media content marketing has high input in explaining the variance in a consumer purchase decision. It is expected that this research would be of great help to the firms to create brand awareness.

It also identified the importance of brand awareness in order to increase the purchase intention of customers. Various facilities are integrated by the event management organisation that assist customers by providing easy and quick information to them. It has been further found that the organisation based on event management firmly uses online marketing strategies for increasing their customers and production. In accordance with the research, it is concluded that in order to long-run, companies use aspects such as increasing the expertise of personnel which enables them to focus on the products and services of the corporation. It is identified that customers prefer a brand just because of its involvement and emotional appeal. The event management sector emphasizes promoting their services and work progressively to increase the level of customer satisfaction. It has been found that companies use tools and techniques to increase the awareness of brands in customers, such as improving quality, increasing quantity, providing efficient pricing for effective products and developing good marketing strategies to generate more customers and move on the path of growth and development.

Along with this, event management companies use innovative approaches to gain positive reviews from buyers. This will aid in ensuring the long-term growth and survival of the business. It has been identified that brand awareness is essential for the upward direction of the business that results in assisting corporations in gaining a strong market position. It aids to integrate all business activities in deriving valid outcome. In the research, the areas covered by mid-sized event management organisations in generating brand awareness in customers were analysed briefly. The outcomes show that these sectors mainly include quality, quantity and price of the products and services provided by these corporations.

One more thing that affects the event management businesses of the UK is greater competition due to the availability of various tourist destinations and the operation of the number of tour operators in the same. The increase in competition leads to various substitutions and alternatives of products that consumers can purchase from the markets. This affects the generation of revenue and the turnover of sales from business to business. Various organisations design attractive logos and slogans to gain customers' attention to increase their image and sales. This strategy encourages new organisations to develop a unique and trendy identity that helps them run for a long period and assists in tackling competitive situations. From the thesis, some organisations develop a unique strategy of branding known as no-brand branding. The products that are of no brand are generally very simple and generic in terms of design.

Successful companies use this type of strategy to attract many consumers, thus increasing their profitability. The change in recent situations forces organisations to formulate and implement various strategies that lead to the business's growth and development. Changes in taste and preference of communities and consumers result in changes in event management corporations' structures and functions. Now they are more focused on increasing their promotion to survive in the competitive markets and developing qualities of goods and services to maintain the status and recognition of brands. From this, it is clear that there is a direct relationship between brand awareness and customer purchase intentions in the UK event management industry. The quantitative research framework reflects the methodology used in the present research, presenting the findings effectively in deriving a valid outcome. The thesis was conducted in an appropriate manner which aids to accomplish the research objectives and purpose.

The quantitative framework was used in the research for carrying out analysis based on factual data. Both the frameworks were used together, which resulted in a valid conclusion and efficient outcomes. From the thesis, it can be concluded that the researcher applied a deductive approach in conducting the research, which helps in the study with theories and general knowledge relating to the objectives of the proposal. The descriptive research design is used in conducting the study. This results in assisting the researcher in presenting the findings most effectively. From this, it can be concluded that the researcher made a critical and brief study of the overall population and made an efficient analysis of data and information collected by him through various sources. Moreover, the descriptive research design helps assess the impact of brand awareness on customers' purchase intention.

Interpretivism philosophy is selected by the researcher, which helps find several facts of single truth in accordance with existing knowledge. The selection of interpretivism research philosophy results in conducting an in-depth analysis of the collected data and deriving the most appropriate outcome. From this, it is clear that the aim and objectives were able to be accomplished with the help of a specific research design and philosophy. The data and information were collected from primary and secondary sources that included surveys, questionnaires, and information from various books, journals, newspapers, and business magazines. The researcher used various statistical tools correlated with the proposal, resulting in effectiveness and efficiency in the research.

The research thesis structure was properly ordered, and activities were conducted according to systematic chapters formulated by the researcher. The first chapter describes the introduction of the thesis. It contains aims, objectives, research methodology to be used, and philosophies to be applied in the proposal. These are considered the most important aspects through which the researcher came to know about the rationale behind selecting a particular topic for investigation. It represents the effectiveness of the topic and relates it specifically to the readers. The second chapter consists of literature reviews in which secondary data are presented effectively. With the help of various sources like ISI-ranked journals, reputable publishers like Oxford University and Blackwell, the researcher effectively accomplished the proposal. By using these sources, the researcher was able to produce a good outcome. The previous work of various research scholars assisted the researcher in making this project effective, which helps the readers and contributes to society.

As for brand awareness in consumers, which is essential in the present era, the researcher focused on all the literature reviews and previous articles essential in completing the thesis. The third chapter shows the research methodology applied in this proposal. Various methods such as type of investigation, research design, philosophy and approaches are explained explicitly. This results in the opportunity for readers to understand the significance of each type of methodology and its contribution towards developing a valid outcome. The end result or outcome of the thesis is found in the fourth chapter, which helps the researcher analyse the collected data using suitable tools and techniques.

The results are adequate for readers to get an in-depth understanding. The discussion and conclusion are the fifth and last chapter of the proposal in which all collected information and analysis is presented. This results in effectiveness by providing valid recommendations, and the researcher can shed light on the main findings and their direct relevance with the research topic.

The researcher used various literature articles made by previous scholars to increase brand awareness in consumers. These literature reviews enabled the researcher in accomplishing the thesis. The research shows the current investigation is based on the relationship between brand awareness and purchasing intention, which recommends a suitable sales strategy for mid-sized event-based companies where the researcher splits the aim into objectives. The aim of the study has been accomplished with the help of assessing the impact of brand awareness on purchase intention in the event management industry of the UK first. Then different key factors influencing the intention to purchase are identified in the research. In this context, it is identified that brand is considered the foremost aspect of adding value. It is regarded as an intangible asset for the business whereby the corporation can effectively increase its overall rate of return along with the higher level of satisfaction among users.

Event management organisations use various tools and techniques to generate more and more customers and improve their brand image. Thus, by using various literature reviews, the researcher could make a precise decision that supports the following research. From this, the conclusion was made regarding the purchase of products based on the following brands. Customers who are attached with a brand behaviourally will tend to be loyal but not emotional. On the other hand, some consumers attached to a particular brand with respect to emotion only. Branding is popularised only with the help of a selection of marketing strategies. The businesses apply sources of communication to gain buyers' attraction and make them more aware of various

products and services. These sources include television advertising, mass media and online marketing.

This results in assisting business by increasing their attention towards the work and provides them with the most suitable kind of services for the wellbeing of consumers. Regarding this context, it is identified that to achieve a leading brand organisation, the workforce's involvement is essential. For these various organisations conduct formal meetings organised with personnel to extract their views and suggestions. This is done more effectively through consultation and an open session. Employees make direct relationships with customers, which helps the organisation produce those quality goods and services that result in the overall productivity of the event management corporations. Digital and human interaction reduce customer complaints as automated systems, and diligent workers handle their complaints. From this, it can be concluded that an organisation cannot increase customer loyalty until the audience or buyers are highly satisfied.

The company's customer service department and their reputation, publicity and trademark or logo of the establishment are involved while considering its brand. It helps the marketing strategy of a business by directly supporting them in the process of advertising. In the achievement of business goals, an effective branding strategy inspires the employees to a great extent. This is the end result of the literature reviews derived by the researcher. Thus, these articles result in improving the overall quality of the research and thesis. Many authors and publishers have previously worked on the brand awareness topic, which helped the researcher conduct an efficient and effective proposal based on genuine facts, appropriate data and generic information. From this context, it can be concluded that to achieve the thesis's aim and objectives, the researcher had to take the help of an appropriate literature review. It helps in studying the behaviour of customers but also assists the organisation in finding its position in the competitive markets. It is identified that a customer-centric approach is apparent to grow with time.

An event management organisation targets it, customers based on their tastes and preferences. From this, an organisation must understand the real interest of the consumers and the activities in which they tend to engage more. The companies can prompt identification of the opportunities to consider creating goods for the closely analysed customers. From the research, it

can be identified that many authors believe that the businesses which take a customer-centric approach are more likely to interpret the purchase behaviour of their clients and users.

Their opinions of customer lifetime value are yet another method by which the consumers can be segmented based on their spending power. In this context, brands that are factually committed to this approach must undertake a passionate attitude to serve the users. From the context, one of the authors believes that it is important for the brands to believe that businesses cannot succeed without getting a prompt response from the consumers. This results in enabling the brands to reflect a more committed outlook towards serving the customers by jointly maximising their experiences. The research identified that brand awareness is considered the prominent aspect behind every organisation's success, which helps them determine their upward direction.

Consumers are more attracted to brands rather than local products and services. From this context, a consumer's intention to purchase is automatically linked with brand awareness. Event management organisations are greatly benefited from offering branded products and services to their variety of consumers. Benefits include greater market shares, overall growth and development, formulation of effective brand image, increased goodwill, and eliminating competitive drawbacks. This assists the corporation in attracting more buyers and keeping them loyal. In this manner, the business's marketing department plays an important role as customers remain satisfied whilst they do not get much better alternatives in the market until they perceive a similar firm is providing the necessary services and products to effectively cater to their requirement. The greater focus on research and development results in ample growth and improvement, thus providing customers with efficient quality products and services.

The shareholders get higher returns due to an increase in productivity and profitability, and the satisfaction of consumers. The thesis determined that the brand image of an organisation showcases its value in the global or national market. Thus, it is concluded that the brand can take the organisation to an international level to treat the customers from different countries. It is identified that brand strategies are extremely important to maximise awareness in numerous consumers worldwide. For this, various social media website such as Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, etc. are used to promote the products and services of the organisation. An online social network proves to be effective for reviving the brand in marketing and raising its awareness

among customers. In this regard, online communities remain highly focused on raising awareness, resulting in more and more customers for an organisation.

It is not the case that online marketing always leads to an effective promotion; both negative and positive outcomes can be derived through an online mode of communication. Appropriate schemes formulated by the organisation can lead to the positivity of promotion and reducing any conflicts. For event management organisations to produce effective quality products and efficient tag lines to advertise their products, no community's sentiments can be harmed. In this context, firms effectively showcase its product and services that the first impression can last for a long time. The research analysis identified that brand awareness seems to be a very important factor behind the corporation's success. It integrates employees and makes them able to incorporate in the decision-making procedure. Branding requires big budget investment in different financing activities, which is critical to face the competition in the marketplace, and some buyers might still switch to another brand. According to the research into event management, it is important for the event management industry in the UK as it assists in order to bring a wide range of customers to the business and also motivates them to come again. Consumer purchase behaviour is classified into five components: problem recognition, information search, alternative evaluation, purchase decision, and post-purchase behaviour. Each step contains its value and determines the nature of the consumer while buying any product from several organisations. Therefore, consumer buying behaviour is important and directly associated with the brand value of the business.

This facilitates the corporation to deliver a good quality of services in accordance with their requirement. It is identified that the consumer gives serious attention to the brand when making a purchase decision. This is because of perceived quality and other related features. This results in making their experience very positive and enables them to prefer a particular brand. At the same time, this forces the organisation to focus on a particular brand and its unique features to make it different from the one which competitors already offer. The researcher takes help from the Aaker model, which describes the loyalty of consumers in five levels. These levels are switcher, habitual, satisfied, likes and committed. This is the tallest consumer buying decision that helps decide customers and defines their loyalty towards a particular product brand. The branding iceberg shows they do not see several elements, some of which are seen by the

customers. This model represents how a company builds its image or brand value by satisfying the customers.

The third chapter focuses on using a different set of methods and techniques to research effectively. In accordance with the research, there is a different set of techniques that the investigator applies appropriately. Step by step is focused in this chapter so that viewers will understand the research process. This research investigates how brand awareness can enable changes in customers' perception positively. From the second chapter, it was identified that there are different types of factors that are considered by individuals when any purchases are made. The firm needs to consider these requirements and take appropriate steps to develop the customer base.

Furthermore, certain sets of expectations are listed down by customers before products or services are used. The brand of the firm enables to raise sales and profitability. It also helps in raising the understanding of customers for the type of goods that are delivered. Moreover, research methodology includes various techniques, approaches, etc., that focus on understanding the topic and selecting appropriate methodologies.

Research methodology is an essential part of the dissertation that uses an entire process for collecting information and analysing it to develop an appropriate outcome. Research design determines the general plan for the research to get an appropriate answer for the topic. There are three different types of research design. From these three types, this research has made use of descriptive research. This design was selected as it enables to provide in-depth understanding in relation to the topic. Five companies were selected, and this method has helped make a proper evaluation of the strategies and develop an effective way to make an evaluation. When this is applied, it enables the development of proper steps through which the dissertation is completed. On the other hand, when these methods are not applied, it becomes difficult for the readers or even investor to determine the proper outcome. In conducting any activities, it needs to have an effective plan to achieve the desired goals. One can develop plans for the future that can be applied, and thus, the objectives set at the initial stage are attained.

The research approach is essential for scientific study, and this is not focused on any specific research area. For the investigator, it was important to select an appropriate approach. There are three types of approaches identified, among which, deductive is the one conducted based on assumptions. Further, an inductive approach is focused on developing new theories,

which helps in providing adequate understanding. Among these approaches, the deductive approach is applied in which the researcher can carry the research from general to specific. This way, it has helped in enhancing the validity of research aspects. In addition to this, it also focused on testing whether there is any type of relationship between general circumstances. Different theories are explored, which are related to developing awareness and how brand value can be raised. It has provided the investigator with an adequate path for logical values that are effectively integrated. At the initial stage, the research has focused on using theories, which has led to developing hypotheses. At the end of the research, there is a list of developed strategies through which the investigator knows whether the hypothesis got accepted or rejected.

Further, research methodology includes philosophy, a specific aspect that enables determining nature, development of knowledge, and scope. This carried an important dimension with the help of which the research is carried out. In other words, the investigator can get a proper outcome for the research questions that are formed. There are four different types of categories included. From this, the research has used positivism in which different forms of dimensions are present. In order to make a proper evaluation of the topic, many methods can be applied other than a scientific method. Through observation, the type of factual knowledge that is obtained is focused. With this philosophy, an investigator is also able to interpret by observing quantifiable data.

There are different types of methods identified through which information in relation to the research topic is selected. In accordance with the selected research topic, it can be stated that different ways can encourage the development of in-depth understanding. Researchers use two types to collect information. In this respect, effective sources include primary and secondary information. Primary data are gathered with the help of interviews and developing questionnaires. More specifically, there were two different groups of selected respondents to get adequate information for the topic. In this context, 5 managers from different companies are selected to have proper information and understanding about the research topic. They know the strategies implemented by companies to develop brand image and raise customers' loyalty. Further, there were 100 customers selected, 20 each from the five different companies. These are selected as respondents as they make use of the services that are delivered by event management. On the other hand, secondary information was gathered with the help of books, journals, articles, etc. Other researchers on similar topics conducted many kinds of research to help raise

understanding for the same. This way, both secondary and primary data has helped in raising the understanding and developing in-depth knowledge.

Many individuals can be selected as respondents, but it becomes difficult to analyse the same properly. With this respect, the sample size was taken from a large population to get appropriate outcomes. There are two types of sampling methods which are probability sampling and non-probability sampling. If a large sample size is selected, it becomes difficult to analyse it. Research made use of a non-probability sample, in which there are 5 companies selected from event management. A single manager was selected from each of the firms; thus, 5 of them. In addition to this, 20 customers selected from 5 companies, which is in total 100 customers. These selected respondents have adequate information and knowledge related to the research topic. In this context, questionnaires were carried out from customers and interview were conducted with managers. This way, the investigator will be able to come up with a proper outcome in accordance with the research topic. The selection of five companies was done randomly, and the selection of the customers was also done randomly. This was effective in providing an equal opportunity to all the population of managers, companies and customers. Further, it helped select 100 customers and 5 managers from 5 different companies involved in event management.

After collecting information from respondents, it is important to make a proper analysis of the data gathered with the help of questionnaires and interviews. For this respect, there are different types of methods that the investigator would have used. As per the analysis made, thematic was applied to make use of graphs, tables, etc. Further, it consists of inspection, improvement, transmutation, and modelling of the gathered information to ultimately result in the disclosure of helpful data that suggests some refined conclusions that support the surveyor to undertake justified decisions at the end. It also involves both unprocessed and refined information. When the analysis is made, then it helps to provide an outcome of the research topic. More specifically, companies involve different types of strategies to raise their brand loyalty among customers. In this respect, these firms focus on understanding the needs and requirements of customers to come up with an appropriate outcome so that the rate of satisfaction can be raised. The analysis has enabled management to evaluate the process effectively and determine the strategies adopted to improve the quality of work. In addition to this, through graphs, tables and charts, it becomes easy for them to understand the outcomes.

Certain sets of limitations are identified concerning the main issues raised due to lack of financial support. There are different types of developed activities, which help conduct the activities effectively. In this context, there is the requirement of an effective analysis to complete the listed-out activities. Further, it is also important that the aim and objectives are made clear so that a step-by-step process is developed through which the research is achieved.

Further, certain ethical considerations have to be taken into account, i.e., all the personal information gathered from the respondents. For this purpose, there was a system used so that information can be protected. All the respondents were informed about the need and the reason for which the research was being conducted. This helped in making individuals focus on the questions that were asked and to provide appropriate answers. Apart from this, all the data used from the research conducted by some other person is used as a reference and properly cited.

By analysing the data, it is concluded that there are many ways there is a great impact on brand awareness on customer purchase intention. Also, by interpreting interview and questionnaire data, the answer to the research question is evaluated. Thus, with the help of data analysis, aims and objectives are attained.

In order to make purchases of a product or services, proper considerations are made by customers before the process of purchase takes place. With this respect, it is important to make sure that the firm is focused on researching as this helps to identify the issues faced by the customer. Over time many changes take place. When research is conducted, then all the related changes are identified. This way, it helps the firm take appropriate steps so that the performance rate can be raised and the customers can develop positive perceptions. Also, some companies deliver their user is similar products and services. In order to overcome this, it requires the business to have close interaction with their customers. For this process, it is necessary to need to use social media to have direct interaction. All the information about new products or services can be displayed on social media and enables the company to get feedback from the customers about their perceptions. When the perception is negative, it will affect the business, but it can help develop strong relationships with customers.

In order to develop the brand, the focus should be on marketing as this helps develop a positive image for the customers' mind. When individuals get more and more information about the firm, it encourages them to get attracted by the products and services of the firm. Further, there is a direct relationship between customers purchasing intention and brand. When customers

intend to use the goods, they have proper information and knowledge about them. Further, certain expectations that customers carry out before purchases are made; therefore, all their requirements and expectations must be fulfilled. The type of expectations that customers have includes quality, quantity, price, etc. When several companies deliver any goods at the same price, but one firm provides them more cheaply, customers who focus on price will make purchases from this particular organisation. When there is high brand recognition, then it becomes helpful in raising sales and profitability. Management needs to consider employees as they are the ones who have direct interaction with customers; they must have the proper information for the type of roles and responsibilities that they play. If employees are not sure or have doubts, they cannot present their work positively. In order to overcome this, proper monitoring needs to be done by the managers so that they can identify the problems faced by the workers. Accordingly, steps should be taken that can boost employees' performance so that customers are satisfied. A high focus needs to be made on quality as customers prefer to use the products and services they deliver at high quality.

In event management, there must be frequent changes in the technology or the requirement of customers. The rate of competition is very high. Customers tend to develop negative perceptions when their experiences are not favourable. It is important that all customers get satisfied and that they share their positive experience. In event management, people generally prefer to make use of services that are of high quality, so that experience that individuals had was positive. Management needs to have effective interaction with customers so that all their needs and requirements are considered. This helps make sure that all the appropriate steps are properly taken to achieve this and thus the satisfaction rate. Furthermore, the people who make repetitive purchases do so because they determine that they are satisfied. These individuals who make purchases regularly are the ones who become loyal to the services, and they will share their experience with others.

There are different types of sources that companies use in order to promote their services. Social media is considered to be the most effective as it enables to development of proper understanding. There are other tools of advertising such as email, newspapers, television, etc. Sources are highly beneficial in order to provide proper information to customers. Employees are the face of the organisation as they are the ones who have direct interaction with customers. The business needs to find out the workers who have doubts about their roles. Therefore, they should

be provided with the training. Management is responsible for this analysis, but areas of development need to be identified before providing training. This way, the employee's contribution will be raised, and they will increase the satisfaction level.

There are different types of pricing strategies used, which help develop a positive perception within customers' minds. Some individuals will prefer to make use of services that are delivered to them at a low cost. In this respect, the pricing strategy should be applied to be low compared with the company's competitors. The companies need to focus on the pricing and quality of the services as these are the main aspects that individuals consider. When these areas are focused, then it raises the satisfaction level and increases brand loyalty. When the price is low, and the quality is high, customers' intention becomes favourable towards the services delivered by the firm. Frequent changes need to be made by companies so that they will be able to develop value, and this is also helpful in attaining a competitive advantage. Changes can be in the technology used and in the improvement in services, etc.

There are other types of strategies applied to attract customers, including discount offers, special offers, etc. These develop curiosity among customers and make them consider purchasing the services delivered. When individuals are engaged, it becomes favourable to increase the satisfaction level and develop a positive image for the firm. Many customers purchase products or services of those firms which have high brand value.

Therefore, by analysing the data, it is concluded that in building a positive image of their brand, companies have to try very hard. To keep the consumer aware of their brand and to sustain their customer a company will have to keep triggering its brand and advertise more and more to let a large number of people know about their brand.

6.2 Recommendations

From the research made on brand awareness in consumers, various areas were identified, which can, directly and indirectly, influence the purchase of branded products by customers. Event management organisations need to develop efficient quality products and services that benefit societies and communities at large. From the analysis, several sectors were identified where the organisation needs some improvement. Recommendations and suggestions for the overall improvement and development of goods and services which can direct organisations to move on the path of success are provided below:

- *Improvement needs in the quality of products-* Customers expect branded products and services to be high quality to generate maximum benefits. Event management organisations are recommended to focus more on the research and development sector of the company so that more effective and efficient quality services can be developed. In addition, these corporations need to improve the overall attribution of products provided to the customers. It helps minimise complaints and aids in increasing the overall image of the brand and organisations. Quality of goods and services is the key factor that aids to promote the customer's purchase decision to a great extent.
- *Improvement required in promotional activities-* The promotion of products and services is vital for organisations, especially those who deal with event management businesses. Companies should interact with the customer by their facing activities so that it becomes easy to provide them with quick information related to products and services. Branding of an event has its own importance, such as promotion, creating brand strategy and setting it up for success. The source of advertising should be effective and customer-centric. It describes the products specifically, and tag lines should not offend any religion or community. An efficient marketing strategy can lead the organisation in the direction of growth and development. In this context, corporations should not neglect the marketing of products and services, leading to loss and deficits.
- *Minimise Complaints-* Complaints arise from customers when organisations cannot provide them with the required product or services. Consumer complaints create negative effects on companies' brand image. This will not only impact on retention of consumers but also negatively affects the attraction of more consumers. To minimise consumer complaints, event management organisations need to focus on the quality, quantity and price of the products. The company's customer service department and its reputation, the publicity and the trademark or logo of the establishment are involved while considering its brand. The organisation must establish a customer care centre, where customers can lodge their grievances or the problems they face with particular products or services. In addition, the organisation must conduct a customer feedback survey to increase their level of knowledge and understanding of the behaviours of the different customers with whom they deal.

- *Improvement in quantity*- The meaning of brand will remain worthless to customers when paying more and getting less. Organisations must improve their strategies regarding products and services quantity, which It should be set according to the price charged and the quality of goods. To increase brand awareness in consumers, companies must focus on quantitative strategies to benefit all the consumers; for this, top management should emphasise developing suitable strategies that can benefit them and society to a greater extent. For an event management organisation, quantity is an important factor that can assist them in sustaining long-run growth and helping them in avoiding competitive pressures.
- *Increase workforce satisfaction*- From the research made, it was identified that to increase the quality of branded products and improve relationships with consumers and the organisation's internal workforce, satisfaction is required. If employees and employers are satisfied with the overall working environment, they will work full motivation and determination. This will directly affect the brand awareness and the goodwill of the company in a positive way. For increasing workforce satisfaction, organisations must conduct multiple activities and practices that involve employees from all levels. This can improve the decision-making process and results in the overall growth of the company. It is recommended that the event management corporation improve employee satisfaction to increase brand quality, commitment, and loyalty.
- *Target consumers globally*- To increase the sales and generation of revenue, the organisation has to focus on developing its market share. The event management business of the UK suffers from greater competition due to the availability of varied tourist destinations and the operation of the number of tour operators involved. For the organisation operating at the mid-level, it is recommended that they increase their capital through investments to deal with international clients and customers. This can only be done if the organisation at the domestic level develops its brand image and awareness in local customers and society, which will result in greater profit and an increase in the overall growth and development of the organisations.
- *Improvement in individual branding*- Individual branding can happen when larger companies manufacture products with their brand name and are independent of their parent company. This strategy will help in establishing the new brand as a unique

identity. This will be very easily recognisable. The event management organisation is advised to improve the strategy of individual branding to increase brand awareness with customers of different segments. It will result in the overall growth and improvement in the corporations' quality and quantity of products and services.

- *Improvement in pricing strategies-* Pricing strategies implemented by the organisation for the branded segments of products should be appropriate. They must be based on the quality and quantity of goods and services. The price of products must be the optimum which can satisfy the customers and their needs. Every product segment should be classified according to the manufacturing cost and selling cost. The event management organisation is advised to set the prices of their services per the products they will offer to targeted customers. This will affect the organisation positively, which will result in increased productivity and the corporation's growth at large.

Thus, if the event management organisation covers these points, it will surely lead them to the path of success and growth. In the modern era, competition is increasing highly, making it critical for businesses to grab the attention of buyers. For this purpose, it is very important to shed light on the expectations of customers. Extra benefits associated with service delivery are considered by the corporation by which customer satisfaction can be increased greatly.

6.3 Summary

The researcher has provided a summary of the whole thesis, briefly covering all the chapters and findings. Consumers are more attracted to brands rather than local products and services. Thus, a consumer's intention to purchase is automatically linked with brand awareness. Event management organisations are greatly benefited from offering branded products and services to its variety of consumers. The researcher has also provided recommendations that the organisation can implement to enhance their customer base. Firms need to use various promotional strategies to provide adequate information to customers about the services and products that are delivered. Furthermore, the business must train their workers so that they develop their skills and capabilities. The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between brand awareness and purchasing intention, recommending a suitable sales strategy with the objective concerned with examining the relationship of brand awareness with the consumer purchase decision.

REFERENCES

Books and Journals

- Aaker, D. A. and Joachimsthaler, E., 2012. *Brand leadership*. Simon and Schuster.
- Aaker, D., 2014. *Aaker on branding: 20 principles that drive success*. Morgan James Publishing.
- Acharya, A. and Rahman, Z., 2016. Place branding research: a thematic review and future research agenda. *International Review on Public and Nonprofit Marketing*. 13(3). pp.289-317.
- Aharoni, I. and Grinstein, A., 2017. How to (re) position a country? A case study of the power of micro-marketing. *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*. pp.1-15.
- Ahmad, A. E. M. K. and et al., 2016. The Impact of Brand Equity on Patients' Purchasing Behaviors in Private Dental Practice in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Business Administration Research*. 5(2) p.41.
- Ahmed, A. and Ibrahim, M., 2017. Business Value of Facebook: A Multiple Case Study from a Developing Country. *Pacific Asia Journal of the Association for Information Systems*. 8(4).
- Ahmed, A. and Ibrahim, M., 2017. Business Value of Facebook: A Multiple Case Study from a Developing Country. *Pacific Asia Journal of the Association for Information Systems*. 8(4).
- Ahmed, T., 2016. Countering Counterfeit Branding: Implications for Public-Sector Marketing. *Journal of Nonprofit & Public Sector Marketing*. 28(3). pp.273-286.
- Ahmed, Z., Rizwan, M. and Haq, M., 2014. Effect of brand trust and customer satisfaction on brand loyalty in Bahawalpur. *Journal of Sociological Research*. 5(1). pp.306-326.
- Ahn, J. and Back, K. J., 2017. Influence of brand relationship on customer attitude toward integrated resort brands: a cognitive, affective, and conative perspective. *Journal of Travel & ToYang*, H.L. and Wu, W.P., 2016. The Effects of Consumers' Belief regarding Internet Rumors on Purchases Intention from Different Spreading Channels. *Tourism Marketing*. pp.1-12.
- Alavi, S., Wieseke, J. and Guba, J.H., 2016. Saving on Discounts through Accurate Sensing—Salespeople's Estimations of Customer Price Importance and Their Effects on Negotiation Success. *Journal of Retailing*, 92(1), pp.40-55.
- Aldhmour, F. and Sarayrah, I., 2016. AN INVESTIGATION OF FACTORS INFLUENCING CONSUMERS INTENTION TO USE ONLINE SHOPPING: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY IN SOUTH OF JORDAN. *The Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce*. 21(2).
- Al-Dmour, H., Zu'bi, M. F. and Kakeesh, D., 2013. The effect of services marketing mix elements on customer-based brand equity: An empirical study on mobile telecom service recipients in Jordan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 8(11), p.13.
- Almeida, S. O. D., Mazzon, J. A. and Müller Neto, H., 2013. Participant diversity and expressive freedom in firm-managed and customer-managed brand communities. *BAR-Brazilian Administration Review*, 10(2), pp.195-218.
- Alves, H., Fernandes, C. and Raposo, M., 2016. Value co-creation: Concept and contexts of application and study. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(5), pp.1626-1633.
- Alwi, S. F. S. and Kitchen, P. J., 2014. Projecting corporate brand image and behavioural response in business schools: Cognitive or affective brand attributes? *Journal of Business Research*, 67(11), pp.2324-2336.
- Alwi, S.F.S., Ali, S.M. and Nguyen, B., 2017. The importance of ethics in branding: Mediating effects of ethical branding on company reputation and brand loyalty. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 27(3), pp.393-422.

- Amatulli, C. and et al.,2017. Inside Luxury: Main Features, Evolving Trends, and Marketing Paradoxes. In *Sustainable Luxury Brands* (pp. 7-34). Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- Ambrose, G. and Harris, P., 2017. *Packaging the brand: the relationship between packaging design and brand identity*. Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Andaleeb, S. S., 2016. Services Marketing. In *Strategic Marketing Management in Asia: Case Studies and Lessons across Industries* (pp. 351-382). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Angelopoulos, G., 2017. A COMPETITIVE ASSESSMENT OF SOUTH AFRICA'S LEADING CITIES--NATIONAL, CONTINENTAL AND GLOBAL PERSPECTIVES. *Strategic Review for Southern Africa*. 39(1). pp.65-92.
- Anselmsson, J., Vestman Bondesson, N. and Johansson, U., 2014. Brand image and customers' willingness to pay a price premium for food brands. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 23(2). pp.90-102.
- Apostolakis, A., Jaffry, S. and Cox, A., 2015. The role of uniqueness in destination branding: the case of historical Portsmouth harbour. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 10(2), pp.198-213.
- Armstrong, G., Adam, S. and Kotler, P., 2014. *Principles of marketing*. Pearson Australia.
- Ashraf, A.R., Thongpapanl, N.T. and Northey, G., 2016, October. The role of m-commerce readiness in emerging and developed markets. American Marketing Association.
- Avraham, E. and Ketter, E., 2016. Marketing and Destination Branding. In *Tourism Marketing for Developing Countries* (pp. 39-66). Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- Ayob, S. F., Low, S. T. and Abdul Jalil, R., 2017. Key determinants of waste separation intention: empirical application of TPB. *Facilities* (just-accepted). pp.00-00.
- Badrinarayanan, V. A., Sierra, J. J. and Taute, H.A., 2014. Determinants and outcomes of online brand tribalism: Exploring communities of massively multiplayer online role-playing games (MMORPGs). *Psychology & Marketing*, 31(10), pp.853-870.
- Balakrishnan, M.S, Nekhili, R. and Lewis, C., 2011. Destination brand components. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*. 5(1). pp.4-25.
- Barnes, S., 2016. Understanding Virtual Reality in Marketing: Nature, Implications and Potential.
- Barreda, A. A. et al.,2016. Online branding: Development of hotel branding through interactivity theory. *Tourism Management*. 57. pp.180-192.
- Barreda, A. A., Bilgihan, A. and Okumus, F., 2015. Generating brand awareness in online social networks. *Computers in human behaviour*, 50, pp.600-609.
- Baumeister, C., Scherer, A. and Wangenheim, F. V., 2015. Branding access offers the importance of product brands, ownership status, and spillover effects to parent brands. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(5), pp.574-588.
- Bayat, A., 2017. City Branding and the Way It Is Perceived in People's Mind, a Case Study of Milad Tower in Iran. In *Advances in Human Factors, Business Management, Training and Education* (pp. 601-607). Springer International Publishing.
- Behe, B. K., Huddleston, P. and Sage, L., 2016. Age cohort influences brand recognition, awareness, and likelihood to buy vegetable and herb transplants. *HortScience*. 51(2). pp.145-151.
- Bell, F. and Bell, F., 2016. Looking beyond place branding: the emergence of place reputation. *Journal of Place Management and Development*. 9(3). pp.247-254.
- Bennett, D. R., Graham, C. and Clemente, M., 2017, May. What long-term measures can tell us about brand loyalty? In *Abstracts in Conference proceedings*.

- Ben-Shaul, M. and Reichel, A., 2017. Motives, Modes of Participation, and Loyalty Intentions of Facebook Tourism Brand Page Consumers. *Journal of Travel Research*, p.0047287517704087.
- Beristain, J.J. and Zorrilla, P., 2011. The relationship between store image and store brand equity: A conceptual framework and evidence from hypermarkets. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. 18(6). pp.562-574.
- Beverland, M. B., Wilner, S. J. and Micheli, P., 2015. Reconciling the tension between consistency and relevance: design thinking as a mechanism for brand ambidexterity. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(5), pp.589-609.
- Biedenbach, G., Bengtsson, M. and Marell, A., 2015. Brand equity, satisfaction, and switching costs: An examination of effects in the business-to-business setting. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*. 33(2). pp.164-178.
- Biedenbach, G., Bengtsson, M. and Marell, A., 2015. Brand equity, satisfaction, and switching costs: An examination of effects in the business-to-business setting. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 33(2), pp.164-178.
- Biedenbach, G., Biedenbach, G., Manzhynski, S. and Manzhynski, S., 2016. Internal branding and sustainability: investigating perceptions of employees. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 25(3), pp.296-306.
- Bijmolt, T.H., Krafft, M. and Viswanathan, V., 2018. Multi-tier Loyalty Programmes to Stimulate Customer Engagement. In *Customer Engagement Marketing* (pp. 119-139). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Bilgihan, A., 2016. Gen Y customer loyalty in online shopping: An integrated model of trust, user experience and branding. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 61. pp.103-113.
- Biscaia, R., Correia, A. and Maroco, J., 2013. Spectator-based brand equity in professional soccer. *Sport Marketing Quarterly*. 22(1). p.20.
- Biscaia, R., Ross, S. and Marôco, J., 2016. Investigating the role of fan club membership on perceptions of team brand equity in football. *Sport Management Review*, 19(2), pp.157-170.
- Booth, N. and Matic, J.A., 2011. Mapping and leveraging influencers in social media to shape corporate brand perceptions. *Corporate Communications: An International Journal*. 16(3). pp.184-191.
- Boukis, A. and Gounaris, S., 2014. Linking IMO with employees' fit with their environment and reciprocal behaviours towards the firm. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 28(1), pp.10-21.
- Braimah, M. and Tweneboah-Koduah, E.Y., 2011. An exploratory study of the impact of green brand awareness on consumer purchase decisions in Ghana. *Journal of Marketing Development and Competitiveness*. 5(7). p.11.
- Brems, C., Temmerman, M., Graham, T. and Broersma, M., 2017. Personal Branding on Twitter: How employed and freelance journalists stage themselves on social media. *Digital Journalism*. 5(4). pp.443-459.
- Bruegelmans, E., Bijmolt, T. H. and Wunderlich, N.V., 2015. Advancing research on loyalty programmes: a future research agenda. *Marketing Letters*, 26(2), pp.127-139.
- Brodie, R. J. and et al., 2016. Country of origin branding: an integrative perspective. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 25(4). pp.322-336.
- Bruhn, M., Schoenmueller, V. and Schäfer, D.B., 2012. Are social media replacing traditional media in terms of brand equity creation?. *Management Research Review*. 35(9). pp.770-790.

- Bues, M., Steiner, M. and Krafft, M., 2017. How Mobile In-Store Advertising Influences Purchase Intention: Value Drivers and Mediating Effects from a Consumer Perspective. *Psychology & Marketing*. 34(2). pp.157-174.
- Buil, I., De Chernatony, L. and Martínez, E., 2013. Examining the role of advertising and sales promotions in brand equity creation. *Journal of Business Research*. 66(1). pp.115-122.
- Buil, I., Martínez, E. and de Chernatony, L., 2013. The influence of brand equity on consumer responses. *Journal of consumer marketing*. 30(1). pp.62-74.
- Burmann, C. and et al., 2017. *Identity-Based Brand Management: Fundamentals—Strategy—Implementation—Controlling*. Springer.
- Butnariu, A., 2017. Ingredient Branding-A Growth Opportunity?. *SEA-Practical Application of Scienc* Williams Jr, R.L. and Williams, H.A., 2017. The Marketing Differentiation Process. In *Vintage Marketing Differentiation* (pp. 5-18). Palgrave Macmillan US.e, (13), pp.101-107.
- Butt, M. M. and et al., 2017. Integrating Behavioural and Branding Perspectives to Maximize Green Brand Equity: A Holistic Approach. *Business Strategy and the Environment*. 26(4). pp.507-520.
- Calvo Porral, C., Martínez Fernández, V. A. and Lévy Mangín, J.P., 2015. Measuring the influence of customer-based store brand equity in the purchase intention. *Cuadernos de Gestión*, 15(1).
- Calvo-Porral, C. and Lévy-Mangin, J. P., 2014. Private label brands: a major perspective of two customer-based brand equity models. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 24(4), pp.431-452.
- Calvo-Porral, C., Martínez-Fernández, V. A. and Lévy-Mangín, J.P., 2013. What matters to store Brand Equity? An approach to Spanish large retailing in a downturn context. *Investigaciones Europeas de Dirección y Economía de la Empresa*, 19(3), pp.136-146.
- Candelo, E., Casalegno, C. and Civera, C., 2014. Meanings and implications of corporate social responsibility and branding in grocer retailers: A comparative study over Italy and the UK. *Handbook of Research on Retailer-Consumer Relationship Development*, p.351.
- Cannon, H. M., Cannon, J. N. and Andrews, C. R., 2014. Modelling cascading demand: Accounting for the effects of captive consumer relationships. *Developments in Business Simulation and Experiential Learning*, 37.
- Carter, M., Wright, R. and Klein, R., 2014. Understanding online customers' ties to merchants: the moderating influence of trust on the relationship between switching costs and e-loyalty. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 23(2), pp.185-204.
- Cassidy, R. and Wymer, W., 2015. The impact of brand strength on satisfaction, loyalty and WOM: An empirical examination in the higher education sector. *Journal of Brand Management*. 22(2). pp.117-135.
- Cassidy, R., 2013. The role of brand orientation in the higher education sector: a student-perceived paradigm. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 25(5), pp.803-820.
- Cerreta, M. and Daldanise, G., 2017, July. Community Branding (Co-Bra): A Collaborative Decision Making Process for Urban Regeneration. In *International Conference on Computational Science and Its Applications* (pp. 730-746). Springer, Cham.
- Chae, H., Ko, E. and Han, J., 2015. How do customers' SNS participation activities impact customer equity drivers and customer loyalty? Focus on the SNS services of a global SPA brand. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science*, 25(2), pp.122-141.

- Chahal, H. and Rani, A., 2017. How trust moderates social media engagement and brand equity. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, (just-accepted). pp.00-00.
- Chan, K., Leung Ng, Y. and Luk, E. K., 2013. Impact of celebrity endorsement in advertising on brand image among Chinese adolescents. *Young Consumers*. 14(2). pp.167-179.
- Chan, T. K., Zheng, X. and Lee, Z. W., 2014. Antecedents and consequences of customer engagement in online brand communities. *Journal of marketing analytics*, 2(2), pp.81-97.
- Chandrashekar, M. S. and et al., 2017. Teaching Note: Case 10: Irrway—A Green Personal Mobility Solution. *An Instructor's Manual for Strategic Marketing Cases in Emerging Markets* (pp. 79-84). Springer International Publishing.
- Chang, A., Chiang, H. H. and Han, T. S., 2015. Investigating the dual-route effects of corporate branding on brand equity. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 20(3), pp.120-129.
- Chang, C. H. and Chen, Y. S., 2014. Managing green brand equity: the perspective of perceived risk theory. *Quality & Quantity*. 48(3). pp.1753-1768.
- Chang, C. H. and Chen, Y. S., 2014. Managing green brand equity: the perspective of perceived risk theory. *Quality & Quantity*. 48(3). pp.1753-1768.
- Chang, C. H. and Chen, Y. S., 2014. Managing green brand equity: the perspective of perceived risk theory. *Quality & Quantity*, 48(3), pp.1753-1768.
- Chang, C.H. and Chen, Y.S., 2014. Managing green brand equity: the perspective of perceived risk theory. *Quality & Quantity*. 48(3). pp.1753-1768.
- Chang, E. C., 2014. Influences of the spokes-character on brand equity antecedents. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 26(3), pp.494-515.
- Chang, F. C., Lee, T. R. and Yen, S.W., 2015. Demand creating service: A hybrid model for identifying key selection criteria and service strategies of international express suppliers. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 27(3), pp.467-585.
- Chang, K. C., Kuo, N. T. and Cheng, Y. S., 2014. The impact of website quality and perceived trust on customer purchase intention in the hotel sector: website brand and perceived value as moderators. *International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*. 5(4). pp.255.
- Chang, K. C., Kuo, N. T. and Cheng, Y.S., 2014. The impact of website quality and perceived trust on customer purchase intention in the hotel sector: website brand and perceived value as moderators—*International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology*, 5(4), p.255.
- Chang, T.Y., 2017. Action Research of Importing Digital Service into Local Brand Marketing—The Workshop Practice. In *Advances in Affective and Pleasurable Design* (pp. 269-280). Springer International Publishing.
- Ganguli, S. and Ebrahim, A.H., 2017. Tourism Management Perspectives. *Tourism Management*, 21, pp.74-84.
- Chen, J. L., 2015. The impact of bed and breakfast atmosphere, customer experience, and customer value on voluntary customer performance: A survey in Taiwan. *Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research*, 20(5), pp.541-562.
- Chen, J. V., Yen, D. C. and Capistrano, E.P.S., 2016. The antecedents of purchase and re-purchase intentions of online auction consumers. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 54, pp.186-196.
- Chen, K. and et al., 2017. Effective strategies for developing meaningful names and associations for co-branded products in new and emerging markets. *Journal of Brand Management*. 24 (4). pp.362-374.

- Chen, S. C., 2015. Customer value and customer loyalty: Is competition a missing link? *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 22, pp.107-116.
- Chen, Y. S., Lin, C. L. and Chang, C. H., 2014. The influence of greenwash on green word-of-mouth (green WOM): the mediation effects of green perceived quality and green satisfaction. *Quality & Quantity*, 48(5), pp.2411-2425.
- Cheung, C. M., Zheng, X. and Lee, M. K., 2014, January. Customer loyalty to C2C online shopping platforms: An exploration of the role of customer engagement. In *System Sciences (HICSS), 2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on* (pp. 3065-3072). IEEE.
- Chhabra, D., 2017. Heritage branding of India: A Gandhi tourism perspective. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 62, pp.110-112.
- Chiambaretto, P. and Gurău, C., 2017. David by Goliath: what is co-branding and what is in it for SMEs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*. 31(1). pp.103-122.
- Chiambaretto, P. and Gurău, C., 2017. David by Goliath: what is co-branding and what is in it for SMEs. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*. 31(1). pp.103-122.
- Chiambaretto, P., Gurău, C. and Le Roy, F., 2016. Competitive branding: Definition, typology, benefits and risks. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 57, pp.86-96.
- Chiaravalle, B. and Schenck, B. F., 2014. *Branding for dummies*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Choi, E., Ko, E. and Kim, A. J., 2016. Explaining and predicting purchase intentions following luxury-fashion brand value co-creation encounters. *Journal of Business Research*. 69(12). pp.5827-5832.
- Choi, M. W., 2015. A study on the branded content as marketing communication media in the viewpoint of relational perspective. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 8(S5), pp.116-123.
- Chouliarakis, L., 2017. Suffering and the Ethics of Solidarity. In *Alleviating World Suffering* (pp. 49-60). Springer International Publishing.
- Chow, W.S. and Shi, S., 2015. Investigating customers' satisfaction with brand pages in social networking sites. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*. 55(2). pp.48-58.
- Clark, M. and et al., 2017. Brand community integration and satisfaction with social media sites: a comparative study. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*. 11(1). pp.39-55.
- Claudiu-Catalin, M., Dorian-Laurentiu, F. and Andreea, P., 2014. The effects of faulty or potentially harmful products on brand reputation and social responsibility of business. *Amfiteatru Economic*, 16(35), p.58.
- Cleary, J. and van Caenegem, W., 2017. Mitigating 'One-Size-Fits-All' Approaches to Australian Agriculture: Is There a Case to Be Made for Geographical Indications?. In *The Importance of Place: Geographical Indications as a Tool for Local and Regional Development* (pp. 111-145). Springer International Publishing.
- Cleave, E. and et al., 2016. Place Marketing, Place Branding, and Social Media: Perspectives of Municipal Practitioners. *Growth and Change*.
- Close, A. G., Lacey, R. and Cornwell, T. B., 2015. Visual processing and need for cognition can enhance event-sponsorship outcomes. *Journal of Advertising Research*, 55(2), pp.206-215.
- Clow, K.E. and Baack, D., 2010. *Integrated Advertising, Promotion, and Marketing Communications. 4th Global Edition*. New Jersey, USA: Pearson Education, Inc.

- Coleman, D. A., de Chernatony, L. and Christodoulides, G., 2015. B2B service brand identity and brand performance: an empirical investigation in the UK's B2B IT services sector. *European Journal of Marketing*, 49(7/8), pp.1139-1162.
- Cossío-Silva, F. J., Revilla-Camacho, M. Á. and Palacios-Florencio, B., 2016. Value co-creation and customer loyalty. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(5), pp.1621-1625.
- Crewe, L. and Martin, A., 2017. Sex and the city: Branding, gender and the commodification of sex consumption in contemporary retailing. *Urban Studies*, 54(3), pp.582-599.
- Cvijikj, I. P. and Michahelles, F., 2013. Online engagement factors on Facebook brand pages. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 3(4), pp.843-861.
- Danish, R. Q., Latif, Y. and Ahmad, Z., 2016. Impact of Advertisement on Customer Satisfaction in Telecom Sector of Pakistan. *Journal of Statistics*, 23(1).
- Daou, A., Karuranga, E. and Su, Z., 2014. Towards a better understanding of intellectual capital in Mexican SMEs. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 15(2), pp.316-332.
- DaSilva, C. M. and Trkman, P., 2014. Business model: what it is and what it is not. *Long range planning*, 47(6), pp.379-389.
- Davies, K. and Freathy, P., 2014. Marketplace spirituality: challenges for the New Age retailer. *The Service Industries Journal*, 34(15), pp.1185-1198.
- De Kerviler, G., Demoulin, N. T. and Zidda, P., 2016. Adoption of in-store mobile payment: Are perceived risk and convenience the only drivers?. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 31, pp.334-344.
- de Noronha, I., Coca-Stefaniak, J.A. and Morrison, A.M., 2017. Confused branding? An exploratory study of place branding practices among place management professionals. *Cities*, 66, pp.91-98.
- de Oliveira, E. R. and Rodrigues, P., 2015. The importance of corporate social responsibility in the brand image—The “Nespresso” case study. *International Journal of Engineering and Industrial Management*, (4), pp.77-87.
- Degaris, L., Kwak, D. H. and McDaniel, S. R., 2017. Modelling the Effects of Sponsorship-Linked Marketing: When Does Memory Matter?. *Journal of Promotion Management*, 23(2), pp.320-339.
- Desai, D. R., Lianos, I. and Waller, S. W. eds., 2015. *Brands, competition law and IP*. Cambridge University Press.
- Desmet, P., 2014. How retailer money-back guarantees influence consumer preferences for retailer versus national brands. *Journal of Business Research*, 67(9), pp.1971-1978.
- Di Benedetto, C. A. and Kim, K. H., 2016. Customer equity and value management of global brands: Bridging theory and practice from financial and marketing perspectives: Introduction to a Journal of Business Research Special Section. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(9), pp.3721-3724.
- Diallo, M. F. and Siqueira, J. R., 2017. How previous positive experiences with store brands affect purchase intention in emerging countries: a comparison between Brazil and Colombia. *International Marketing Review*, (just-accepted), pp.00-00.
- DiMartino, C. and Jessen, S.B., 2016. School brand management: The policies, practices, and perceptions of branding and marketing in New York City's public high schools. *Urban Education*, 51(5), pp.447-475.
- Dixon, A. W., Martinez, J. M. and Martin, C. L., 2015. Employing social media as a marketing strategy in college sport: examining perceived effectiveness in accomplishing organisational objectives. *International Review on Public and Nonprofit Marketing*, 12(2), pp.97-113.

- Dolbec, P.Y. and Chebat, J.C., 2013. The impact of a flagship vs. a brand store on brand attitude, brand attachment and brand equity. *Journal of Retailing*. 89(4). pp.460-466.
- Dragin-Jensen, C., Schnittka, O. and Arkil, C., 2016. More options do not always create perceived variety in life: Attracting new residents with quality-vs. quantity-oriented event portfolios. *Cities*. 56. pp.55-62.
- Duma, F., Willi, C.H., Nguyen, B. and Melewar, T.C., 2016. The management of luxury brand behaviour: Adapting luxury brand management to the changing market forces of the 21st Century. *The Marketing Review*, 16(1), pp.3-25.
- Dutta, N. and Bhat, A., 2016. Exploring the effect of store characteristics and interpersonal trust on purchase intention in the context of online social media marketing. *Journal of Internet Commerce*. 15(3). pp.239-273.
- East, R., Singh, J. and Vanhuele, M., 2016. *Consumer behaviour: applications in marketing*. Sage.
- Easterby-Smith, M., Thorpe, R. and Jackson, P. R., 2008. *Management research*. London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Echambadi, R., Jindal, R. P. and Blair, E. A., 2013. Evaluating and managing brand repurchase across multiple geographic retail markets. *Journal of Retailing*, 89(4), pp.409-422.
- Eide, T. T., Hargreaves, P. and Cunningham, L.A., 2016. *Quality investing: Owning the best companies for the long-term*. Harriman House Limited.
- Eismann, T. T. and et al., 2017. Untangling social media excellence: five typical patterns of super successful posts.
- Elbedweihy, A. M. and Jayawardhena, C., 2014. Consumer-brand identification: A social identity-based review and research directions. *The marketing review*, 14(2), pp.205-228.
- Elliot, S. and et al., 2016. Measuring dimensions of brand influence for tourism products and places. *International Journal of Culture, Tourism and Hospitality Research*. 10(4). pp.396-409.
- Ene, S. and Ozkaya, B., 2014. A study on corporate image, customer satisfaction and brand loyalty in the context of retail stores. *Asian Social Science*. 10(14). p.52.
- Esch, F.R., Langner, T., Schmitt, B.H. and Geus, P., 2006. Are brands forever? How brand knowledge and relationships affect current and future purchases. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 15(2). pp.98-105.
- Ewing, A., 2017. *Qualitative Content Analysis of Social Media as Marketing Endeavor for Small to Mid-Sized Non-profit Organisations* (Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University).
- Faqih, K.M., 2016. An empirical analysis of factors predicting the behavioral intention to adopt Internet shopping technology among non-shoppers in a developing country context: Does gender matter?. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. 30. pp.140-164.
- Farsky, M., Schnittka, O. and Lorth, C., 2017. Brand-anchored discrete choice experiment (BDCE) vs. direct attribute rating (DAR): An empirical comparison of predictive validity. *Marketing Letters*. 28(2). pp.231-240.
- Faryabi, M., Sadeghzadeh, K. and Zakeri, A., 2015. The Relationship Continuity Model and Customer Loyalty in the Banking Industry: A Case Study of the Maskan Bank of Iran. *Journal of Relationship Marketing*, 14(1), pp.37-52.
- Fatema, M., Azad, M. A .K. and Masum, A. K. M., 2015. Impact of Brand Image and Brand Loyalty in Measuring Brand Equity of Islami Bank Bangladesh Ltd. *Asian Business Review*. 2(1). pp.42-46.

- Ferreira, V.L., da Veiga, C.R.P. and da Veiga, C.P., 2017. Generic drugs in times of economic crisis: Are there changes in consumer purchase intention?. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. 37. pp.1-7.
- Fleury, F. A., Cardoso, M. V. and Marques, R., 2014. The Impact of the Stadium in the Supporter's Consumption: How Does the Frequency at The Stadium Boosts the Demand for the Clubs'. *Future Studies Research Journal: Trends and Strategies*, 6(2), pp.126-156.
- Folgado-Fernández, J. A., Hernández-Mogollón, J. M. and Duarte, P., 2017. Brand-anchored discrete choice experiment (BDCE) vs. direct attribute rating (DAR): An empirical comparison of predictive validity. *Marketing Letters*. 28(2). pp.231-240.
- Folgado-Fernández, J. A., Hernández-Mogollón, J. M. and Duarte, P., 2017. Destination image and loyalty development: the impact of tourists' food experiences at gastronomic events. *Scandinavian Journal of Hospitality and Tourism*, 17(1), pp.92-110.
- Frank, B., Enkawa, T. and Schvaneveldt, S. J., 2014. How do the success factors driving repurchase intend differ between male and female customers? *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 42(2), pp.171-185.
- Franklin, M., 2012. *Understanding Research: Coping with the quantitative - Qualitative Divide*. Routledge.
- Sanjaya, B. (2013). *Pengaruh Brand Awareness Dan Brand Association Terhadap Brand Loyalty Melalui Perceived Quality Pada Sepatu Merk Nike Di Surabaya*. *Jurnal Ilmu Manajemen*, 2(1), 1-7.
- Fujiwara, K. and Nagasawa, S. Y., 2015. Relationship between Purchase Intentions for Luxury Brands and Customer Experience: Comparative Verification among Product Categories and Brand Ranks. *Science Journal of Business and Management*, 3, pp.1-10.
- Funamori, M. and Mori, M., 2016, July. Conceptual Design toward a Visualization System of University's Web Presence: Simple Analysis and System Development Using Twitter. In *Advanced Applied Informatics (IIAI-AAI), 2016 5th IIAI International Congress on* (pp. 456-461). IEEE.
- Gad, T., 2016. *Customer Experience Branding: Driving Engagement Through Surprise and Innovation*. Kogan Page Publishers.
- Gallucci, C., Santulli, R. and Calabrò, A., 2015. Does family involvement foster or hinder firm performance? The missing role of family-based branding strategies. *Journal of Family Business Strategy*. 6(3). pp.155-165.
- Gao, S., Smits, M. and Wang, C., 2016. A conjoint analysis of corporate preferences for the sectoral crediting mechanism: a case study of Shanxi Province in China. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 131. pp.259-269.
- Gartner, W.C. and Ruzzier, M.K., 2011. Tourism destination brand equity dimensions: Renewal versus repeat market. *Journal of Travel Research*. 50(5). pp.471-481.
- Gatrell, J., Reid, N. and Steiger, T.L., 2017. Branding spaces: Place, region, sustainability and the American craft beer industry. *Applied Geography*.
- Gerber, L. and Sriramesh, K., 2016. Corporate social responsibility in the Swiss watch industry: perceptions and practices. *Revista Organicom*. 13(24).
- Geurin, A. N. and Burch, L. M., 2017. User-generated branding via social media: An examination of six running brands. *Sport Management Review*. 20(3). pp.273-284.

- Ghose, S., Heiman, A. and Lowengart, O., 2017. Isolating strategy effectiveness of brands in an emerging market: A choice modelling approach. *Journal of Brand Management*, 24(2), pp.161-177.
- Giordano, M.C., Manuti, A. and de Palma, P.D., 2016. Human Capital Reloaded: The Use of Social Media in Human Resource Management. In *The Social Organisation: Managing Human Capital through Social Media* (pp. 1-13). Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- Giovanis, A., Athanasopoulou, P. and Tsoukatos, E., 2015. The role of service fairness in the service quality–relationship quality–customer loyalty chain: An empirical study. *Journal of Service Theory and Practice*, 25(6), pp.744-776.
- Glynn, M. S. and Widjaja, T., 2015. Private label personality: applying brand personality to private label brands. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 25(4), pp.362-378.
- Godey, B. and et al., 2016. Social media marketing efforts of luxury brands: Influence on brand equity and consumer behavior. *Journal of business research*. 69(12). pp.5833-5841.
- Godey, B., Manthiou, A. and Singh, R., 2016. Social media marketing efforts of luxury brands: Influence on brand equity and consumer behavior. *Journal of business research*. 69(12). pp.5833-5841.
- Goodwin, A. and et al., 2017. Leveraging Charity Sport Events to Develop a Connection to a Cause. *Event Management*. 21(2). pp.175-184.
- Gough, D., 2017. Re-Contextualized Carnivals: A Brazilian Art Form in the Global Spaces of Festivalization. *ASAP/Journal*, 2(1), pp.199-219.
- Govers, R. and Go, F., 2016. *Place branding: Glocal, virtual and physical identities, constructed, imagined and experienced*. Springer.
- Goyal, E. and Srivastava, S., 2015. Study on Customer Engagement Model-Banking Sector. *SIES Journal of Management*, 11(1).
- Grainer, M., Noble, C. H. and Broetzmann, S. M., 2014. What unhappy customers want. *MIT Sloan Management Review*. 55(3). pp.31.
- Green, M. R., 2016. The impact of social networks in the development of a personal sports brand. *Sport, Business and Management: An International Journal*. 6(3). pp.274-294.
- Griff Round, D.J. and Roper, S., 2012. Exploring consumer brand name equity: Gaining insight through the investigation of response to name change. *European Journal of Marketing*. 46(7/8). pp.938-951.
- Grimmer, M. and Grube, D. C., 2016. Political branding: A consumer perspective on Australian political parties. *Party Politics*. pp.1354068817710585.
- Grube, D. C. and Grimmer, M., 2017. Political branding: A consumer perspective on Australian political parties.
- Gu, Z., Wei, J. and Xu, F., 2016. An Empirical Study on Factors Influencing Consumers' Initial Trust in Wearable Commerce. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*. 56(1). pp.79-85.
- Gürhan-Canli, Z., Hayran, C. and Sarial-Abi, G., 2016. Customer-based brand equity in a technologically fast-paced, connected, and constrained environment. *AMS review*, 6(1-2), pp.23-32.
- Habibi, M. R., Laroche, M. and Richard, M. O., 2014. The roles of brand community and community engagement in building brand trust on social media. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 37, pp.152-161.
- Hafeez, K. and et al., 2016. The role of place branding and image in the development of sectoral clusters: The case of Dubai. *Journal of Brand Management*. 23(4). pp.383-402.

- Hafeez, K., Foroudi, P., Dinnie, K., Nguyen, B. and Parahoo, S.K., 2016. The role of place branding and image in the development of sectoral clusters: The case of Dubai. *Journal of Brand Management*, 23(4), pp.383-402.
- Hajli, N., Shanmugam, M. and Richard, M.O., 2017. Branding co-creation with members of online brand communities. *Journal of Business Research*. 70. pp.136-144.
- Hakala, U., Svensson, J. and Vincze, Z., 2012. Consumer-based brand equity and top-of-mind awareness: a cross-country analysis. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 21(6). pp.439-451.
- Hall, C.M., 2016. 100% Pure Neoliberalism: Brand New Zealand, New Thinking, New Stories, Inc. *Commercial Nationalism and Tourism: Selling the National Story*, 77, p.105.
- Hamari, J., Alha, K. and Paavilainen, J., 2017. Why do players buy in-game content? An empirical study on concrete purchase motivations. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 68. pp.538-546.
- Han, T. I. and Stoel, L., 2017. Explaining Socially Responsible Consumer Behavior: A Meta-Analytic Review of Theory of Planned Behavior. *Journal of International Consumer Marketing*. 29(2). pp.91-103.
- Hannibal, M. and Rasmussen, E.S., 2017. The Intended Image of a Place Brand: A Danish Case Study. In *Global Place Branding Campaigns across Cities, Regions, and Nations* (pp. 74-93). IGI global.
- Hao, Y., Dong, X.Y. and Ma, Y., 2016. What influences personal purchases of new energy vehicles in China? An empirical study based on a survey of Chinese citizens. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*. 8(6). p.065904.
- Hashemi, S. A. and Mokhtaran, M., 2016. The Effect of Brand Equity Dimensions on Current and Future Purchase Behavior of Customer (An Approach Towards First Familiar Brand). *International Business Management*. 10(17). pp.4037-4041.
- He, H. and et.al.,, 2016. Moral identity centrality and cause-related marketing: the moderating effects of brand social responsibility image and emotional brand attachment. *European Journal of Marketing*. 50(1/2). pp.236-259.
- He, Y. and Lai, K. K., 2014. The effect of corporate social responsibility on brand loyalty: the mediating role of brand image. *Total Quality Management & Business Excellence*, 25(3-4), pp.249-263.
- Heinberg, M., Ozkaya, H. E. and Taube, M., 2016. A brand built on sand: Is acquiring a local brand in an emerging market an ill-advised strategy for foreign companies? *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 44(5), pp.586-607.
- Helm, S. V. and Özergin, B., 2015. Service inside: The impact of ingredient service branding on quality perceptions and behavioral intentions. *Industrial Marketing Management*. 50. pp.142-149.
- Herbig, P. and Milewicz, J., 2012. The relationship of reputation and credibility to brand success. *Pricing Strategy and Practice*.
- Herstein, R., Herstein, R., Drori, N., Drori, N., Berger, R., Berger, R., Barnes, B.R. and Barnes, B.R., 2017. Exploring the gap between policy and practice in private branding strategy management in an emerging market. *International Marketing Review*, 34(4), pp.559-578.
- Herzog, M., Lepa, S. and Egermann, H., 2016. Towards automatic music recommendation for audio branding scenarios.
- Hew, J. J., Lee, V. H. and Lin, B., 2016. Mobile social commerce: The booster for brand loyalty?. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 59. pp.142-154.

- Hodge, C., Pederson, J. A. and Walker, M., 2015. How do you “like” my style? Examining how communication style influences Facebook behaviors. *International Journal of Sport Communication*, 8(3), pp.276-292.
- Horner, S., 2016. The Future of Market Segmentation and Relationship Marketing in the Tourism and Hospitality Sectors. *Atna Journal of Tourism Studies*, 1(1), pp.1-14.
- Hsin Chang, H. and Wen Chen, S., 2008. The impact of online store environment cues on purchase intention: Trust and perceived risk as a mediator. *Online information review*. 32(6). pp.818-841.
- Hsu, C. H., 2014. Brand evaluation of foreign versus domestic luxury hotels by Chinese travelers. *Journal of China Tourism Research*, 10(1), pp.35-50.
- Hsu, L. C. and Hsu, L. C., 2017. Investigating community members’ purchase intention on Facebook fan page: From a dualistic perspective of trust relationships. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*. 117(5). pp.766-800.
- Huang, R. and Sarigöllü, E., 2014. How brand awareness relates to market outcome, brand equity, and the marketing mix. In *Fashion Branding and Consumer Behaviors* (pp. 113-132). Springer New York.
- Huang, S. L. and Chang, Y. C., 2017. Factors That Impact Consumers' Intention to Shop on Foreign Online Stores.
- Hult, G. T. M., Morgeson, F. V. and Fornell, C., 2017. Do managers know what their customers think and why? *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 45(1), pp.37-54.
- Hur, W. M., Kang, S. and Kim, M., 2015. The moderating role of Hofstede’s cultural dimensions in the customer-brand relationship in China and India. *Cross Cultural Management*, 22(3), pp.487-508.
- Hur, W. M., Kim, M. and Kim, H., 2014. The role of brand trust in male customers' relationship to luxury brands. *Psychological reports*, 114(2), pp.609-624.
- Hutter, K and et al., 2013. The impact of user interactions in social media on brand awareness and purchase intention: the case of MINI on Facebook. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 22(5/6). pp.342-351.
- Hutter, K., Hautz, J., and Fuller, J., 2013. The impact of user interactions in social media on brand awareness and purchase intention: the case of MINI on Facebook. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 22(5/6). pp.342-351.
- Hwang, J. and Hyun, S. S., 2017. First-class airline travellers’ tendency to seek uniqueness: how does it influence their purchase of expensive tickets?. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*. 34(7). pp.935-947.
- Hwang, J., 2016. Organic food as self-presentation: The role of psychological motivation in older consumers' purchase intention of organic food. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*. 28. pp.281-287.
- Hyun, S. and Kim, W., 2011. Dimensions of brand equity in the chain restaurant industry. *Cornell Hospitality Quarterly*. 52(4). pp.429-437.
- Imanina, N. N., Lu, T. K. and Fadhilah, A.R., 2016, March. A proposed model of factors influencing hydrogen fuel cell vehicle acceptance. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 32, No. 1, p. 012052). IOP Publishing.
- Islam, J. U. and Rahman, Z., 2017. The impact of online brand community characteristics on customer engagement: An application of Stimulus-Organism-Response paradigm. *Telematics and Informatics*. 34(4). pp.96-109.

- Islam, J. U. and Rahman, Z., 2017. The impact of online brand community characteristics on customer engagement: An application of Stimulus-Organism-Response paradigm. *Telematics and Informatics*, 34(4), pp.96-109.
- Jackson, S., 2010. *Research Methods: A Modular Approach*. Cengage Learning.
- Jahn, B. and Kunz, W., 2014. A brand like a friend—The influence of customer engagement with social media brand pages on brand relationships and loyalty intentions. *Social Science Electronic Publishing, Inc.*
- Jaikumar, S. and Sahay, A., 2015. Celebrity endorsements and branding strategies: event study from India. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 24(6). pp.633-645.
- Janssen, C., Vanhamme, J. and Leblanc, S., 2017. Should luxury brands say it out loud? Brand conspicuousness and consumer perceptions of responsible luxury. *Journal of Business Research*.
- Acuti, D., Mazzoli, V., Donvito, R. and Chan, P., 2017, July. ARE FASHION CITIES REALLY FASHION CITIES? AN ANALYSIS ON CITY BRAND ASSOCIATIONS. In *2017 Global Fashion Management Conference at Vienna* (pp. 230-234).
- Jeon, J. O., Jeon, J. O. and Baeck, S., 2016. What drives consumer's responses to brand crisis? The moderating roles of brand associations and brand-customer relationship strength. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 25(6), pp.550-567.
- Jeon, M. M. and et al., 2017. Customers' perceived website service quality and its effects on e-loyalty. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. 29(1). pp.438-457.
- Jiang, H. and Zhang, Y., 2016. An investigation of service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty in China's airline market. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 57, pp.80-88.
- Jin, B. and Cedrola, E. eds., 2017. *Fashion Branding and Communication: Core Strategies of European Luxury Brands*. Springer.
- Jin, H., Park, S. T. and Li, G., 2015. Factors influencing customer participation in mobile SNS: Focusing on Wechat in China. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 8(26).
- Jin, X. and Weber, K., 2013. Developing and testing a model of exhibition brand preference: The exhibitors' perspective. *Tourism Management*, 38, pp.94-104.
- Johnson, B. and Christensen, L., 2008. *Educational research: quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.
- Johnson, N., Asare-Marfo, D. and Birol, E., 2017. Building the case for biofortification: measuring and maximising impact in the HarvestPlus program. *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*. 17(2). pp.12078-12091.
- Jung, J. and et al., 2016. Factors affecting attitudes and behavioural intention towards social networking advertising: a case of Facebook users in South Korea. *International Journal of Advertising*. 35(2). pp.248-265.
- Jung, J. H. and Kim, I. G., 2015. Relationship between brand perception, brand identification, brand emotion and brand loyalty for sports event sponsor company. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*, 8(24), p.1.
- Juntunen, M., Juntunen, J. and Juga, J., 2011. Corporate brand equity and loyalty in B2B markets: A study among logistics service purchasers. *Journal of Brand Management*. 18(4-5). pp.300-311.
- Kalafatis, S. P., 2016. Strategic brand alliances. *The Routledge Companion to Contemporary Brand Management*. pp.120.
- Kanji, P. and Ganesan, M., 2017. Antecedents and consequences of private brand purchase: a systematic review and a conceptual framework. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*. 45(6).

- Kapferer, J., 2012. *The new strategic brand management*. London: Kogan Page.
- Kapferer, J.N., 2012. *The new strategic brand management: Advanced insights and strategic thinking*. Kogan page publishers.
- Kapferer, J.N., 2012. *The new strategic brand management: Advanced insights and strategic thinking*. Kogan page publishers.
- Karjaluoto, H., Mustonen, N. and Ulkuniemi, P., 2015. The role of digital channels in industrial marketing communications. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 30(6), pp.703-710.
- Karunaratna, A.R. and Crouch, R., 2016. Can Country of Origin Branding be a Competitive Advantage for Agri-Products from Emerging Countries?. In *Making a Difference Through Marketing* (pp. 167-183). Springer Singapore.
- Kasemsap, K., 2014. The role of brand loyalty on CRM performance: An innovative framework for smart manufacturing. In *Smart manufacturing innovation and transformation: Interconnection and intelligence* (pp. 252-284). IGI Global.
- Kasemsap, K., 2015. The roles of corporate marketing strategies and brand management in the global retail industry. *Successful technological integration for competitive advantage in retail settings*, pp.310-339.
- Kasemsap, K., 2016. Role of social media in brand promotion: An international marketing perspective. In *Managing public relations and brand image through social media* (pp. 62-88). IGI Global.
- Katiyar, V. and Sain, G. K., 2016. Impact of Social Media Activities on Employer Brand Equity and Intention to Apply. *NMIMS Management Review*. 28.
- Kato, J. and Schoenberg, R., 2014. The impact of post-merger integration on the customer–supplier relationship. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 43(2), pp.335-345.
- Kaufmann, H. R., Kaufmann, H. R. and Manarioti, A., 2016. Exploring behavioural branding, brand love and brand co-creation. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 25(6), pp.516-526.
- Keller, K.L., Parameswaran, M.G. and Jacob, I., 2011. *Strategic brand management: Building, measuring, and managing brand equity*. Pearson Education India.
- Keohane, K., 2014. *Brand and Talent*. Kogan Page Publishers.
- Ketelaar, P. E. and et al., 2017. Disentangling location-based advertising: the effects of location congruency and medium type on consumers' ad attention and brand choice. *International Journal of Advertising*. 36(2). pp.356-367.
- Khan, S. N. and Mohsin, M., 2017. The power of emotional value: Exploring the effects of values on green product consumer choice behavior. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 150. pp.65-74.
- Khasawneh K. and Hasouneh A., 2010. The effect of familiar brand names on consumer behaviour: A Jordanian perspective. *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, 43(1), 34–57.
- Khuong, M. N., Hoa, N. V. A. and Nguyen, T. D., 2016. The Effect of Television Commercials on Customers' Loyalty--A Mediation Analysis of Brand Awareness. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*. 7(2). p.18.
- Khuong, M. N., Hoa, N. V. A. and Nguyen, T. D., 2016. The Effect of Television Commercials on Customers' Loyalty--A Mediation Analysis of Brand Awareness. *International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance*, 7(2), p.18.
- Kiaie, R. H., Safari, M. and Ghanbari, G., 2013. The Meaning and Symbol of Commercial Brand Regarding Consumers, Point of View and Introducing the Ways for Creating the Brand

- Symbol. *Singaporean Journal of Business, Economics and Management Studies*. 1(6). pp.88-94.
- Kim, J. E. and Cho, W. Y., 2014. Effect of Brand Awareness of Coffee shops on Switching Intentions, Purchasing Behavior, and Revisiting Intention. *Journal of the Korean Society of Food Culture*. 29(5). pp.406-414.
- Kim, K. and Ahn, S. J. G., 2017. Rewards that undermine customer loyalty? A motivational approach to loyalty programmes. *Psychology & Marketing*, 34(9), pp.842-852.
- Kim, K. P., Kim, Y. O. and Youn, M. K., 2014. The effects of co-brand marketing mix strategies on customer satisfaction, trust and loyalty for medium and small traders and manufacturers. *E+ M Ekonomie a Management*, (1), p.140.
- Kim, K., Ko, E. and Hoon Kim, K., 2014. Fashion collaboration effects on consumer response and customer equity in global luxury and SPA brand marketing. *Journal of Global Scholars of Marketing Science*, 24(3), pp.350-364.
- Kim, S. and Jun, J., 2016. The impact of event advertising on attitudes and visit intentions. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*. 29.pp.1-8.
- Kim, S. J. and et al., 2016. "Understanding a fury in your words": The effects of posting and viewing electronic negative word-of-mouth on purchase behaviors. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 54. pp.511-521.
- Kladou, S., 2017. The case of Istanbul as a cultural destination brand. *The Routledge Handbook of Consumer Behaviour in Hospitality and Tourism*. pp.326.
- Kleppe, I. A. and Mossberg, L. L., 2015. Company Versus Country Branding: "Same, same but Different". In *Creating and Delivering Value in Marketing* (pp. 53-60). Springer, Cham.
- Klimchuk, M.R. and Krasovec, S.A., 2013. *Packaging design: Successful product branding from concept to shelf*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Knittel, Z., Beurer, K. and Berndt, A., 2016. Brand avoidance among Generation Y consumers. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 19(1), pp.27-43.
- Kondasani, R. K. R. and Panda, R. K., 2015. Customer perceived service quality, satisfaction and loyalty in Indian private healthcare. *International journal of health care quality assurance*, 28(5), pp.452-467.
- Koshki, Nasrin, Hassan Esmailpour, and Abbas Saleh Ardestani. "The Study on the Effects of Environmental Quality, Food and Restaurant Services on Mental Image of the Restaurant, Customer Perceived Value, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Behavioral Intentions: Case Study of Boroujerd's Restaurants". *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review* 3, no. 10 (2014): 261-272.
- Kotler P, and Armstrong G., 2011. *Principles of Marketing. 14th Edition*. Upper Saddle River: Pearson Education Inc.
- Kristal, S. and et al., 2016. Is co-creation really a booster for brand equity? The role of co-creation in observer-based brand equity (OBBE). *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 25(3). pp.247-261.
- Krystallis, A., 2017. The Concept of Authenticity and its Relevance to Consumers: Country and Place Branding in the Context of Food Authenticity. *Food Authentication: Management, Analysis and Regulation*, p.27.
- Kudeshia, C., Sikdar, P. and Mittal, A., 2016. Spreading love through fan page liking: A perspective on small scale entrepreneurs. *Computers in Human Behaviour*. 54. pp.257-270.
- Kujala, J., 2014. Branding as a Tool for CSR. *Empowering Organisations through corporate social responsibility*, p.266.

- Kumar Mishra, M., Kumar Mishra, M. and Das, D., 2016. The relationship between risk aversion, brand trust, brand affect and loyalty: Evidence from the FMCG industry. *Journal of Indian Business Research*, 8(2), pp.78-97.
- Kumar, S. and Kothari, M., 2015. A Study on Consumer Perception Regarding Private Label Branding in India. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 7(10), pp.225-232.
- Kumar, V. and Pansari, A., 2016. Competitive advantage through engagement. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 53(4), pp.497-514.
- Kumar, V., 2013. *Profitable customer engagement: Concept, metrics and strategies*. SAGE Publications India.
- Kuo, Y. F. and Feng, L. H., 2013. Relationships among community interaction characteristics, perceived benefits, community commitment, and oppositional brand loyalty in online brand communities. *International Journal of Information Management*, 33(6), pp.948-962.
- Kurtz, D.L., 2011. *Contemporary Marketing*. 14th edition. Nelson Education, Ltd. Canada.
- Ladkin, A. and Buhalis, D., 2016. Online and social media recruitment: hospitality employer and prospective employee considerations. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(2), pp.327-345.
- Lam, C., Ho, G. K. and Law, R., 2015. How can Asian hotel companies remain internationally competitive? *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 27(5), pp.827-852.
- Laming, C. and Mason, K., 2014. Customer experience—An analysis of the concept and its performance in airline brands. *Research in Transportation Business & Management*, 10, pp.15-25.
- Lang, C. and et al., 2016. Stress management in physical education class: an experiential approach to improve coping skills and reduce stress perceptions in adolescents. *Journal of Teaching in Physical Education*. 35(2). pp.149-158.
- Larkin, Y., 2013. Brand perception, cash flow stability, and financial policy. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 110(1), pp.232-253.
- Larsen, F., 2014. Branding as a Bridge for Commodities Towards a Liberalized Market: A Study in the Electricity Sector. *Journal of Economics & Management*, (15), pp.123-154.
- Larsen, F., 2017. Branding and Related Research Fields. In *Energy Branding*(pp. 11-47). Springer International Publishing.
- Lee, A., Yao, J. and Lambert, C., 2015. *The strategy of global branding and brand equity*. Routledge.
- Lee, D., Moon, J. and Mun, Y.Y., 2015. Antecedents and consequences of mobile phone usability: Linking simplicity and interactivity to satisfaction, trust, and brand loyalty. *Information & Management*. 52(3). pp.295-304.
- Lee, J. H. and Park, C. I., 2014. A Study on the Influence of Brand Identity Expressional Elements and Brand Awareness in Cosmetic Road Shop's Facade-Focusing on Designs of Facades of Cosmetic Road Shops in Myeongdong. *Korean Institute of Interior Design Journal*. 23(2). pp.40-50.
- Lee, S., Oh, H. and Hsu, C.H., 2017. Country-of-operation and brand images: evidence from the Chinese hotel industry. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(7).
- Lee, S., Oh, H. and Hsu, C.H., 2017. Country-of-operation and brand images: evidence from the Chinese hotel industry. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 29(7).

- Leek, S. and Christodoulides, G., 2011. A literature review and future agenda for B2B branding: Challenges of branding in a B2B context. *Industrial Marketing Management*. 40(6). pp.830-837.
- Leekha Chhabra, N. and Sharma, S., 2014. Employer branding: strategy for improving employer attractiveness. *International Journal of Organisational Analysis*. 22(1). pp.48-60.
- Leekha Chhabra, N. and Sharma, S., 2014. Employer branding: strategy for improving employer attractiveness. *International Journal of Organisational Analysis*, 22(1), pp.48-60.
- Leyshon, A., Thrift, N. and Webb, P., 2016. Leveraging affect: Mobilizing enthusiasm and the co-production of the musical economy. *The Production and Consumption of Music in the Digital Age*, pp.248-262.
- Liao, Y. K., Wu and Lin Ju, T., 2017. Cognitive, experiential, and marketing factors mediate the effect of brand personality on brand equity. *Social Behavior and Personality: an international journal*. 45(1). pp.1-18.
- Liat, C. B., Mansori, S. and Huei, C. T., 2014. The associations between service quality, corporate image, customer satisfaction, and loyalty: Evidence from the Malaysian hotel industry. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 23(3), pp.314-326.
- Lin, Y. C., 2013. Evaluation of co-branded hotels in the Taiwanese market: the role of brand familiarity and brand fit. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 25(3), pp.346-364.
- Lin, Z. and Bennett, D., 2014. Examining retail customer experience and the moderation effect of loyalty programmes. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 42(10), pp.929-947.
- Lin, Z. and He, X., 2015. The images of foreign versus domestic retailer brands in China: A model of corporate brand image and store image. *Journal of Brand Management*, 22(3), pp.211-228.
- Liu, C. M., Huang, C. J. and Chen, M. L., 2014. Relational benefits, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty in chain store restaurants. *International Journal of Organisational Innovation (Online)*, 7(1), p.46.
- Lu, L. and Gursoy, D., 2017. Would Consumers Pay More for Nongenetically Modified Menu Items? An Examination of Factors Influencing Diners' Behavioral Intentions. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*. 26(3). pp.215-237.
- Lu, L. C., Chang, W. P. and Chang, H.H., 2014. Consumer attitudes toward blogger's sponsored recommendations and purchase intention: The effect of sponsorship type, product type, and brand awareness. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 34. pp.258-266.
- Luis Méndez, J., Oubiña, J. and Rubio, N., 2011. The relative importance of brand-packaging, price and taste in affecting brand preferences. *British Food Journal*. 113(10). pp.1229-1251.
- Lumsdon, L., 2016. *Marketing for tourism*. Springer.
- M. Bizri, R., 2014. A study of Islamic banks in the non-GCC MENA region: evidence from Lebanon. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 32(2), pp.130-149.
- MA, D. and LIU, N., 2016. Study on City Tourism Branding: A Strategic View. In *Eastern academic forum*. Available via <http://www.seiofbluemountain.com/upload/product/201307/2013gjyx303a8.pdf> (Vol. 10, No. 09).
- MacGillavry, K. and Wilson, A., 2014. Delivering loyalty via customer experience management at DHL Freight. *Global Business and Organisational Excellence*, 33(6), pp.6-20.
- Magatef, S. G. and Tomalieh, E. F., 2015. The impact of customer loyalty programmes on customer retention. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 6(8), pp.78-93.

- Malär, L. and et. al., 2011. Emotional brand attachment and brand personality: The relative importance of the actual and the ideal self. *Journal of Marketing*. 75(4). pp.35-52.
- Malhotra, A. and Kubowicz Malhotra, C., 2013. Exploring switching behaviour of US mobile service customers. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 27(1), pp.13-24.
- Malone, C. and Fiske, S. T., 2013. *The human brand: How we relate to people, products, and companies*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Mann, B. and Kaur, M., 2013. Exploring branding strategies of FMCG, services and durables brands: evidence from India. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*. 22(1). pp.6-17.
- Marland, A., Lewis, J.P. and Flanagan, T., 2017. Governance in the age of digital media and branding. *Governance*, 30(1), pp.125-141.
- Marlow, C., 2010. *Research Methods for Generalist Social Work*. 5th ed. Cengage Learning.
- Marticotte, F., Marticotte, F. and Baudry, D., 2016. The impact of brand evangelism on oppositional referrals towards a rival brand. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 25(6), pp.538-549.
- Martin, B. A. and Strong, C. A., 2016. The trustworthy brand: effects of conclusion explicitness and persuasion awareness on consumer judgments. *Marketing Letters*. 27(3). pp.473-485.
- Martinelli, E., Belli, A. and Marchi, G., 2015. The role of customer loyalty as a brand extension purchase predictor. *The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research*, 25(2), pp.105-119.
- Martínez, P., 2015. Customer loyalty: exploring its antecedents from a green marketing perspective. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 27(5), pp.896-917.
- Mazodier, M. and Merunka, D., 2012. Achieving brand loyalty through sponsorship: the role of fit and self-congruity. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 40(6). pp.807-820.
- McCorkle, D. and Payan, J., 2017. Using Twitter in the Marketing and Advertising Classroom to Develop Skills for Social Media Marketing and Personal Branding. *Journal of Advertising Education*, 21(1), p.33.
- Melovic, B., Mitrovic, S. and Vajčnerová, I., 2015. Satisfaction as a determinant of customer loyalty towards mobile communication. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 62(6), pp.1363-1371.
- Merrilees, B., 2017. Experience-centric branding: challenges and advancing a new mantra for corporate brand governance. *Journal of Brand Management*, 24(1), pp.1-13.
- Metaxas, T. and Liapis, A., 2017. Rebranding Syngrou: Changing the image of Syngrou Avenue, in Greece.
- Miquel-Romero, M. J., Caplliure-Giner, E. M. and Adame-Sánchez, C., 2014. Relationship marketing management: Its importance in private label extension. *Journal of Business Research*. 67(5). pp.667-672.
- Mishra, A. A., 2014. Shopping value, satisfaction, and behavioral intentions: a sociodemographic and interproduct category study on private label brands. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 27(4), pp.226-246.
- Mohan Kathuria, L. and Gill, P., 2013. Purchase of branded commodity food products: empirical evidence from India. *British Food Journal*, 115(9), pp.1255-1280.
- Mohd Yasin, N., Nasser Noor, M. and Mohamad, O., 2007. Does image of country-of-origin matter to brand equity?. *Journal of Product & brand management*. 16(1). pp.38-48.

- Mohsin, A. and Lengler, J., 2015. Service experience through the eyes of budget hotel guests: do factors of importance influence performance dimensions? *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 23, pp.23-34.
- Molinillo, S. and et al., 2017. Responsible brands vs active brands? An examination of brand personality on brand awareness, brand trust, and brand loyalty. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*. 35(2). pp.166-179.
- Monfared, N. A., 2015. Impact of advertisement on brand loyalty using structural equation modeling approach. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 4(1 (s)), p.47.
- Mooij, M., 2010. *Global marketing and advertising: understanding cultural paradoxes*. 3rd Edition. California: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Mosca, F., Bertoldi, B. and Giachino, C., 2015. Development Strategies for International Distribution in luxury industry. *International Journal of Management Cases*, 17(3), pp.4-18.
- Mosley, R. W., 2014. Employer brand management. *The Definitive Book of Branding*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, pp.217-240.
- Moss, G. D., 2016. *Pharmaceuticals-Where's the Brand Logic? Branding Lessons and Strategy*. CRC Press.
- Mrkosová, K., Dufek, O. and Majer, L., 2014. Loyalty programmes as a part of company's marketing strategy. *Acta Universitatis Agriculturae et Silviculturae Mendelianae Brunensis*, 59(2), pp.199-204.
- Müller, S. and Piepenstock, I., 2016. Examining the collaboration between human resources and marketing functions within employer branding: A multiple-case study.
- Musa, H., Ab Rahim, N. and Othman, N.A., 2016. Social media marketing and online small and medium enterprises performance: Perspective of Malaysian small and medium enterprises. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 6(7S).
- Nam, C., Dong, H. and Lee, Y. A., 2017. Factors influencing consumers' purchase intention of green sportswear. *Fashion and Textiles*. 4(1). p.2.
- Ng, S. C., Zhao, X. and Rungtusanatham, J. M., 2014. TQM and brand-building by Chinese original brand manufacturers: impact on business performance. *International Journal of Production Research*, 52(3), pp.825-846.
- Nguyen, B. and et al., 2016. Critical brand innovation factors (CBIF): Understanding innovation and market performance in the Chinese high-tech service industry. *Journal of Business Research*. 69(7). pp.2471-2479.
- Nikraftar, T. and et al., 2016. Factors affecting entrepreneurial opportunities recognition in tourism small and medium sized enterprises. *Tourism Review*. 71(1). pp.6-17.
- Nolan, L., 2015. The impact of executive personal branding on non-profit perception and communications. *Public Relations Review*. 41(2). pp.288-292.
- Noyan, F. and Şimşek, G. G., 2014. The antecedents of customer loyalty. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 109, pp.1220-1224.
- O'Brien, K., 2017. Employer branding through social media platforms in financial consulting companies.
- Odoom, R., Odoom, R. and Boateng, R., 2017. Branding in small-and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) Current issues and research avenues. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 20(1), pp.68-89.
- Oh, J., Shin, J. and Park, G., 2016. The Relationship among Brand Personality, Brand Trust, Brand Attachment, and Purchase Intention. *인터넷전자상거래연구*. 16(2).pp.215-230.
- Okonkwo, U., 2016. *Luxury fashion branding: trends, tactics, techniques*. Springer.

- Osakwe, C. N., Chovancova, M. and Ogbonna, B. U., 2016. Linking SMEs profitability to brand orientation and market-sensing capability: A service sector evidence. *Periodica Polytechnica. Social and Management Sciences*. 24(1). p.34.
- Osman, Z. and Sentosa, I., 2013. Mediating effect of customer satisfaction on service quality and customer loyalty relationship in Malaysian rural tourism.
- Özdemir, G., 2016. IMC Strategies of Festivals in Destination Branding. *Strategic Innovative Marketing: 4th IC-SIM, Mykonos, Greece 2015*, p.131.
- P. Becerra, E. and Badrinarayanan, V., 2013. The influence of brand trust and brand identification on brand evangelism. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 22(5/6), pp.371-383.
- Padfield, R. and et al., 2016. Landscapes in transition: an analysis of sustainable policy initiatives and emerging corporate commitments in the palm oil industry. *Landscape Research*. 41(7). pp.744-756.
- Panchal, S.K., Khan, B.M. and Ramesh, S., 2012. Importance of 'brand loyalty, brand awareness and perceived quality parameters' in building brand equity in the Indian pharmaceutical industry. *Journal of Medical Marketing*. 12(2). pp.81-92.
- Panda, D. and Reddy, S., 2016. Resource based view of internationalization: evidence from Indian commercial banks. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*. 10(1). pp.41-60.
- Pansari, A. and Kumar, V., 2017. Customer engagement: the construct, antecedents, and consequences. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*. 45(3). pp.294-311.
- Papadimitriou, D., Apostolopoulou, A. and Kaplanidou, K., 2016, January. Participant-based brand image perceptions of international sport events: The case of the Universiade. In *Journal of convention & event tourism* (Vol. 17, No. 1, pp. 1-20). Routledge.
- Papadimitriou, D., Kaplanidou, K. K. and Papacharalampous, N., 2016. Sport event-sponsor fit and its effects on sponsor purchase intentions: a non-consumer perspective among athletes, volunteers and spectators. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*. 31(2). pp.247-259.
- Papasolomou, I., Crowther, D. and Capaldi, N., 2016. Cause-related marketing: Doing good for your company and your cause. *The Ashgate Research Companion to Corporate Social Responsibility*, p.387.
- Pappu, R. and Quester, P., 2016. Brand innovativeness effects on perceived quality, satisfaction and loyalty. In *Looking Forward, Looking Back: Drawing on the Past to Shape the Future of Marketing* (pp. 763-763). Springer International Publishing.
- Park, E. and Kwon, S. J., 2017. What motivations drive sustainable energy-saving behavior?: An examination in South Korea. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 79. pp.494-502.
- Paulsen, C., 2019. Cybersecuring small businesses. *Computer*. 49(8). pp.92-97.
- Pawaskar, P. and Goel, M., 2014. A conceptual model: Multisensory marketing and destination branding. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 11, pp.255-267.
- Pearson, D. and Pearson, T., 2017. Branding Food Culture: UNESCO Creative Cities of Gastronomy. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*. 23(3). pp.342-355.
- Phua, J., Jin, S. V. and Kim, J. J., 2017. Gratifications of using Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, or Snapchat to follow brands: The moderating effect of social comparison, trust, tie strength, and network homophily on brand identification, brand engagement, brand commitment, and membership intention. *Telematics and Informatics*. 34(1). pp.412-424.
- Pickering, M. E., 2017. Post-acquisition integration processes in publicly owned professional service companies: Senior professional behaviour and company performance. *Journal of Organisational Behavior*.

- Pike, S. D., 2013. Measuring a destination's brand equity between 2003 and 2012 using the consumer-based brand equity (CBBE) hierarchy. *8th Consumer Psychology of Tourism, Hospitality & Leisure Sy.*
- Pittz, T.G., and et al., 2017. Opportunity or Opportunism?: An Examination of International Recruitment via Employer and Nation Branding Strategies. *Business and Professional Ethics Journal*. 36(2). pp.157-176.
- Plangger, K. and Watson, R. T., 2015. Balancing customer privacy, secrets, and surveillance: Insights and management. *Business Horizons*, 58(6), pp.625-633.
- Pohjola, M., 2020. Branding a family business.
- Pongjit, C. and Beise-Zee, R., 2015. The effects of word-of-mouth incentivization on consumer brand attitude. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 24(7), pp.720-735.
- Ponnam, A. and Balaji, M.S., 2015. Investigating the effects of product innovation and ingredient branding strategies on brand equity of food products. *British Food Journal*. 117(2). pp.523-537.
- Popp, B. and Woratschek, H., 2016. Introducing branded communities in sport for building strong brand relations in social media. *Sport Management Review*, 19(2), pp.183-197.
- Prakash, G. and Pathak, P., 2017. Intention to buy eco-friendly packaged products among young consumers of India: A study on developing nation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 141. pp.385-393.
- Pride, W.M. and Ferrell, O.C., 2010. *Marketing. 15th International Edition*. Mason, Ohio, United Kingdom: South-Western.
- Pucci, T., Pucci, T. and Zanni, L., 2017. Place branding-exploring knowledge and positioning choices across national boundaries: The case of an Italian superbrand wine. *British Food Journal*, 119(8), pp.1915-1932.
- Pullman M.E. And Gross M.A., 2004. Ability of experience design elements to elicit emotions and loyalty behaviors. *Decision Sciences*, 35(3), 551-578.
- Punyatoya, P., 2014. Evaluation of branding strategies for global versus local brand: the role of concept consistency. *International Journal of Business Excellence*. 7(1). pp.112-128.
- Punyatoya, P., 2014. Linking environmental awareness and perceived brand eco-friendliness to brand trust and purchase intention. *Global Business Review*, 15(2), pp.279-289.
- Punyatoya, P., 2015. Effect of perceived brand environment-friendliness on Indian consumer attitude and purchase intention: An integrated model. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 33(3), pp.258-275.
- Pyper, K. L. and Gounaris, S., 2016, August. Global branding in a B2B setting: investigating international brand management as driver of export performance. American Marketing Association.
- Qi, J. Y., Qu, Q. X. and Li, L., 2015. The impact of users' characteristics on customer lifetime value raising: evidence from mobile data service in China. *Information Technology and Management*, 16(4), pp.273-290.
- Quan, H., 2016. *Assessing the Impact of Festival Brand Congruency on Destination Brands Using Schema Theory* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Quoquab, F., Pahlevan, S. and Thurasamy, R., 2017. Factors affecting consumers' intention to purchase counterfeit product: Empirical study in the Malaysian market. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, (just-accepted). pp.00-00.
- Rahman, M. K., 2014. Empirical evaluation of customer loyalty in Malaysian retail outlets. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 2(2), pp.129-143.

- Ramiz, M., Qasim, M. and Khurshid, A., 2014. The Comparative Analysis of the Factors Effecting Brand Loyalty towards Samsung Products. *Journal of Sociological Research*, 5(1), pp.327-349.
- Rathod, C. B. and Bhatt, N. H., 2014. Determinants of Customer Loyalty: A Study in the Context of Private Label Apparel Stores in India. *IUP Journal of Brand Management*, 11(1), p.47.
- Reimann, O. and Wagner, U., 2016. The Potential of Co-branding as a Branding Strategy for Premium Private Labels: A Theoretical Assessment. In *Advances in National Brand and Private Label Marketing* (pp. 91-94). Springer International Publishing.
- Rexhepi, G. and et al., 2017. Models and strategies of family businesses internationalization: A conceptual framework and future research directions. *Review of International Business and Strategy*. 27(2). pp.248-260.
- Reza Jalilvand, M. and Samiei, N., 2012. The effect of electronic word of mouth on brand image and purchase intention: An empirical study in the automobile industry in Iran. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*. 30(4). pp.460-476.
- Rigas, D., Hussain, H. A. and Riaz, N., 2017. Online Branding and Marketing: A User Perspective. In *Advertising and Branding: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications* (pp. 31-44). IGI Global.
- Rindell, A., 2017. CORPORATE IMAGE HERITAGE. *Foundations of Corporate Heritage*. pp.275.
- Robertson, J., 2016. Marketing masculinity, branding the book: Current gender trends in the presentation of selected boys' adventure novels. *Journal of Language and Cultural Education*. 4(3). pp.257-267.
- Robertson, J.T., Hurst, T., Williams, K. and Kieth, L., 2017. The Potential Return on Investment of the Recruitment Strategies for an Academic Unit Focused on Agricultural Sciences. *Journal of Applied Communications*, 101(2), p.6.
- Rocha, C. M. and Fink, J. S., 2017. Attitudes toward attending the 2016 Olympic Games and visiting Brazil after the games. *Tourism Management Perspectives*. 22. pp.17-26.
- Romaniuk, J., Dawes, J. and Nenycz-Thiel, M., 2014. Generalizations regarding the growth and decline of manufacturer and store brands. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 21(5), pp.725-734.
- Roncha, A. and Radclyffe-Thomas, N., 2016. How TOMS' "one day without shoes" campaign brings stakeholders together and co-creates value for the brand using Instagram as a platform. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*, 20(3), pp.300-321.
- Rosenbaum-Elliott, R., Percy, L. and Pervan, S., 2015. *Strategic brand management*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- Rosethorn, H., 2016. *The employer brand: Keeping faith with the deal*. CRC Press.
- Roustasekehravani, A., Hamid, A. B. A. and Pooladireishahri, M., 2014. Does brand personality really enhance satisfaction and loyalty toward brand? A review of theory and empirical research. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(25), pp.174-183.
- Ruane, L. and Wallace, E., 2013. Generation Y females online: insights from brand narratives. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 16(3), pp.315-335.
- Rubio, N., Oubiña, J. and Villaseñor, N., 2014. Brand awareness–Brand quality inference and consumer's risk perception in store brands of food products. *Food quality and preference*. 32. pp.289-298.
- Ryan, J. and Silvanto, S., 2013. The critical role of corporate brand equity in B2B marketing: An example and analysis. *The Marketing Review*, 13(1), pp.38-49.

- Saleem, H. and Raja, N. S., 2014. The impact of service quality on customer satisfaction, customer loyalty and brand image: Evidence from hotel industry of Pakistan. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*. 19(5). pp.706-711.
- Sam, G. A. and Daniel, S. P., 2011. *Research Methodology*. Gyan Publishing House.
- Samiee, S. and et al., 2016. Fifty Years of Empirical Research on Country-of-Origin Effects on Consumer Behavior: A Meta-Analysis. In *Rediscovering the Essentiality of Marketing* (pp. 505-510). Springer International Publishing.
- Sandbacka, J., Nätti, S. and Tähtinen, J., 2013. Branding activities of a micro industrial services company. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 27(2), pp.166-177.
- Sasmita, J. and Mohd Suki, N., 2015. Young consumers' insights on brand equity: Effects of brand association, brand loyalty, brand awareness, and brand image. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*. 43(3). pp.276-292.
- Saunders, M. et al., 2009. *Research Methods for Business Students*, Harlow: Prentice Hall.
- Schatz, M., Popovic, A. and Dervin, F., 2017. From PISA to national branding: exploring Finnish education®. *Discourse: Studies in the Cultural Politics of Education*. 38(2). pp.172-184.
- Schroeder, J., Borgerson, J. and Wu, Z., 2016. A Brand Culture Perspective on Global Brands. *The Routledge Companion to Contemporary Brand Management*. pp.153.
- Seetharaman, A. and et al., 2017. A Study of the Moderate Growth of Online Retailing (Ecommerce) In the UAE. *The Journal of Developing Areas*. 51(4). pp.397-412.
- Šeric, M., Gil-Saura, I. and Ozretić-Došen, Đ., 2015. Insights on integrated marketing communications: implementation and impact in hotel companies. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 27(5), pp.958-979.
- Seyedghorban, Z., Matanda, M.J. and LaPlaca, P., 2016. Advancing theory and knowledge in the business-to-business branding literature. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(8), pp.2664-2677.
- Shah, P., 2015. Kill it or keep it? The weak brand retain-or-discard decision in brand portfolio management. *Journal of Brand Management*, 22(2), pp.154-172.
- Shaltoni, A. M., 2017. From websites to social media: exploring the adoption of internet marketing in emerging industrial markets. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, (just-accepted). pp.00-00.
- Shamim, A. and Mohsin Butt, M., 2013. A critical model of brand experience consequences. *Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Logistics*, 25(1), pp.102-117.
- Shamim, A., Ghazali, Z. and Albinsson, P. A., 2016. An integrated model of corporate brand experience and customer value co-creation behaviour. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 44(2), pp.139-158.
- Shams, S. R., 2015. Stakeholders' perceptions and reputational antecedents: a review of stakeholder relationships, reputation and brand positioning. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, 12(3), pp.314-329.
- Shieh, H. S. and Lai, W. H., 2017. The relationships among brand experience, brand resonance and brand loyalty in experiential marketing: Evidence from smart phone in Taiwan. *Journal of Economics & Management*. 28.
- Shimp, T.A., 2010. *Advertising, promotion, and other aspect of integrated marketing communications*. USA: South-Western Cengage Learning.
- Shukla, P., Banerjee, M. and Singh, J., 2016. Customer commitment to luxury brands: Antecedents and consequences. *Journal of Business Research*. 69(1). pp.323-331.

- Siala, H., 2013. Religious influences on consumers' high-involvement purchasing decisions. *Journal of services marketing*, 27(7), pp.579-589.
- Simon, C., Simon, C. and Fassnacht, M., 2016. The impact of external social and internal personal forces on consumers' brand community engagement on Facebook. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 25(5), pp.409-423.
- Singh, K. Y., 2010. *Research Methodology*. APH Publishing.
- Sobihah, M., Mohamad, M. and Ismail, W. Z. W., 2015. E-commerce service quality on customer satisfaction, belief and loyalty: a proposal. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(2), p.260.
- Solomon, M.R., 2014. *Consumer behavior: Buying, having, and being* (Vol. 10). Engelwood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Song, H. J. and et al., 2017. Identifying antecedents and outcomes of festival satisfaction: The case of a cosmetics & beauty expo. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. 29(3). pp.947-965.
- Spry, A., Pappu, R. and Cornwell, T. B., 2011. Celebrity endorsement, brand credibility and brand equity. *European journal of marketing*. 45(6). pp.882-909.
- Stan, V., 2015. Does Consumer Gender Influence the Relationship Between Consumer Loyalty and Its Antecedents? *Journal of Applied Business Research*, 31(4), p.1593.
- Steenkamp, J. B., 2017. *Global Brand Strategy: World-wise Marketing in the Age of Branding*. Springer.
- Stephenson, A. L., Heckert, A. and Yerger, D. B., 2016. College choice and the university brand: exploring the consumer decision framework. *Higher Education*. 71(4). pp.489-503.
- Strebinger, A., 2014. Rethinking brand architecture: a study on industry, company-and product-level drivers of branding strategy. *European Journal of Marketing*. 48(9/10). pp.1782-1804.
- Sturgeon, T. and et al., 2016. Brazil in Global Value Chains.
- Subramanian, N., Gunasekaran, A. and Gao, Y., 2016. Innovative service satisfaction and customer promotion behaviour in the Chinese budget hotel: an empirical study. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 171, pp.201-210.
- Suh, J.H., 2017. *The effects of e-word-of-mouth via social media on destination branding: An empirical investigation on the influences of customer reviews and management responses* (Doctoral dissertation, Michigan State University).
- Suhartanto, D. and Triyuni, N. N., 2016. Tourist loyalty toward shopping destination: the role of shopping satisfaction and destination image. *European Journal of Tourism Research*. 13. p.84.
- Sujchaphong, N., Nguyen, B. and Melewar, T. C., 2017. Towards a branding oriented higher education sector: An overview of the four perspectives on university marketing studies. *The Marketing Review*, 17(1), pp.87-116.
- Sun, S., Tong, K. T. and Law, R., 2017. Chinese hotel guest perception of international chain hotels under the same hotel brand in different travel destinations: The cases of intercontinental and Sheraton. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 23(2), pp.172-188.
- Szymoszkowskyj, A. and et al., 2016. Professional football clubs retail branding strategies. *Sport, Business and Management: An International Journal*. 6(5). pp.579-598.
- Tabaku, E. and Zerellari, M., 2015. Brand loyalty and loyalty programmes; a literature review. *Romanian Economic and Business Review*, 10(2), p.87.
- Temporal, P., 2014. *Branding for the public sector: Creating, building and managing brands people will value*. John Wiley & Sons.

- Thomas, R. J., 2015. Out with the old and in with the new: a study of new kit sponsorship and brand associations in the Barclays Premier League. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 24(3), pp.229-251.
- Thompson, A. J., 2017. Communication and social media. *Understanding Sport Management: International Perspectives*. p.215.
- Tiago, M.T.P.M.B. and Veríssimo, J.M.C., 2014. Digital marketing and social media: Why bother?. *Business Horizons*. 57(6). pp.703-708.
- Tingchi Liu, M., Anthony Wong, I. and L. Brock, J., 2014. The impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) performance and perceived brand quality on customer-based brand preference. *Journal of Services Marketing*. 28(3). pp.181-194.
- Tingchi Liu, M., Anthony Wong, I. and Tseng, T.H., 2014. Do perceived CSR initiatives enhance customer preference and loyalty in casinos? *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 26(7), pp.1024-1045.
- Todor, R. D., 2014. The importance of branding and rebranding for strategic marketing. *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov. Economic Sciences. Series V*, 7(2), p.59.
- ToHan, H., 2017. Acculturation of brand. Strategic design for European luxury fashion brands in china consumer market. *Polimi design phd_017: 10 PhD thesis on Design as we do in POLIMI*. pp.101-110. *urism Management*. 61. pp.443-450.
- Tollin, K. and Christensen, L. B., 2017. Sustainability Marketing Commitment: Empirical Insights About its Drivers at the Corporate and Functional Level of Marketing. *Journal of Business Ethics*. pp.1-21.
- Tong, C. and Wong, A., 2014. The influences of corporate social responsibility to customer repurchases intentions, customer word-of-mouth intentions and customer perceived food quality of fast-food restaurants in Hong Kong and the mediating effects of corporate reputation. *British Journal of Economics, Management & Trade*, 4(11), pp.1655-1678.
- Tripathi, M. N., 2014. Customer Satisfaction and Engagement-Customer Retention strategies for brand manager. *Vilakshan: The XIMB Journal of Management*, 11(1).
- Trudeau H, S. and Shobeiri, S., 2016. Does social currency matter in creation of enhanced brand experience? *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 25(1), pp.98-114.
- Tsai, Y. H., Joe, S. W. and Shen, K.T., 2015. Exploring corporate citizenship and purchase intention: mediating effects of brand trust and corporate identification. *Business ethics: A European review*, 24(4), pp.361-377.
- Tungate, M., 2009. *Luxury world: the past, present, and future of luxury brands*. London: Kogan Page Limited.
- Ulfat, S., Muzaffar, A. and Shoaib, M., 2014. To Examine the Application and Practicality of Aakers' Brand Equity Model in Relation with Recurrent Purchases Decision for Imported Beauty Care products (A study of female customers of Pakistan). *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(11), pp.120-133.
- Uribe, R., 2016. Separate and joint effects of advertising and placement. *Journal of Business Research*. 69(2). pp.459-465.
- Vaishnavi, G., Ganesh, S. K. G. and Thomas, C. V., 2014. Environmental Behaviour of Consumers vis-à-vis Customer Relationship, Trust and Loyalty: Some Research Reflections and Organisational Practices. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 6(2), p.85.
- Valaei, N. and et al., 2016. The effect of culture on attitude towards online advertising and online brands: applying Hofstede's cultural factors to internet marketing. *International Journal of Internet Marketing and Advertising*. 10(4). pp.270-301.

- Vanwesenbeeck, I., Ponnet, K. and Walrave, M., 2017. Young adolescents' advertising literacy and purchase intention in social network games: Influence of perspective taking and need for cognition. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*, 16(1). pp.23-33.
- Varey, R. J., 2015. Corporate reputation and the discipline of marketing communication. In *Handbook of Communication and Corporate Reputation* (p. 104). Wiley Blackwell.
- Vasanth, S. and Vinoth, K., 2017. The Key Factors of Employer Brand an Empirical Analysis with Special Reference to IT Industry. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research & Development*, 8(2).
- Veljković, S. and Kaličanin, Đ., 2016. Improving business performance through brand management practice. *Economic Annals*, 61(208), pp.137-167.
- Veloutsou, C., Veloutsou, C. and Guzmán, F., 2017. The evolution of brand management thinking over the last 25 years as recorded in the Journal of Product and Brand Management. *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 26(1). pp.2-12.
- Venkatesh, U., 2017. Branding Impetus for Start-Ups. *Global Entrepreneurship and New Venture Creation in the Sharing Economy*. pp.54.
- Vinh, T. T., 2016. The relationships among brand equity, brand preference, and purchase intention: empirical evidence from the motorbike market in Vietnam. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 8(3), p.75.
- Vu, M. V. and Huan, H. H., 2016. The relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty: An investigation in Vietnamese retail banking sector. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 8(2).
- Wahab, N. A., Hassan, L. F. A. and Maon, S. N., 2016. The Relationship Between Marketing Mix and Customer Loyalty in Hijab Industry: The Mediating Effect of Customer Satisfaction. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 37, pp.366-371.
- Wallace, A. P. M., Lings, I. and Sheldon, N., 2014. Attracting and retaining staff: the role of branding and industry image. In *Workforce development* (pp. 19-36). Springer Singapore.
- Walsh, P.R. and Dodds, R., 2017. Measuring the Choice of Environmental Sustainability Strategies in Creating a Competitive Advantage. *Business Strategy and the Environment*.
- Wang, C. L., Wang, C. L. and Barnes, B.R., 2017. Brand management and consumer experience in emerging markets: directions for future research. *International Marketing Review*, 34(4), pp.458-462.
- Wang, C.L., Wang, C.L., He, J., He, J., Barnes, B.R. and Barnes, B.R., 2017. Brand management and consumer experience in emerging markets: directions for future research. *International Marketing Review*, 34(4), pp.458-462.
- Wang, H. J. and Horng, S. C., 2016. Exploring green brand associations through a network analysis approach. *Psychology & Marketing*, 33(1), pp.20-35.
- Wang, J., 2016. *Understanding Cleveland as a Sports Destination: an Empirical Study of Brand Personality Theory* (Doctoral dissertation, Kent State University).
- Wang, W., 2017. The Impacts of Dialectical Thinking and Perceived Fit Between Brand Personalities on Cobrand Evaluations. In *Marketing at the Confluence between Entertainment and Analytics* (pp. 1023-1028). Springer, Cham.
- Wang, X. and Yang, Z., 2010. The effect of brand credibility on consumers' brand purchase intention in emerging economies: The moderating role of brand awareness and brand image. *Journal of Global Marketing*, 23(3). pp.177-188.

- Wang, Z., Wang, X. and Guo, D., 2017. Policy implications of the purchasing intentions towards energy-efficient appliances among China's urban residents: Do subsidies work?. *Energy Policy*. 102. pp.430-439.
- Whiteley, M. A. and Whiteley, J., 2006. The familiarization study in qualitative research: from theory to practice. *Qualitative Research Journal*. 6(1). pp.69–85.
- Williams Jr, R.L. and Williams, H.A., 2017. Origins of Today's Marketing and Branding Strategies. In *Vintage Marketing Differentiation* (pp. 1-4). Palgrave Macmillan US.
- Williams, M. D. and et al., 2017. Risk, Trust, and Compatibility as Antecedents of Mobile Payment Adoption.
- Wilson, J.A. and Hollensen, S., 2013. Assessing the implications on performance when aligning customer lifetime value calculations with religious faith groups and after lifetime values—a Socratic elenchus approach. *International Journal of Business Performance Management*, 14(1), pp.67-94.
- Wirtz, J., Den Ambtman, A. and Kandampully, J., 2013. Managing brands and customer engagement in online brand communities. *Journal of Service Management*. 24(3). pp.223-244.
- Wolny, J. and Mueller, C., 2013. Analysis of fashion consumers' motives to engage in electronic word-of-mouth communication through social media platforms. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 29(5-6), pp.562-583.
- Wu, L., 2017. Relationship building in nation branding: The central role of nation brand commitment. *Place Branding and Public Diplomacy*. 13(1). pp.65-80.
- Wu, S. I. and Wang, W. H., 2014. Impact of CSR perception on brand image, brand attitude and buying willingness: a study of a global café. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 6(6), p.43.
- Xie, L.S., Peng, J. M. and Huan, T. C., 2014. Crafting and testing a central precept in service-dominant logic: Hotel employees' brand-citizenship behaviour and customers' brand trust. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 42, pp.1-8.
- Yang, F. X., 2017. Effects of restaurant satisfaction and knowledge sharing motivation on eWOM intentions: the moderating role of technology acceptance factors. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 41(1), pp.93-127.
- Yang, H. L. and Wu, W. P., 2016. The Effects of Consumers' Belief regarding Internet Rumours on Purchases Intention from Different Spreading Channels.
- Yang, W. and S. Mattila, A., 2014. Do affluent customers care when luxury brands go mass? The role of product type and status seeking on luxury brand attitude. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 26(4), pp.526-543.
- Yigitcanlar, T., Guaralda, M., Taboada, M. and Pancholi, S., 2016. Place Making for Knowledge Generation and Innovation: Planning and Branding Brisbane's Knowledge Community Precincts. *Journal of Urban Technology*, 23(1), pp.115-146
- Zavattaro, S. M. and Adams, F. G., 2016. Bridging the gap: An exploration of how DMO managers use education to overcome challenges. *Urban Studies*. 53(4). pp.669-688.
- Zenker, S. and Jacobsen, B. P. eds., 2015. *Inter-regional place branding: Best practices, challenges and solutions*. Springer.
- Zenker, S., Braun, E. and Petersen, S., 2017. Branding the destination versus the place: The effects of brand complexity and identification for residents and visitors. *Tourism Management*, 58, pp.15-27.

- Zentes, J., Morschett, D. and Schramm-Klein, H., 2017. Retail Branding and Positioning. In *Strategic Retail Management* (pp. 185-206). Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden.
- Zerfass, A. and Winkler, L., 2016. Corporate Communication in SMEs: Unveiling an Ignored Field of Practice. In *The Management Game of Communication* (pp. 265-286). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.
- Zhang, J., and et al., 2013. Ingredient branding strategies in an assembly supply chain: models and analysis. *International Journal of Production Research*. 51(23-24). pp.6923-6949.
- Zhang, J., Shabbir, R., Pitsaphol, C. and Hassan, W., 2014. Creating brand equity by leveraging value creation and consumer commitment in online brand communities: A conceptual framework. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 10(1), p.80.
- Zhang, M., Liu, X. and Yang, J., 2017. Why should I pay for e-books? An empirical study to investigate Chinese readers' purchase behavioural intention in the mobile era. *The Electronic Library*. 35(3).
- Zhao, W., Sun, R. and Kakuda, N., 2017. Institutionalized place branding strategy, interfirm trust, and place branding performance: Evidence from China. *Journal of Business Research*.
- Zhu, Z., 2017. THE STUDY OF APPLYING DESTINATION BRANDING TO BUSINESS CLUSTERS.
- Sürücü, Ö., Öztürk, Y. and Bilgihan, A., 2019. Brand awareness, image, physical quality and employee behavior as building blocks of customer-based brand equity: Consequences in the hotel context. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 40, pp.114-124.
- Dedeoğlu, B.B., van Niekerk, M. and Okumuş, F., 2020. Effect of social media sharing on destination brand awareness and destination quality. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*, 26(1), pp.33-56.
- Cheung, M.L., Pires, G.D. and Rosenberger III, P.J., 2019. Developing a conceptual Model for examining social media marketing effects on brand awareness and brand image. *International Journal of Economics and Business Research*, 17(3), pp.243-261.
- Samran, Z., Wahyuni, S. and Putri, A., 2019. Determination of Digital Marketing Strategies as Effective Communication Techniques for GoOntravel Brand Awareness. *Journal of Research in Marketing*, 9(3), pp.752-757.
- Erkan, I., Gokerik, M. and Acikgoz, F., 2019. The Impacts of Facebook Ads on Brand Image, Brand Awareness, and Brand Equity. In *Handbook of Research on Entrepreneurship and Marketing for Global Reach in the Digital Economy* (pp. 442-462). IGI Global.

Online

- Analysis*. 2006. [Online]. Available through: <<https://www.socialresearchmethods.net/kb/analysis.php>>. [Accessed on 17th June 2017].
- Annetonia, 2012. *Branding Key Words Summary*. [Online]. Available through: <<https://annetonia.wordpress.com/2012/10/10/dut-3/>>. [Accessed on 5th June 2017].
- Atwood, A., 2017. *How to promote your brand effectively*. [Online]. Available through: <<https://www.coxblue.com/how-to-promote-your-brand-effectively/>>. [Accessed on 30th June 2017].
- Dudovskiy, J., 2016. *Data Analysis*. [Online]. Available through: <<http://research-methodology.net/research-methods/data-analysis/>>. [Accessed on 17th June 2017].

- Kear, J., 2014. *5 most effective marketing tactics for an event planning business*. [Online]. Available through: <<https://blog.planningpod.com/2014/03/12/5-effective-marketing-tactics-event-planning-business/>>. [Accessed on 30th June 2017].
- Lake, L., 2017. *Why Branding Is Important When It Comes to Marketing*. [Online]. Available through: <<https://www.thebalance.com/why-is-branding-important-when-it-comes-to-your-marketing-2294845>>. [Accessed on 30th June 2017].
- Vadhani, R. H., 2017. *Marketing & Branding - Key for Survival & Growth*. [Online]. Available through: <<http://www.fibre2fashion.com/industry-article/3860/marketing-branding-key-for-survival-growth?page=2>>. [Accessed on 5th June 2017].
- Walmsley, C., 2014. *How brands can move beyond contend marketing*. [Online]. Available through: <<https://www.theguardian.com/media-network/media-network-blog/2014/jan/08/brands-move-beyond-contend-marketing>>. [Accessed on 30th June 2017].

APPENDIX 1

Interview with managers

1. Do you think there is a direct relationship between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention?
2. Do you think that there is a direct link between the brand and the business's sales strategy?
3. How quality services drive customers towards a repetitive purchase?
4. How a brand makes a huge contribution in maximising the scope of targeted customers?
5. How can you say that the brands can be best promoted through social media?
6. Why is advertising not the only way through which brand promotion can be facilitated?
7. Do you think that adopting the process of networking by using different social media sites is one of the best suitable strategies of branding for an event management firm?
8. Why do you think that branding has a vital contribution in marketing goods and services?
9. Do you think that pricing and Quality are the factors that best describe the purchase intention of buyers?
10. How is branding directly related to the purchase intention of consumers referring to buy a commodity?
11. Do you think that volatility is amongst the best-suited role of branding in an event management company as per the experience of most of the participants?
12. What are your reviews on how employees are important in raising brand loyalty?
13. How price plays a vital role in developing the brand loyalty of the organisation?
14. Why is the engagement of customers important in raising brand loyalty?
15. What is the role of quality of service within the purchase intention of the customer?
16. Do you think your company is taking feedback from clients or customers who are coming for attending events?
17. What other factors would you consider important for buyers except for quality and price?
18. What is the importance of brand awareness for your company?
19. Do you think your company's sales strategy effectively attracts a sufficient number of customers from the market?
20. Do you think that brand perception will be influencing the purchase decision of event industry customers?

APPENDIX 2

Questionnaires for customers

Q1) Do you always go to branded industry?

- Yes always
- Never
- Only when quality is important
- Rarely

Q2) How brands impact your purchasing power?

- Very effective
- Effective
- Average
- Not effective

Q3) Which of the following, according to you, essential to develop a good brand image?

- Quality
- Communication strategies
- Free trials and discount offers
- Competitive Pricing

Q4) Do you trust your branded organisation?

- Yes
- No
- Somewhat
- Do not Know

Q5) On a scale of 1 to 5 Star, how you will rate branded organisation?

- 1 Star
- 2 Star
- 3 Star
- 4 Star
- 5 Star

Q6) What key factors you consider before going for any brands?

- Quality

- Quantity
- Price
- Brand Image

Q7) How do you benefit from choosing branded products?

- Very much
- Average
- Not much
- Do not Know

Q8) How is the brand different from its competitors?

- Very different
- Somewhat Different
- Not different
- Do not know

Q9) How did you first hear about the products?

- TV
- Newspapers
- Internet
- Heard from a friend/relative

Q10) Would you recommend anyone about the brands?

- Definitely not
- not sure
- probably
- definitely

Q11) How likely are you to buy the product in the future?

- Very Unlikely
- Somewhat Unlikely
- Not sure
- Very likely

Q12) According to you, what impacts the brand negatively?

- Quality

- Price
- Quantity
- Marketing

Q13) According to you, which factors impacts positively for brands?

- Quality
- Quantity
- Price
- Marketing

Q14) Does brand inspire loyalty?

- Definitely not
- Probably
- Definitely
- Not sure

Q15) Does the brand can fulfil your desire?

- Very Unlikely
- Somewhat Unlikely
- Not sure
- Very likely

Q16) What do you want from an event management industry?

- Provide high-quality facility
- Loyalty
- Low price
- Customer care

Q17) What are the key factors that influence your intention of purchase?

- Brand Value
- Services quality
- Low Cost
- User feedbacks

Q18) How do you feel after utilising the service of branded products?

- Positive

- Negative
- Neutral
- No feelings

Q19) Does your brand follow all the environmental protection measures?

- Yes
- Somewhat
- No
- Do not know

Q20) What is your recommendation regarding the brand?

- Focus more on quality
- Focus more on quantity
- Focus more on price strategy
- Not required

APPENDIX 3

Colour coding

Favourable	
Neutral	
Unfavourable	

Manager 1

Date: JANUARY 12th

Time: 12 PM

Location: Office of Ticket Desk Piccadilly

Q1) Is there a direct relationship exists between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention?

M1) Yes, I believe that customer prefers brands while selecting event company.

Q2) Is there a direct link between the brand and the sales strategy of the business?

M1) According to this, there is a direct link between the brand and sales strategy of the business.
The sales strategy helps the management to improve their brand value efficiently.

Q3) Does Quality services drive customers towards a repetitive purchase?

M1) Yes, it can be said that quality services drive customers towards repetitive purchase. It is the factor that aid in increasing the productivity of the organisation.

Q4) How does the brand make a huge contribution in maximising the scope of targeted customers?

M1) Brand makes a huge contribution in increasing the scope of target customers in many ways.
One thing I observed in customer behaviour is that customer nowadays become brand conscious.

Q5) How your brands can be best promoted through social media?

M1) According to me, social media is a powerful tool for organisation that aid in promoting the products and services of the organisation efficiently and effectively.

Q6) Why advertising is not the only way through which brand promotion can be facilitated?

M1) I believe that advertisement is essential but not the only way to promote the organisation. There are methods such as the reputation of the brand, customers feedback, etc.

Q7) Do you think that adopting networking using different social media sites is one of the best suitable branding strategies for an event management firm?

M1) I think that social media are highly effective and important in this modern world to connect with customers. These sources are highly effective in developing strong interaction with service users and determining the issues they face.

Q8) Why do you think that branding has a vital contribution in marketing goods and services?

M1) When customers have a positive perception of their mind with the products and services delivered by the business, it becomes favourable enough to raise sales and profitability.

Q9) Do you think that pricing and Quality are the factors that best describe buyers' purchase intention?

M1) Purchases have different types of preferences and can develop positive perception within their mind. It is identified that when the rate of price is low, then it becomes helpful to attract more and more customers.

Q10) How branding is directly related to the purchase intention of consumers referring to buy a commodity?

M1) The mind of customers can develop a positive perception of the services and products t

Q11) Do you think that volatility is amongst the best-suited role of branding in an event management company as per most participants' experience?

M1) Yes, I think that volatility is among the best-suited roles of branding.

Q12) What are your reviews on how employees are important in raising brand loyalty?

M1) Employees have direct interaction with customers. They can understand the issues or the problems faced by each of the customers, so they are helpful to raise brand loyalty.

Q13) How price plays a vital role in developing brand loyalty of the organisation?

M1) When prices are low, customers tend to use the business's services and products.

Q14) Why engagement of customers is important in raising brand loyalty?

M1) When employees are engaged, they become favourable enough to develop a strong relationship with customers.

Q 15) What is the role of quality of service within the purchase intention of the customer?

M1) At the time of providing service, quality will be majorly impacting the intention of customers.

Q16) Do you think your company is taking feedback from clients or customers who are coming to attend events?

M1) Yes, at my side, I will be taking feedback from clients and customers whom all are attending events.

Q17) What other factors would you consider important for buyers except for quality and price?

M1) Customer's preference is also considered one of the most important factors for buyers except quality or price.

Q18) What is the importance of brand awareness for your company?

M1) Will be important for launching new product and service.

Q19) Do you think that your company's sales strategy is that effective to attract a sufficient number of customers from the market?

M1) Leading with the prospect will be the most important strategy which is most effective to attract several customers from market

Q20) Do you think that brand perception will be influencing the purchase decision of event industry customers?

M1) Brand perception will be resulting from customer experience with the purchase of the product.

Manager 2

Date: 22ND FEBRUARY

Time: 1 PM

Location: Office of TKTS

Q1) Is there a direct relationship exists between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention?

M2) brand enables them to maintain their existing customer base, and it is also useful for getting more recognition from other entities

Q2) Is there a direct link between the brand and the sales strategy of the business?

M2) When sales strategies are applied, then employees can develop a strong relationship with customers.

Q3) Does Quality services drive customers towards a repetitive purchase?

M2): It is important to make sure that there is proper quality of services delivered, and when the service quality is high, then there are repetitive purchases.

Q4) How does the brand make a huge contribution in maximising the scope of targeted customers?

M2) Brand enables developing positive perception within customers' minds and making them purchase the products and services.

Q5) How your brands can be best promoted through social media?

M2) Social media to a greater extent because a large pool of customers are available on the same source

Q6) Why advertising is not the only way through which brand promotion can be facilitated?

M2) With time, many changes have taken place with technology, and there are many other sources available for promotion.

Q7) Do you think that adopting networking using different social media sites is one of the best suitable branding strategies for an event management firm?

M2) Yes, I do think that social media is effective enough for branding strategy.

Q8) Why do you think that branding has a vital contribution in marketing goods and services?

M2) some firms deliver their customers with a similar set of products and services. In order to be different from others, branding is a helpful aspect.

Q9) Do you think that pricing and Quality are the factors that best describe buyers' purchase intention?

M2) Yes, I think that quality and pricing are important factors to make customers make purchase decisions.

Q10) How branding is directly related to the purchase intention of consumers referring to buy a commodity?

M2) Branding is not directly related to the purchase intention of customers.

Q11) Do you think that volatility is amongst the best-suited role of branding in an event management company as per most participants' experience?

M2) No, I do not believe that.

Q12) What are your reviews on how employees are important in raising brand loyalty?

M2) When employees cannot effectively perform their roles, it affects customers' perception, and so the brand gets affected by employees' performance.

Q13) How price plays a vital role in developing brand loyalty of the organisation?

M2) I do not think price makes much difference.

Q14) Why engagement of customers is important in raising brand loyalty?

M2) Involvement of employees is important in order to develop positive perception within the mind of customers.

Q 15) What is the role of quality of service within the purchase intention of the customer?

M2) There is no such role of quality of service within customers' purchase intention as they majorly look at the price of that product.

Q16) Do you think your company is taking feedback from clients or customers who are coming to attend events?

M2) No, I do not think that company is taking any feedback from customers who are coming to attend events

Q17) What other factors would you consider important for buyers except for quality and price?

M2) Both price and quality of product are the only two most important factors that customers prefer the most.

Q18) What is the importance of brand awareness for your company?

M2) This will be called extending to which the customer can recall and recognise the brand or product, or company.

Q19) Do you think that your company's sales strategy is that effective to attract a sufficient number of customers from the market?

M2) Clearing articulating results is the sales strategy that will be most effective for attracting a sufficient number of customer from around the market.

Q20) Do you think that brand perception will be influencing the purchase decision of event industry customers?

M2) This is majorly dealing with awareness and impression about the company which customers are having

Manager 3: From LIFESTYLE TICKETS

Date: 20th APRIL

Time: 2 PM

Location: Leicester square box office

Q1) Is there a direct relationship exists between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention?

M3) Most of the customers are brand conscious, and as a result, they prefer to get services from those entities only to whom they get services frequently.

Q2) Is there a direct link between the brand and the sales strategy of the business?

M3) Focus on brand helps them to encourage customers towards more purchase, and it is also useful in amending the ratio of customer loyalty.

Q3) Does Quality services drive customers towards a repetitive purchase?

M3): Different people have different type of preference. Some may be focused on quality, and some may prefer to price.

Q4) How does the brand make a huge contribution in maximising the scope of targeted customers?

M3) With the help of the brand, the firm can develop a unique place within the mind of customers.

Q5) How your brands can be best promoted through social media?

M3) There are many sites on which advertisements can be provided, and when customers get to view the firm name, again and again, it develops the brand.

Q6) Why advertising is not the only way through which brand promotion can be facilitated?

M3) other sources can also be used for brand promotion.

Q7) Do you think that adopting networking using different social media sites is one of the best suitable branding strategies for an event management firm?

M3) No, I do not think that way as there are other options.

Q8) Why do you think that branding has a vital contribution in marketing goods and services?

M3) As I said earlier, branding enables to development of the unique identity of the goods and the firm.

Q9) Do you think that pricing and Quality are the factors that best describe buyers' purchase intention?

M3) No, pricing and quality are not just the only factors.

Q10) How branding is directly related to the purchase intention of consumers referring to buy a commodity?

M3) Branding is directly related as it enables to raise the sales and profitability.

Q11) Do you think that volatility is amongst the best-suited role of branding in an event management company as per most participants' experience?

M3) I am not sure about this.

Q12) What are your reviews on how employees are important in raising brand loyalty?

M3) Employees should be trained to understand customers' requirement as the brand gets affected by employees.

Q13) How price plays a vital role in developing brand loyalty of the organisation?

M3) Price of the product should be kept comparatively low when compared with competitors.

Q14) Why engagement of customers is important in raising brand loyalty?

M3) Engaging employees help to make them understand the quality of services and products that are delivered.

Q 15) What is the role of quality of service within the purchase intention of the customer?

M3) This plays the most important role in setting up the quality of the product for dealing with customers' intention.

Q16) Do you think your company is taking feedback from clients or customers who are coming to attend events?

M3) Yes, I am taking feedback from my customers who are attending events

Q17) What other factors would you consider important for buyers except for quality and price?

M3) Taking reviews from family and friends will be regarded as an important consideration for quality and price.

Q18) What is the importance of brand awareness for your company?

M3) This will be helping in the formulation of correct feedback and then putting it into the operations of the business.

Q19) Do you think that your company's sales strategy is that effective to attract a sufficient number of customers from the market?

M3) I think starting with niche markets will be regarded as one of the best sales strategies for attracting a significant number of customers.

Q20) Do you think that brand perception will be influencing the purchase decision of event industry customers?

M3) Brand perception is nothing to do with influencing the purchase decision of the event industry customers

Manager 4

Date: 27th JUNE

Time: 2 PM

Location: Office of MCI UK Limited

Q1) Is there a direct relationship exists between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention?

M4) Yes, a direct relationship exists between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention.

Q2) Is there a direct link between the brand and the sales strategy of the business?

M4) Yes, there is a direct link between the brand and sales strategy of the business

Q3) Does Quality services drive customers towards a repetitive purchase?

M4) Yes, quality services drive customers towards repetitive purchase

Q4) How does the brand make a huge contribution in maximising the scope of targeted customers?

M4) Brand enables to make customers recognise the type of services or products provided by the firm.

Q5) How your brands can be best promoted through social media?

M4) There are different types of social sites available in which proper information to customers is provided regarding the products and services.

Q6) Why advertising is not the only way through which brand promotion can be facilitated?

M4) With time there is various type of changes that have taken place, and it has helped in to have direct interaction with service users.

Q7) Do you think that adopting networking by using different social media sites is one of the best suitable branding strategies for an event management firm?

M4) Yes, it is one of the best strategies

Q8) Why do you think that branding has a vital contribution in marketing goods and services?

M4) With branding, people can develop an image and distinguish each of the business to make their purchase decisions.

Q9) Do you think that pricing and Quality are the factors that best describe buyers' purchase intention?

M4) Yes, price and quality play a vital role.

Q10) How branding is directly related to the purchase intention of consumers referring to buy a commodity?

M4) It help customers to make differences in the firms that deliver their customer's similar products and services.

Q11) Do you think that volatility is amongst the best-suited role of branding in an event management company as per most participants' experience?

M4) Yes, I think that volatility is amongst the best-suited role of branding in an event management company as per the experience of most of the participants

Q12) What are your reviews on how employees are important in raising brand loyalty?

M4) Employees have direct interaction with customers, and when they fail to perform their set of roles effectively, it negatively impacts the business and its brand.

Q13) How price plays a vital role in developing brand loyalty of the organisation?

M4) some firms deliver their customer's similar products and services, and when the price is given, they differentiate them.

Q14) Why engagement of customers is important in raising brand loyalty?

M4) When employees are engaged, they can understand their preferences for the products and services. As per the findings made, improvement is made, and raise of customer's satisfaction is raised.

Q 15) What is the role of quality of service within the purchase intention of the customer?

M4) the Only price will be playing a role within the purchase intention of customers

Q16) Do you think your company is taking feedback from clients or customers who are coming to attend events?

M4) No, the company is not taking feedback from client or customers coming to attend events

Q17) What other factors would you consider important for buyers except for quality and price?

M4) Price will be considered too as the most important factor for the customer more than quality.

Q18) What is the importance of brand awareness for your company?

M4) Brand awareness will be helping the company to determine bonding with the company and customers

Q19) Do you think that your company's sales strategy is that effective to attract a sufficient number of customers from the market?

M4) Being flexible will be the most important sales strategy for the company which they are adopting.

Q20) Do you think that brand perception will be influencing the purchase decision of event industry customers?

M4) Yes, the Brand perception will be influencing purchase decision which customer is taking of an event industry

Manager 5

Date: 28th AUGUST

Time: 2 PM

Location: Office of Encore Charing cross

Q1) Is there a direct relationship exists between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention?

M5) Yes, I believe that there is direct relationship exists between the brand of the business and customer purchase intention.

Q2) Is there a direct link between the brand and the sales strategy of the business?

M5) Yes, there is a direct link between the brand and the business's sales strategy.

Q3) Does Quality services drive customers towards a repetitive purchase?

M5) Quality services indeed drive customers towards repetitive purchase.

Q4) How does the brand make a huge contribution in maximising the scope of targeted customers?

M5) Customers are more attracted to the brands. Thus, it makes a huge contribution in maximising the scope of targeted customers.

Q5) How your brands can be best promoted through social media?

M5) Millions of people are registered on social media. With the help of social media marketing, our brand promotes its products on social media.

Q6) Why advertising is not the only way through which brand promotion can be facilitated?

M5) There are various ways other than advertising to felicitate the brand effectively and efficiently.

Q7) Do you think that adopting networking using different social media sites is one of the best suitable branding strategies for an event management firm?

M5) Yes, I believe that adopting the process of networking by using different social media sites is one of the best suitable strategies of branding for an event management firm.

Q8) Why do you think that branding has a vital contribution in marketing goods and services?

M5) Branding helps increase customer attraction and thus lay direct impacts on the marketing of goods and services.

Q9) Do you think that pricing and Quality are the factors that best describe buyers' purchase intention?

M5) No, I do not think that pricing and Quality are the factors that best describe buyers' purchase intention.

Q10) How branding is directly related to the purchase intention of consumers referring to buy a commodity?

M5) Brand attracts the customers and impact their purchase behaviour.

Q11) Do you think that volatility is amongst the best-suited role of branding in an event management company as per most participants' experience?

M5) Yes, I think that volatility impacts the best-suited role of branding.

Q12) What are your reviews on how employees are important in raising brand loyalty?

M5) Employees are an essential part of the organisation and important assets to the management. They help efficiently in raising brand loyalty.

Q13) How price plays a vital role in developing brand loyalty of the organisation?

M5) Price of the product should be kept comparatively low when compared with competitors.

Q14) Why engagement of customers is important in raising brand loyalty?

M5) Involvement of employees is important in order to develop positive perception within the mind of customers.

Q15) What is the role of quality of service within the purchase intention of the customer?

M5) The role of quality service will be to attract more customers

Q16) Do you think your company is taking feedback from clients or customers who are coming to attend events?

M5) No, the company I supposed to take feedback from customers, but certainly, they are not taking

Q17) What other factors would you consider important for buyers except for quality and price?

M5) Innovation is one of the most important factors for a customer other than quality and price

Q18) What is the importance of brand awareness for your company?

M5) brand awareness will be very important for the company.

Q19) Do you think that your company's sales strategy is that effective to attract a sufficient number of customers from the market?

M5) Using leading scoring to prioritising prospects for sales strategy effectively attracts many customers from markets.

Q20) Do you think that brand perception will be influencing the purchase decision of event

industry customers?

M5) Brand perception will influence the purchasing decision of event industry customers

Appendix 4

Evidence of data

The screenshot shows the SPSS Regression output window. The menu bar includes File, Edit, View, Data, Transform, Insert, Format, Analyze, Direct Marketing, Graphs, Utilities, Add-ons, Window, and Help. The toolbar contains icons for file operations, data management, and analysis. The Output window on the left shows a tree view with 'Regression' selected, containing sub-items: Title, Notes, Active Dataset, Variables Entered, Model Summary, ANOVA, Coefficients, and Log.

Regression

[DataSet2] C:\Users\user\AppData\Local\Temp\lijin.sav

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	According to you which factors impacts positively for brands?, How do you benefited by choosing branded products? ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: What are the key factors that influence your intention of purchase?
b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.920 ^a	.847	.844	.380

a. Predictors: (Constant), According to you which factors impacts positively for brands?, How do you benefited by choosing branded products?

Output
 Regression
 Title
 Notes
 Active Dataset
 Variables Entered
 Model Summary
 ANOVA
 Coefficients
 Log

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	77.319	2	38.660	268.030	.000 ^b
	Residual	13.991	97	.144		
	Total	91.310	99			

a. Dependent Variable: What are the key factors that influence your intention of purchase?

b. Predictors: (Constant), According to you which factors impacts positively for brands?, How do you benefited by choosing branded products?

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.239	.163		2.320	.022
	How do you benefited by choosing branded products?	.353	.081	.365	4.376	.000
	According to you which factors impacts positively for brands?	.565	.077	.594	7.332	.000

a. Dependent Variable: What are the key factors that influence your intention of purchase?

	Name	Type	Width	Decimals	Label
1	Doyoualway...	Numeric	12	0	Do you a
2	Howbrandsi...	Numeric	12	0	How bran
3	Whichofthef...	Numeric	12	0	Which of
4	Doyoutrusty...	Numeric	12	0	Do you tr
5	Fromscaleof...	Numeric	12	0	From sca
6	Whatkeyfac...	Numeric	12	0	What key
7	Howdoyoub...	Numeric	12	0	How do y
8	Howisthebra...	Numeric	12	0	How is th
9	Howdifyoufi...	Numeric	12	0	How did y
10	Wouldyoure...	Numeric	12	0	Would yc
11	Howlikelyar...	Numeric	12	0	How likel
12	Accordingto...	Numeric	12	0	Accordin
13	Accordingto...	Numeric	12	0	Accordin
14	Doesbrandi...	Numeric	12	0	Does bra
15	Doesbrandi...	Numeric	12	0	Does bra
16	Whatdoyou...	Numeric	12	0	What do
17	Whatarethe...	Numeric	12	0	What are
18	Howdoyoufe...	Numeric	12	0	How do y
19	Doesyourbr...	Numeric	12	0	Does you
20	Whatarevou...	Numeric	12	0	What are

	Name	Type	Width	Decimals	Label
1	Doyoualway...	Numeric	12	0	Do you always go to branded industry?
2	Howbrandsi...	Numeric	12	0	How brands impacts on your purchasing power?
3	Whichofthef...	Numeric	12	0	Which of the following according to you, essential to develop a good brand image?
4	Doyoutrusty...	Numeric	12	0	Do you trust your branded organisation?
5	Fromscaleof...	Numeric	12	0	From scale of 1 to 5 Star how you will rate branded organisation?
6	Whatkeyfac...	Numeric	12	0	What key factors you consider before going for any brands?
7	Howdoyoub...	Numeric	12	0	How do you benefited by choosing branded products?
8	Howisthebra...	Numeric	12	0	How is the brand different from its competitors?
9	Howdidyoufi...	Numeric	12	0	How did you first hear about the products?
10	Wouldyoure...	Numeric	12	0	Would you recommend anyone about the brands?
11	Howlikelyar...	Numeric	12	0	How likely are you to buy product in the future?
12	Accordingto...	Numeric	12	0	According to you what impacts the brand negatively?
13	Accordingto...	Numeric	12	0	According to you which factors impacts positively for brands?
14	Doesbrandi...	Numeric	12	0	Does brand inspire loyalty?
15	Doesbrandi...	Numeric	12	0	Does brand is able to fulfil your desire?
16	Whatdoyou...	Numeric	12	0	What do you want from an event management industry?
17	Whatarethe...	Numeric	12	0	What are the key factors that influence your intention of purchase?
18	Howdoyoufe...	Numeric	12	0	How do you feel after utilising service of branded products?
19	Doesyourbr...	Numeric	12	0	Does your brand follow all the environmental protections measures?
20	Whatareyou...	Numeric	12	0	What are your recommendation regarding the brand?

Output

- Regression
 - Title
 - Notes
 - Active Dataset
 - Variables Entered
 - Model Summary
 - ANOVA
 - Coefficients
- Log

Regression

[DataSet2] C:\Users\user\AppData\Local\Temp\lijin.sav

Variables Entered/Removed^a

Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	According to you which factors impacts positively for brands?, How do you benefited by choosing branded products? ^b	.	Enter

a. Dependent Variable: What are the key factors that influence your intention of purchase?
 b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.920 ^a	.847	.844	.380

a. Predictors: (Constant), According to you which factors impacts positively for brands?, How do you benefited by choosing branded products?

Appendix 5

Participant consent form

Title of project-

“An Investigation into the relationship between brand awareness and purchasing intention, recommending the suitable sales strategy for a mid-sized event-based company.

Consent to take part in research

I voluntary agree to take part in this study.

I understand that even if I agree, I can withdraw anytime from it.

I can refuse to withdraw my permission from the interview after that data are deleted from it.

I agree to record my voice during the interview

I understand that I will not benefit from taking part in the study.

Name, degree and contact details of the researcher.

Signature of research participant

.....

Signature of participant

.....

Date -

Signature of researcher

I believe participants are giving informed consent to participate in the study

.....

Date -

Participant information sheet

Dear participant

Overview

You have been selected for the study of an investigation into the relationship between brand awareness and purchasing intention, recommending a suitable sales strategy for a mid-sized event-based company.

What is the purpose of the study?

In this study, the researcher will analyse the relationship between brand awareness and purchase intention. This will assist them in making sure that a suitable sales strategy is utilised

so that the firm's business has been expanded and grow.

What you have been asked to do

In this, you have been asked to participate in a confidential and face to face to interview round of 30 minutes. It will be arranged for the time, date, and location of it.

Your data

To maintain data accuracy, it will be quantitative analysis from the interview. In this audio will be recorded of interview.

Will your taking part in the research be confidential?

Yes, all your data will be kept confidential, and the researcher will make sure that your data has not been leaked.

Compensation

You will be provided with refreshment and lunch. Also, travel cost in it will be reimbursed within 7 days of it.

Thank you for reading this information sheet, and we hope to speak with you soon.

Researcher

Ethical approval

Paul Reynolds <Paul.Reynolds@partner.uws.ac.uk>

Wed 30/06/2021 19:39

To:

To whom it may concern

Gaurav filled the Ethical Approval application form in manually and I signed it manually. On the 6 months progress report Gaurav stated he had applied to the School for approval but had not received it. On the 12 months progress report he stated he had applied to the School and had received approval. I am sure he did show me something from the School at the monthly supervision meeting to support his entry made on the 12 months progress report, but I do not have a copy as this was left to the student. Based on the 12 months progress report which stated approval had been gained Gaurav was given permission to proceed.

Regards,

Paul L Reynolds

Dr Paul L Reynolds,
Lead Supervisor/DOS,
30-06-2021

Appendix 6

Section 1: Basic details:

Project title:

"An Investigation in to the relationship between brand awareness and purchasing intention, recommending of the suitable sales strategy for a mid-size event-based company.

Student name: Gaurav Aggarwal

Student ID number: B00299765

Programme: DBA

University Name: University of the West of Scotland

Intended research start date: 02 November 2015

Intended research end date: 14th June 2021.

Section 2 Project summary

Please select all research methods that you plan to use as a part of your project:

Interviews	Yes	No
Questionnaires	Yes	No
Observations	Yes	No
Use of personal records	Yes	No
Data Analysis	Yes	No
Action Research	Yes	No
Focus Groups	Yes	No
Others (Please specify):		

Section 3 : Ethical Issues

Are there any particular features of your proposed work, which may raise ethical concerns? If so, please outline how you will deal with these:

You must demonstrate your awareness of potential risks that may arise because of your

research. Please consider/address all issues that may apply. Ethical concerns may include, but are not limited to the following:

- **Informed consent.**
- Potentially vulnerable participants.
- **Sensitive topics**
- Risk to participants and researchers
- **Confidentiality/anonymity**
- Disclosures/ limits to confidentiality
- Data storage and security, both during and after the research (including transfer, sharing, encryption, protection).
- **Reporting**
- Dissemination and use of your findings.

Section 4 : Declaration

I have read, understood and will abide by the institution's Research and Ethics Policy:

Yes

I have discussed the ethical issues relating to my research with my Unit Tutor:

Yes

I confirm that to the best of my knowledge:

The above information is correct, and this is a full description of the ethical issues that may arise in the course of my research

Name:

Date:

Please submit your completed form to your supervisor and attach it to the Research Proposal when submitting it to Turnitin.